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“Modern Approaches and Pedagogical Innovations in Education”

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Paper 1

STUDY ON EFFICACY OF E- LEARNING

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: E-learning or Online learning refers to a learning environment that uses the web and alternative technological devices and tools for synchronous and asynchronous educational delivery and management of educational programs (Usher & Barak, 2020; Huang, 2019). The Efficacy of Online Learning is gaining quality globally over as a result of many of its options that had contributed to creating the method of education easy. The effectuality of online learning allowed students from across the world to recruit themselves during a form of programs, that is well accessible and permits for a bespoke learning experience. The Efficacy of Online Learning meets the need of an outsized population that will not want to attend a standard schoolroom or students who sleep in remote areas.

Design/Methodology/Approach: Using the theoretical framework by Albert Bandura (1971) with four major sources of efficacy of individuals. the researcher concentrates on studying the efficacy of online learning among Senior Secondary Students of Mangalore Taluk with a sample size of 350 students. A standardized tool titled, ‘An Online Learning Self-Efficacy Scale (OLSES)’ of 22 items by Zimmerman and KuliKomich (2016) is used to check Efficacy of Online Learning. Descriptive Statistics of Mean, Median, Standard Deviation; Graphical Representation Normal Probability Curve and Ogive were used to analyse the data.

Findings/Result: The study concludes that the Efficacy of Online Learning among Senior Secondary Students is normally distributed and it is also observed that 62.8% of the students fall in the category of Moderate self-Efficacy of Online Learning, 21.4% of the Senior Secondary Students are high self- Efficient with Online Learning, 15.85% of the Senior Secondary Students are low Self-Efficient with Online Learning.

Originality/Value: The paper is based on the theoretical framework by Albert Bandura (1971) which assumes, if one has a confidence in completing a task, then there is more probability of being successful in it by this increased level of self-efficacy. There are four major sources of

efficacy of individuals: mastery experiences, social modelling, verbal persuasion and physiological factors.

Paper Type: Survey Research

Keywords: Efficacy, E- Learning, mastery experience, social modelling, verbal persuasion, physiological factors

INTRODUCTION:

The Efficacy of Online Learning is gaining quality globally over as a result of many of its options that had contributed to creating the method of education easy. The effectuality of online learning allowed students from across the world to recruit themselves during a form of programs, that is well accessible and permits for a bespoke learning experience. The Efficacy of Online Learning meets the need of an outsized population that will not want to attend a standard schoolroom or students who sleep in remote areas. The Efficacy of Online Learning not solely stood helpful for college students however additionally clad to be a boon for academics to form the teachings attention-grabbing victimization technology, easy accessibility to the attending of the students, change themselves with new learning methods and technology, and immediate evaluation. Education has modified its ways from traditional to Online Learning which has adversely shown the impact on the tutorial action of the student's and additionally contributed to their varied behaviour patterns.

RELATED WORKS:

Aisha Naz Ansari (2022) concluded that both age groups (young and older) have a certain level of self-efficacy for online learning. It is studied that higher class students have higher self-efficacy than their counterparts. The findings of **Seibel ÖZTÜRK DEMİR's, Esra EREN (2022)** concluded that no significant correlation was found between students' readiness and academic achievement, and Students generally had positive opinions about online learning environment.

Study by Balakamakshi T Y, Dr. R Savithri (2021) concluded that E-learning provides for effective time management and motivates students to learn independently. Thus, it is evident that the world is moving towards it much faster than expected.

Gat Gat, Edi Abdurahman, Dezie L. Warganegara, Wibowo Kosasih(2021) suggested that online learning mediated in the collaborative learning scheme positively and significantly contributed to the remarkable achievement of students' academic achievement.

Nurdiyanti Nurdiyanti(2019) concluded that students get a higher score of learning outcomes who are taught by online learning system. There is an effect of the online learning system toward students' academic

achievement.

Study by Alicia Johnson & Barbara B. Lockee (2018) investigated that it may be beneficial to revisit intervention studies, focusing on strategies to increase academic self-efficacy in online learners, since self-efficacy is malleable and has been shown to have a positive effect on academic success.

The results by Liang-Yi Li, Chin-Chung Tsai (2017) on a study on Accessing online learning material suggested First, the students viewed the learning materials related to their classroom lectures that include audio and video lectures for longer and more often than other learning materials which is shared assignments and posted messages. Second, most did not use annotation tools although the students spent a great deal of time viewing the online learning materials. Third, students' were divided into three behaviour patterns: who intensively used all of the learning materials- “consistent use students”, who intensively used the lecture slides -“slide intensive use students”, and who infrequently used any learning material -“less use students”. These behaviour patterns went along with their motivation and learning performance.

CHENG-YUAN LEE- 2015 found that the course content of self-efficacy and online technologies self-efficacy fluctuated, but task value remained unaffected during the course of the semester.

OBJECTIVE

1. To study the Efficacy of E-Learning among Senior Secondary Students of Mangalore Taluk.

METHODOLOGY:

This paper consists of studying Efficacy of E-Learning among Senior Secondary Students of Mangalore Taluk. In this paper the researcher concentrates on studying the efficacy of online learning among Senior Secondary Students of Mangalore Taluk with a sample size of 350 students. A standardized tool titled, ‘An Online Learning Self-Efficacy Scale (OLSES)’ of 22 items by Zimmerman and KuliKomich (2016) is used to check Efficacy of Online Learning. Descriptive Statistics of Mean, Median, Standard Deviation; Graphical Representation Normal Probability Curve and Ogive were used to analyse the data.

JUSTIFICATION OF THE STUDY

Keeping in mind the advancement in education with the advent of online learning, education is at its best and fulfilling the requirement of the traditional platform. Though the pandemic gave us the boon of online learning, which is effective and at par with the rest of the world. In order to make online learning effective in long run, we need to measure its impact in the short run to see its positive or negative impact and how the problems can be rectified. There are many researchers conducted on online learning and how it's impacting

the education platform, but a very few have seen it as a cause of behavioral change and growth. This study is conducted in Mangalore Taluk to see the Efficacy of online learning among senior secondary students which will also benefit them to know which internal factors are impacted through online learning.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK ON EFFICACY AND E- ELARNING

Bandura has defined self-efficacy as “an individual’s belief that he/she is able to complete a given activity” (Bandura, 1997, p. 3). There is more probability of being successful in it by this increased level of self efficacy if one has a confidence in completing a task, then. Moreover, there are four major sources of efficacy of individuals: mastery experiences, social modelling, verbal persuasion and physiological factors.

Mastery experience is the most effective approach to create strong efficacy among individuals. Bandura believed that success leads to future successes in a particular task while failure leads to obstacles in attempting it again. So, if one is successful in attempting a task, there is a probability of attempting it again.

The second source of Bandura’s self-efficacy theory is **social modelling**. Most people do not like to attempt the tasks which seem impossible to succeed. Bandura emphasized that observing others similar to yourself succeeding in a particular task can motivate you to accomplish the same task easily.

Verbal persuasion is the third source of self-efficacy theory. A great way to build self-efficacy is by receiving positive feedback from others. If a person receives negative feedback, it can lower their self efficacy.

Physiological factors the last source of efficacy. Emotions, moods, physical reactions and stress level could affect tone’s personal abilities. A learner may experience low level of self-efficacy if he/she has negative attitude such as anxiety and stress to perform a task.

Bandura (1993) described higher self-efficacy as that which fosters intrinsic interest and deep engrossment in activities (p.71)” people may have low ambitions and give up easily as a result of lower level of self-efficacy as alternatively mentioned by Bandura.

Higher level of self-efficacy among students is not only a predictor of higher academic performance but also make them able to cope up with demanding situations in their learning experiences.

E-learners who are less confident in their abilities, may be demotivated to learn and in return may achieve lower grades in their online learning environments. Individuals who are enrolled in online learning courses for the first time, can be less confident in using computers so the structure of online courses should be designed to promote the student’s efficacy (Taipjutorus, Hansen & Brown 2012).

Efficacy of Online Learning among Senior Secondary Students has been classified into three categories.

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- **High Efficacy of Online Learning:** Scores of students who have High Efficacy of Online Learning has been given by mean + 1SD
- **Moderate Efficacy of Online Learning:** Scores of students who have Moderate Efficacy of Online Learning has been given by Mean
- **Low Efficacy of Online Learning:** Scores of students who have Low Efficacy of Online Learning has been given by mean - 1SD

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF OBJECTIVE 1

The descriptive statistics namely Mean, Median, Standard Deviation, Graphical representation in the form of probability curve were used. The Smoothed Frequency Curve of the scores on the Efficacy of E-Learning among Senior Secondary Schools is given in Figure 1

Figure 1 Normal Probability Curve representing the scores on Efficacy of E-Learning among Senior Secondary Students of Mangalore Taluk.

Table 2 showing Mean, Median, Standard deviation and Skewness of Efficacy of E-Learning

Variable	N	Mean	Median	Standard Deviation	Skewness
Efficacy of Online Learning	350	51.7	53	8.042	0.201

Efficacy of Online Learning among Senior Secondary Students has been classified into three

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categories.

- **High Efficacy of E-Learning:** Scores of students who have High Efficacy of E-Learning has been given by mean + 1SD
- **Moderate Efficacy of E-Learning:** Scores of students who have Moderate Efficacy of E-Learning has been given by Mean
- **Low Efficacy of E-Learning:** Scores of students who have Low Efficacy of E-Learning has been given by mean - 1SD

Distribution of scores on Efficacy of Online Learning is presented in Table 3 and Figure

Table 3 Distribution of Scores on Efficacy of E-Learning

Efficacy of E-Learning	High	Moderate	Low	Total
Number	75	220	55	350
Percentage	21.4%	62.8%	15.8%	100%

Figure 2: Distribution of scores on Efficacy of E-Learning among senior Secondary Students of Mangalore Taluk.

7.1 INTERPRETATION OF OBJECTIVE 1

The figure 1 shows the smoothed frequency of the scores of Efficacy of E-Learning among senior secondary Students of Mangalore Taluk. The distribution shows that half of the cases fall at the middle portion of the curve. The graph has the shape of Normal Probability Curve.

From the Table 2, it is observed that the Mean value of the scores on Efficacy of E- Learning is 51.7, Median value is 53 and Standard Deviation of the scores is 8.042. The Skewness of the Probability curve is 0.201. Since the obtained Mean value is close to the Median value and the Probability curve having a positive skewness of 0.201, it can be concluded that the scores on Efficacy of E-learning are nearly normally distributed.

Table 3 and Figure 2 shows the percentage of scores on Efficacy of E-learning reveals that 62.8% of the students fall in the category of Moderate Efficacy of E-learning score. Remaining 21.4% in the category of High efficacy of E-learning and 15.85 % in the Low Efficacy of E-learning category. This indicated that the Efficacy of E-learning of senior Secondary students is Moderate and that the distribution of the scores is nearly normal.

7.2 FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

It can be concluded that the Efficacy of E-learning of senior secondary Students is nearly normally distributed. 21.4% of students are having high self-efficacy of E-learning, 62.8% of students possess Moderate Self-efficacy of E-learning, and 15.85% of students possess Low Efficacy of E-learning. The findings revealed that a greater number of students are able to make use of E-learning moderately to fulfil their objective. Although many researchers have emerged in the field of Online Learning, The findings of the present study based of Efficacy of E-learning among Senior Secondary students were supported with the help of the study conducted by Balakamashi TY & Dr. R Savithri (2021).

RECOMMENDATIONS:

The teachers can significantly reduce their teaching load and can make classes interactive and joyful. So, to be successful and motivated in online environments, the students should have IT self-efficacy of two types. Initially to interact with the content provided online, class fellows and instructors, the learners should be efficacious enough in using distance learning mechanisms. Secondly, there should be a liking for the course content by students.

- The results revealed that overall students’ level of self-efficacy was at moderate level. As online learning is students-centred and self-directed therefore, the level of students’ self-efficacy should be improved to perform well in online learning environments.
- Linnenbrink and Pintrich (2002) say motivation and self-efficacy plays a great role in improving students’ academic performance. Therefore, to enhance the performance of students, some measures may be taken to improve self-efficacy of the students.
- Measuring self-efficacy is sometimes restricted to specific academic activities according to Bong (2004). But the current study states that self-efficacy includes academic tasks like depth of the course

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content, preparation for exams and quizzes, and participating in discussions

- With students’ progress to higher classes in school, more autonomy and intellectual freedom is needed. Online learning facilitates pursuing highly individualised learning programmes, possibly even college level courses. These can be highly beneficial to their learning progress combined with hands-on exercises, real world exploration, and thorough assessments. This is done through exploring their options by trying out introductory topics from different fields, before committing to a specialisation.
- Online learning platforms transforms students into independent learners, prior to higher education.

CONCLUSIONS:

The current COVID-19 crisis has shown deep crack in the education system due to the non-penetration of Technology. This can be considered as an eye opener to modify or change the learning methods used in teaching – learning process. The education system is in the dire need of roadmap which shows Technology penetration, teacher training, self-efficiency and addition of necessary infrastructure. Introduction of E-Learning methods such as augmented reality, online quizzes, discussion forums, flipped classrooms can reduce the burden of traditional way of Education amongst students as well as helps teachers to make lessons more interactive and interesting.

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Paper 2

Approaches and Creativity in Teaching Mathematics: A New Research Perspectives

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ABSTRACT

Creative imagination, which uncovers and communicates the underlying meanings of its objects through a process of reconstruction, is the ultimate kind of imagination. Creative imagination elevates the specifics to the level of the universal and gives significance to the relationships between individuals with the growth of the whole. Dewey considers as the basic function of the creative imagination the construction of meanings and their incorporation into perceptible forms, thus expressing the freedom of action of human subjectivity. This paper analyses the importance of imagination and creativity in teaching mathematics in the school curriculum. Also it outlines the different approaches in teaching mathematics.

Design/Methodology/Approach: The research questions of this study are pursued by means of a systematic research analysis. We stress the importance of the advancement of research on creativity in mathematics education. We discuss many methods for teaching mathematics creatively as well as concepts of creativity. We conducted this research through systematically searching and screening for relevant research articles through secondary sources and analysing them with the purpose of answering our scientific study. This research is a descriptive study. The necessary secondary data was collected from various sources, magazines, journals, other publications, etc. This data was then analysed and reviewed to arrive at the inferences and conclusions.

Findings/Result: Creativity, imagination and its development can be the foundation in building a common locus between mathematics and creative endeavours in educational practice.

Keywords: Creativity, Imagination, Mathematics, Approaches.

INTRODUCTION:

The development of students critical thinking, problem-solving, and logical reasoning ability depends heavily on mathematics education. However, rote memorization and repetitive drills are frequently extensively emphasised in traditional ways of teaching mathematics, which may restrict students'

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involvement, creativity, and conceptual comprehension. Researchers have shifted their focus to investigating novel strategies that incorporate creativity into the teaching of mathematics as a result of the realisation that a new viewpoint is required. With an emphasis on the emergence of fresh research viewpoints in this area, this paper attempts to give a general overview of the significance of approaches and creativity in mathematics instruction. While the imagination is unrestricted and limitless in any artistic endeavour, it is constrained in every mathematical endeavour by the knowledge of mathematics itself, which has been crystallised and organised into axiomatic systems, as well as by the rules of deductive logic. On such a ground, the imagination and in particular the creative imagination could be considered a common locus of mathematics and arts in teaching mathematics. For students to be actively involved in the learning process and to develop a deeper comprehension of mathematical concepts, effective teaching methods are essential. Traditional methods, like the lecture-based approach, frequently place an emphasis on procedural knowledge and conventional approaches to problem-solving. Research, however, indicates that different strategies that promote active student involvement, cooperation, and exploration can improve mathematical thinking and problem-solving skills. Inquiry-based learning, project-based learning, problem-based learning, and game-based learning are a few examples of these strategies. These methods give students the chance to strengthen their mathematical reasoning and critical thinking abilities by moving the emphasis from memorizing information to conceptual understanding.

NEED FOR THE STUDY:

Since math instruction has traditionally played a significant role in the educational system, every student should have an equal opportunity to effectively master arithmetic concepts. The role of the teacher, his attitude towards mathematics, and the method of encouraging students that would lead to success in this field are vital if everyone is to have this opportunity (Furner et al., 2005). In most mathematics curricula, students' creative potential is encouraged, but sadly this encouragement typically only occurs at the declarative level, depending on the personal affinities of the teachers, students, and textbook publishers (Koludrovic & Reic Ercegovac, 2010). Teachers frequently reproduce facts and employ inflexible algorithms while teaching maths, which hampers student learning. In mathematics teaching, teachers most often use rigid algorithms and reproduction of facts, which in turn hinders the development of abilities such as divergent thinking, independent recognition of mathematical problems and the development of original solutions to problems (Pinter Krekic & Ivanovic, 2013).

OBJECTIVES

1. To analyse the role of creativity in teaching mathematics and mathematics educations.

2. To evaluate the actions to incorporate creativity into teaching mathematics.
3. Does creativity enhances collaborative learning?
4. To discuss the different approaches in teaching mathematics

METHODOLOGY

The research questions of this study are pursued by means of a systematic research analysis. We conducted this analysis through systematically searching and screening for relevant research articles through various sources and books and analysing them with the purpose of answering our scientific enquiry.

ANALYSIS

Analysis of objectives: 1

The role of creativity in teaching mathematics and mathematics education.

A critical aspect of mathematics, that is frequently ignored in conventional teaching techniques is creativity. Students' ability to view mathematics as a creative endeavour is constrained by the idea that the subject is a strict, rule-based discipline. However, mathematical creativity calls for the capacity for flexible thought, linkages, and the exploration of many approaches to problem-solving. Maths education may be made more engaging for students and help them gain a deeper understanding of the material by infusing creativity into the lesson plans. Students are encouraged to investigate open-ended questions, use mathematical ideas in practical settings, and create their own distinct problem-solving strategies through the use of creative teaching methods. The gender gap can also be closed and under-represented groups can participate more actively if innovation is encouraged in mathematics education.

New Research Perspectives

Innovative strategies for incorporating approaches and creativity into teaching practises have started to be explored in recent mathematics education research. Researchers are looking into the creative potential and student engagement benefits of digital tools like interactive simulations, virtual manipulatives, and educational games. Furthermore, the development of computational thinking and its incorporation into mathematics courses present fresh chances for original problem-solving. The effects of teacher professional development initiatives that emphasise promoting creativity in mathematics classrooms are also being studied by researchers. These programmes are designed to give instructors the information, abilities, and pedagogical techniques they need to effectively foster creativity and engage students in mathematics instruction.

Gradually, approaches that foster creativity, critical thinking, and problem-solving abilities are being

included into the traditional methods of teaching mathematics. Educators may create a setting where students are inspired to think critically, participate actively, and get a deeper understanding of mathematics by embracing these new research approaches. In the end, this change has the potential to revolutionise mathematics teaching and enable pupils to develop into capable problem solvers and lifelong maths learners.

Analysis of objectives: 2.

To incorporate creativity into teaching mathematics

The ability to be creative is essential while teaching maths. It can improve the pupils' comprehension, involvement, and problem-solving abilities. Here are some strategies for adding creativity to maths lessons:

1. Real world applications: Connect mathematical principles to problems in the real world that students can connect to. Display to them the applications of mathematics in industries like engineering, architecture, banking, and even the arts. Students' curiosity is piqued and they are able to better understand the value of mathematics.

2. Problem-based learning: Give pupils riddles or open-ended challenges that call for original thought to answer. Encourage kids to experiment with various techniques, think critically, and examine a variety of ideas. This method encourages innovative problem-solving abilities and a greater comprehension of mathematical ideas.

3. Visual aids and manipulatives: Use visual aids to illustrate abstract mathematical concepts, such as diagrams, graphs, or models. Students can better understand things by using manipulatives like blocks, numbers, or geometric objects to help them visualise them. This practical method can encourage imagination and aid in a deeper comprehension of mathematical concepts.

4. Open-ended inquiries: Ask open-ended inquiries that can be answered in a variety of ways. This enables students to use their imaginations, consider numerous options, and support their arguments. Additionally, it develops students' capacity for critical thought and aids in the growth of their own mathematical intuition.

5. Technology integration: Use interactive simulations, graphing programmes, or educational apps to engage pupils and improve their comprehension of mathematical ideas. Students can discover mathematics in a fun and engaging way with the help of these tools, which can offer interactive and dynamic experiences.

6. Personalization and selection: Give students the chance to tailor their mathematics education. Give them the freedom to select topics or assignments that match their interests. This independence promotes ownership of learning and challenges learners to consider innovative applications of mathematics connects to their lives and passions.

7. Arts integration: Include creative thinking and the arts in maths lessons. Students can, for instance, design tessellations, make geometric art, or look for patterns in nature. This multidisciplinary approach

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fosters a holistic knowledge and allows students to appreciate the beauty and creativity that are innate to mathematics.

Remember that encouraging investigation, critical thinking, and problem-solving requires the creation of an atmosphere in mathematics teaching. We may encourage a creative mentality in our students and make mathematics a fun and interesting subject to study by implementing these techniques.

By implementing these techniques, we can develop an interactive and stimulating learning environment that fosters students' mathematical creativity. These methods not only help them better learn the content, but they also give them valuable problem-solving and critical thinking abilities that go beyond just maths.

Analysis of objectives: 3

Creativity enhances collaborative learning.

Encourage pupils to address problems in groups or pairs by encouraging collaborative learning. Students who work together can exchange concepts, talk about tactics, and benefit from one another's methods. Students can draw from many viewpoints and come up with unique solutions as a group, which encourages creative thinking.

Students can share ideas, learn from one another, and work together to solve challenges when they collaborate. Working together in teams or individuals allows students to discuss different approaches, examine alternate viewpoints, and explain their mathematical thinking. By fostering the sharing of ideas and challenging students to consider many methods to problem-solving critically, collaborative learning promotes creativity.

Analysis of objectives: 4

The different approaches in teaching mathematics.

1. Teaching by inquiry.

Giving students content-related problems to work on during class research is referred to as inquiry teaching. The learners identify the problem once the teacher gives it to them.

The steps in the inquiry process

- A present-day unexpected occurrence or particular challenging circumstance.
- Encourage observation to create a statement of the research's goals.
- Encourage the testing of the hypothesis;
- Develop a tentative conclusion and generalisation;
- Request students' observations and explanations;
- Review the procedure

2. A process of Demonstration.

A teaching technique known as the demonstration approach involves the teacher "in a learning task other than just talking about it". A teaching technique known as the demonstration approach involves the teacher "in a learning task other than just talking about it". To give pupils a visual and practical knowledge of mathematical concepts and procedures, the demonstration technique is frequently employed in mathematics instruction. Here are some concrete examples of how the demonstrative approach might be used to teach maths: The demonstrative approach to teaching maths ought to encourage participation, engagement, and the improvement of problem-solving abilities. be adjustments to your strategy according to your students' grade level and learning preferences, and be sure to strike a balance between teacher-led demonstrations and student participation.

3. Development approach.

"International Learning" is Discovery Learning. Depending on the role the instructor plays, guided discovery (which requires close monitoring) to free or pure discovery (which requires very little supervision), both the learner and the teacher play active roles in discovery learning.

4. Mathematical lab approach.

The Mathematics Laboratory Approach is a teaching strategy in which students in small groups complete a task card or assignment to learn and discover mathematics on their own.

5. PWA, or practical work approach.

In this method, the students engage in activities and/or the manipulation of tangible objects to develop a conceptual grasp of a phenomenon, circumstance, or notion. The environment serves as a laboratory where studies in mathematics or science can be conducted on natural events or phenomena.

6. Module based individualised instruction.

The use of individualised instruction enables students to advance by mastering curriculum steps at their own pace and independently of other students' progress.

7. Brainstorming.

It is a teaching technique in which the teacher obtains as many ideas from the students as possible but holds off on evaluating them until every concept that can be created has been thought brainstorming typically involves four stages.

i) Problem identification, ii) Idea generation, iii) Idea evaluation, iv) solution implementation and evaluation are the first four steps.

8. Problem solving

The most accurate definition of problem-solving is that it is a learner-directed method that requires students to "think patiently and analytically about complex situations in order to find answers to questions." A

circumstance in which you are attempting to achieve a goal and need to find a path there is referred to as a dilemma.

9. Cooperative learning

Eliminating competition among students is made easier through cooperative learning. It motivates them to cooperate to achieve shared objectives. In the classroom, it promotes constructive intergroup attitudes.

10. Integrative technique

The Integrated Curriculum Mode (also known as Integrative Teaching to some) is a "method of teaching and a way of organising the instructional programme so that many subject areas and skills provided in the curriculum can be linked to one another".

RESULTS AND FINDINGS

The findings of the study of creativity in teaching mathematics.

1. Enhancing student engagement:

Increasing student engagement: Students are more engaged and interested in mathematics when it is taught creatively. It helps children develop critical thinking skills, consider alternative strategies, and come up with original ideas. Increased motivation and love of maths can result from this, which can ultimately improve student learning outcomes.

Fostering creative thinking and problem-solving abilities are important aspects of mathematics. Teachers can offer opportunities for students to strengthen their problem-solving skills by infusing creativity into maths lessons. Innovative methods can encourage pupils to think creatively, try out new techniques, and get a deeper comprehension of mathematical ideas.

2. Fostering problem-solving skills:

Fostering creative thinking and problem-solving abilities are important aspects of mathematics. Teachers can offer opportunities for students to strengthen their problem-solving skills by infusing creativity into maths lessons. Innovative methods can encourage pupils to think creatively, try out new techniques, and get a deeper comprehension of mathematical ideas.

3. Encouraging critical thinking:

Critical thinking skills are encouraged via innovative teaching strategies for mathematics. Students are more inclined to challenge assumed facts, examine other viewpoints, and assess mathematical concepts when they are encouraged to think creatively. This fosters a deeper comprehension of mathematical ideas and enhances students' capacity to use their mathematical learning in practical settings.

Researchers are examining fresh viewpoints and cutting-edge tactics to improve teaching practises as the importance of creativity in mathematics education becomes more widely acknowledged.

4. Promoting innovation and originality:

The discipline of mathematics lives on creativity and originality. Teaching with creativity encourages students to explore new concepts, build original mathematical models, and find creative solutions to problems. Innovators and mathematicians of the future are fostered by this.

5. Addressing diverse learning styles:

Differentiation and catering to different learning styles are made possible by creativity in mathematics education. Since not all students learn in the same way, innovative methods can offer different routes for grasping mathematical ideas. Teachers can better meet the needs of various students and encourage diversity in the classroom by providing a variety of learning opportunities and teaching styles.

6. Developing life long learners:

Creativity in mathematics instruction encourages pupils to continue learning throughout their lives. Students who participate in imaginative mathematical activities grow to love mathematics and become curious about it outside of the classroom. They may be motivated by this to pursue additional education in mathematics, related subjects, or professions that call for sharp analytical and problem-solving abilities.

CONCLUSION:

Creativity is one of the essential characteristics of a person. Therefore, it is of great importance that this characteristic is nurtured and developed in students through education. Teaching for creativity and creative teaching should be an integral part of every school subject, including mathematics teaching, which is usually reduced to learning facts without the possibility of entering one's own ideas and solutions. Observing the definitions of mathematical creativity, we can conclude that every type of non-reproductive activity of students, which leads to independent acquisition of knowledge or solving a mathematical problem, is mathematical creativity. In this paper, it is presented how the application of creativity in teaching mathematics can positively affect the acquisition of knowledge in this area in students as well as techniques that can be used in teaching mathematics.

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Paper 3

**A Correlational Study on Soft Skills and Positive Emotions
among the College Students**

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ABSTRACT

Positive Psychology is the scientific study of the strengths that enable individuals and communities to thrive. The field is founded on the belief that people want to lead meaningful and fulfilling lives, to cultivate what is best within themselves and to enhance their experiences of love, work, and play. “Positive Psychology is the scientific study of human flourishing, and an applied approach to optimal functioning. It is "the scientific study of what makes life most worth living", or "the scientific study of positive human functioning and flourishing on multiple levels that include the biological, personal, relational, institutional, cultural, and global dimensions of life". Positive psychology is concerned with eudemonia, "the good life", reflection about what holds the greatest value in life – the factors that contribute the most to a well-lived and fulfilling life. It is the scientific study of the strengths that enable individuals and communities to thrive. The field is founded on the belief that people want to lead meaningful and fulfilling lives, to cultivate what is best within them, and to enhance their experiences of love, work, and play. Positive psychology began as a new domain of psychology in 1998 when Martin Seligman chose it as the theme for his term as president of the American Psychological Association. Mihaly Csikszentmihalyi, Christopher Peterson and Barbara Fredrickson are regarded as co-initiators of this development. It is a reaction against psychoanalysis and behaviorism, which have focused on "mental illness", meanwhile emphasizing maladaptive behavior and negative thinking.

Key Words; Positive Psychology, Soft Skills, Positive Emotions.

INTRODUCTION

Positive Psychology is the scientific study of the strengths that enable individuals and communities to thrive. The field is founded on the belief that people want to lead meaningful and fulfilling lives, to cultivate what is best within themselves and to enhance their experiences of love, work, and play. “Positive Psychology is the scientific study of human flourishing, and an applied approach to optimal functioning. It is "the scientific study of what makes life most worth living", or "the scientific study of positive human functioning and flourishing on multiple levels that include the biological personal, relational, institutional,

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cultural, and global dimensions of life". Positive psychology is concerned with eudemonia, "the good life", reflection about what holds the greatest value in life – the factors that contribute the most to a well-lived and fulfilling life. It is the scientific study of the strengths that enable individuals and communities to thrive. The field is founded on the belief that people want to lead meaningful and fulfilling lives, to cultivate what is best within them, and to enhance their experiences of love, work, and play.

Positive psychology began as a new domain of psychology in 1998 when Martin Seligman chose it as the theme for his term as president of the American Psychological Association. Mihaly Csikszentmihalyi, Christopher Peterson and Barbara Fredrickson are regarded as co-initiators of this development. It is a reaction against psycho-analysis and behaviorism, which have focused on "mental illness", meanwhile emphasizing maladaptive behavior and negative thinking. It builds further on the humanistic movement, which encouraged an emphasis on happiness, well-being, and positivity, thus creating the foundation for what is now known as positive psychology. Positive psychology is "the scientific study of what makes life most worth living", or "the scientific study of positive human functioning and flourishing on multiple levels that include the biological, personal, relational, institutional, cultural, and global dimensions of life".

Positive emotions may be considered as any feeling where there is a lack of negativity, such that no pain or discomfort is felt. Frederickson (2009) identifies the ten most common positive emotions as joy, gratitude, serenity, interest, hope, pride, amusement, inspiration, awe and love. She also noted that we really need a 3:1 ratio of positive to negative in order to have a good life.

'Joy' is a common term that is used to describe the spectrum of happiness, from gentle comfort to ecstatic bliss. As a positive emotion, it is probably the most common one to be identified and also the one that is most commonly sought. Joy is often short-term, appearing quickly and also fading fast. Overall happiness can be increased by finding more things to be joyful about. Joy can be found in many of the other positive emotions, all of which are linked to 'being happy', yet it is useful to separate them out for individual consideration.

Gratitude is one of the strongest emotion that correlates with happiness. Simply by being grateful for what you have, you are focusing on the positive, as opposed to being unhappy about what you do not have. Expressing gratitude multiplies this as it not only reinforces the internal positive attitude but helps gain the altruistic pleasure of helping others and may be reflected in their 'gratitude for gratitude' and how they seek to make you happy in future.

Serenity is the calm of being content with what you have. It is an Epicurean pleasure in the way Epicurus

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defined pleasure as the absence of pain. Serenity is linked with higher spiritual state where the person feels one with the universe and is neither a victim nor a beneficiary of fate.

We have interest in those things that will help us to meet needs and achieve our goals. Interest is also sparked by novelty which piques our curiosity and thereby causes inquiry arousal. Just having interest in what is going on around you and in the world at large gives space for the pleasure of discovery to appear.

Hope is anticipatory happiness. It is the pleasure of an assumed future where good things happen and you will experience joy or other positive emotions. Hope is associated with optimism and our natural bias towards this can bring happiness into an unhappy situation as we think about how things can only get better.

Pride can have both negative and positive sides. A prideful person is arrogant and concerned with their status over others. They may feel happy, but at the expense of others. The more positive form of pride is typified by the pride in one's work or one's team. It is a 'purer' form of pride as it is intrinsically felt and is not negative about other people.

Amusement happens when we find something funny, from jokes to the incongruous nature of the world around us. Humor is an easy way of connecting with others and a shared sense of amusement is a helpful social bond. Being easily amused is also not to take things too seriously, especially ourselves. If you can laugh at your own mistakes then you can be happy forever.

Inspiration is what we feel when we see consummate skill or hear a great speech, and are inspired to do something as a result of this. In this way, inspiration is a strong motivational force and can be very powerful for changing minds. Leaders in particular will use this, particularly when using charismatic and transformational styles of leadership.

Awe is the feeling you get when you see a wonderful sunset or landscape. It is what you feel when you experience great art and marvel at the skill of the artist. This can be achieved through appreciation of painting, performance or some other creative expression. Awe can also be spiritual as you wonder at the marvels of the infinite universe or the totality of your god. Awe can come just from openness to experience. When you think of the wonders around you and even within you, you can just feel in awe of it all.

Love is a hugely powerful emotion which we first experience as an infant from our parents or care givers. It is also complex and there are several forms that may or may not seek reciprocation. The purest form is unconditional love, seeking to with no expectations.

Altruism is the pleasure of helping other people. It is related to love but is not quite the same, although it can be seen as being based on the love of humanity. Helping people, even strangers, is a very powerful act for

gaining happiness and it has strong social value as well as proving us as 'higher beings' who are not solely driven by selfish motivations.

Satisfaction is the pleasure of meeting challenges and achieving goals. It is related both to pride and serenity and is a low-activation emotion.

THE BENEFITS OF POSITIVE EMOTION

Positive emotions can help you be more creative. If you've ever been stuck trying to solve a problem for a long time, positive emotions can help you think out of the box and come up with creative solution. If you think of the last time you felt fear which caused high pulse rate, sweating and flustering; you may also recollect that positive emotion helped you regain your composure. Positive emotions help bring the body back down to baseline more quickly after experiencing the physical impact of negative emotions.

SOFT SKILLS

Soft skills are a combination of people skills, social space skills, communication skills, character of personality traits, attitudes, career attribute, social intelligence and emotional intelligence quotients among others that enable people to navigate their environment, work well with others, perform well, and achieve their goals with complementing hard skills. The Collins English Dictionary defines the term "soft skills" as "desirable qualities for certain forms of employment that do not depend on acquired knowledge: they include common sense, the ability to deal with people, and a positive flexible attitude.

Soft skill is commonly defined as a personal quality required to apply for a job, to do a job as well as to run a business. In other words, soft skill is a skill or an ability to manage oneself and others. Soft skill must be developed together with technical skill which can be used as an instrument to navigate the journey based on the positive mindset to reach visible achievement for short term period, medium period, as well as long-term period. Studies conducted by Havard University and some other famous universities show that 85% of an individual's success is derived from soft skill, while the other 15% is caused by other skills.

What are the Key Soft Skills?

Communication, as a soft skill; Communication is not about multiple syllables or rousing speeches. Soft Skills includes self-motivation, leadership, responsibility, teamwork., problem solving, decisiveness, ability to work under pressure and time management. Having the positive attitude and the initiative to work well without round-the-clock supervision is a vital soft skill for any employee. Not only does it demonstrate reliability and commitment, but it shows that you can fit efficiently into an organizational structure without

the need for constant oversight. Leadership is a competency employers look for in candidates who are applying for jobs that require them to lead, motivate and develop other people, usually team leader and management positions.

Defining Social and Emotional Learning and Soft Skills

Several sectors, including education, use the umbrella terms “social and emotional skills” and “soft skills” to refer to a broad set of cognitive, social, and emotional competencies that affect how children and youth interact with each other, solve problems, make decisions, and feel about themselves. Navigating the often-overlapping use of these umbrella terms within and across sectors and countries can pose a challenge in programming towards skill development. At USAID, the terms “social and emotional skills” and “soft skills” refer to a set of cognitive skills (e.g., attention focusing and shifting, impulse control, planning, and goal setting), social skills (e.g., perspective taking, prosocial behavior, and conflict resolution), and emotional skills (e.g., emotion knowledge, emotion regulation, and empathy) that shape how individuals interact with one another.

The term “social and emotional skills” is used in the context of formal and non-formal education programming and the term “soft skills” is used in the context of workforce development programs and higher education. “Social and emotional learning,” or SEL, is the process by which individuals learn and apply cognitive, social, emotional, and soft skills needed to succeed in educational settings, work, and the community. Specific social and emotional skills noted by USAID include managing emotions, setting and achieving goals, feeling and demonstrating empathy, developing and maintaining positive relationships, and making responsible decisions. Specific soft skills noted by USAID include higher-order thinking, communication skills, positive self-concept, social skills, and self-control.

REVIEWS OF THE STUDY

It is worth mentioning that for this study only the four items corresponding to Life Satisfaction were considered ($\alpha = .786$) as well as the following facets (WHO, 1998): Positive Feelings examines to what extent a person experiences positive feelings of satisfaction, balance, peace, happiness, hope, and joy as well as the enjoyment of the good things in life ($\alpha = .714$). Self-esteem refers to feelings that people have towards themselves ($\alpha = .787$). Interpersonal Relationships evaluate to what extent people feel companionship, love, and the support they want from their significant others ($\alpha = .603$). Lastly, Social Support refers to what extent a person perceives commitment, approval, and availability for receiving help from family and friends ($\alpha = .623$). Listening and communication. Listening is a very important part of effective communication be aware that physical barriers, noise or interruptions will make good

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communication difficult. Mute telephones or other communication devices to ensure you are really listening.

Jeroen Kuntze, and Marise Born conducted a study on a “The Five Traits and Assertiveness do not Affect mastery of communication skills. Mastering communication skills is often emphasized as an important aspect of job or academic performance. However, research into the relationships between personality factors and these skills is scarce. Purpose: This study investigated whether the big-five personality factors and assertiveness predict mastery of communication skills before and after following communication skills training. Method: The skills level of 143 psychology students was assessed after two communication skills courses, namely a basic and an advanced communication skills training. Personality factors were assessed with the Five Factor Personality Inventory and the Scale for Interpersonal Behavior. Results: Participants showed substantial progress in their mastery of the communication skills after both courses. Surprisingly, none of the personality factors predicted the level of mastery of these skills. Discussion: This seems to imply that trainees can become professional communicators, regardless of their scores on these personality factors.

Need for the study: According to WHO individuals who possess soft skill will gradually develop positive emotions in them. The investigator was interested in knowing whether the students with soft skills have positive emotions in them. Study the relationship between these two variables and understand How gender and locale vary in these aspects?.

Objectives of the Study:

1. To find out if any significant difference exists between boys and girls in their positive emotions and soft skill.
2. To find out if any significant difference exist between rural and urban students in their positive emotions and soft skill.
3. To find out the relationship between the two variables positive emotions and soft skills.

Hypothesis of the study

1. There is significant difference between boys and girls in their positive emotions.
2. There is a significant difference between boys and girls in their soft skills.
3. There is a significant difference between rural and urban students in their positive emotion.
4. There is significant difference between rural and urban students in their soft skills.
5. There is moderate relationship between the two variables; positive emotion and soft skills.

Methodology: The researcher employed descriptive survey method to collect the data. The sample consisted of 400 college students of kasaragod district. Stratified Random sampling technique was employed to collect the data. The tools used for the study were rating scales namely- Rating scale for positive emotions (RSPE) and Rating scale for Soft Skills (RSSS). These two tools were developed by the investigator himself and standardized by consulting experts, Psychologists and Educationists. The tools consisted of 5 point scale rating ie Agree, Strongly Agree, Undecided, Disagree, Strongly disagree. Each tool consisted of 75 items which was reduced to 50 by items by item analysis through pilot testing.

Collection of Data: The investigator herself administered the rating scale by giving clear cut instructions to the students. The data was collected individually and scored for analysis. For the analysis of the data ‘t’ test and pearson’s product moment correlation ‘r’ was employed.

Findings of the study reveal that

- There is no significant difference exist between boys and girls in their positive emotions.
- There is no significant difference exist between boys and girls in their soft skill.
- There is no significant difference exist between rural and urban students in their positive emotions.
- There is no significant difference exist between rural and urban students in their soft skill. There is moderate relationship between the two variables positive emotions and soft skills.

Discussion; A positive attitude enhances soft skills, similarly, it is understood that soft skills are needed to develop a positive attitude. So, two variable are required for the internal development of a person. Soft skills are helpful in increasing one’s empathic skills and positive empathic and emotional development is essential. So the study proved that there is no difference in soft skills and positive attitude of rural and urban students. There is moderate relationship between the two varianbles; positive emotions and soft skills.

CONCLUSION

Soft skills refer to a group of personal qualities that make up a good student or employee, personal qualities such as a positive attitude, communication, planning and organizing, critical thinking, interpersonal skills and more. soft skill there is a core set of competencies that are necessary for successful skill development. Many of the core competencies for soft skills have a foundation in emotional intelligence skills.

positive Emotions is a learned ability to identify, experience, understand, and express human emotions in healthy and productive ways. Emotional intelligence is known in educational settings as social/emotional learning. Whatever term you prefer, the concept is the same: to help individuals learn to use their emotions in a positive, constructive way. Emotional intelligence skills form the base of competencies that all soft skills are built upon.

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Paper 4

Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK): A Model for 21st Century prospective teachers for upgrading their teaching-learning Scenario

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ABSTRACT

TPACK is a framework that highlights the interplay between technology, pedagogy, and content knowledge in effective teaching and further excels in the scenario of the classroom environment for prospective teachers. The 21st century is governed by technology and the gamut of teaching-learning is also influenced by modern innovative digitalized technology. The prospective teacher must understand the usage of technology and how to use it judiciously for their success in the classroom. The TPACK is a model which can be used by the teacher for their classroom scenario which in turn increases the students' collaboration and promotes better learning outcomes.

Introduction

TPACK stands for Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge, which is a framework that highlights the interplay between technology, pedagogy, and content knowledge in effective teaching. It was first proposed by educational researchers Mishra and Koehler in 2006 as a model to guide 21st-century teachers in integrating technology into their teaching practices. TPACK refers to the knowledge and understanding that teachers possess about how technology, pedagogy, and content knowledge intersect and influence each other. It emphasizes the need for teachers to integrate technology seamlessly into their teaching practices, aligning it with pedagogical strategies and the specific content being taught. Mishra, & Koehler, (2006).

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Source:- <http://tpack.org/>

Components of TPACK

1. Technological Knowledge (TK)
 - Understanding the capabilities and limitations of different technologies and how to effectively use them in educational settings.
2. Pedagogical Knowledge (PK)
 - Knowledge of teaching methods, instructional strategies, and learning theories that support effective teaching and learning.
3. Content Knowledge (CK)
 - Deep understanding of the subject matter being taught, including its concepts, theories, and interdisciplinary connections.
4. Technological Pedagogical Knowledge (TPK)
 - Knowledge of how to apply technology to support pedagogical goals and enhance teaching and learning experiences.
5. Technological Content Knowledge (TCK)
 - Understanding how technology can be used to facilitate the teaching and learning of specific content areas.
6. Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PCK)
 - Integration of pedagogical approaches and content knowledge to design and deliver effective instruction.
7. Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK)
 - The integration and synthesis of technological, pedagogical, and content knowledge to create meaningful learning experiences.

Importance of TPACK in the 21st century

The importance of TPACK (Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge) in the 21st century lies in its ability to empower teachers with the knowledge and skills necessary to effectively integrate technology into teaching and learning. Here are some key reasons why TPACK is significant:

1. **Enhancing Teaching Practices:** TPACK enables teachers to leverage technology tools and resources to create engaging and interactive learning experiences. It helps them design innovative instructional strategies that cater to diverse student needs and promote a deeper understanding of the content (Ertmer et al., 2012).
2. **Promoting Student Engagement and Learning Outcomes:** TPACK encourages active student participation and collaboration, leading to increased student engagement and motivation. When technology is used appropriately in alignment with pedagogical goals and content knowledge, it can enhance student learning outcomes (Niess et al., 2009).
3. **Facilitating Personalized and Differentiated Instruction:** With TPACK, teachers can utilize technology to provide personalized and differentiated instruction that meets individual student needs. Adaptive learning platforms, educational apps, and online resources enable tailored learning experiences (Koehler et al., 2013).
4. **Encouraging Collaboration and Communication:** (Angeli & Valanides, 2009) explains TPACK equips teachers with the knowledge to foster collaborative learning environments through technology-mediated platforms. Students can collaborate, share ideas, and engage in authentic communication, extending learning beyond the traditional classroom.
5. **Authentic Learning Experiences:** TPACK facilitates the creation of authentic learning experiences that connect classroom learning to real-world applications through technology integration (Mishra & Koehler, 2006).
6. **Digital Citizenship:** TPACK helps teachers educate students about responsible and ethical technology use, fostering digital citizenship skills essential in the 21st century (Koehler & Mishra, 2008).
7. **Continuous Professional Development:** TPACK encourages educators to engage in continuous professional development to enhance their technological, pedagogical, and content knowledge, keeping pace with evolving educational trends (Harris & Hofer, 2009).

The Role of TPACK in Enhancing teaching practices prospective teachers:

The role of TPACK (Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge) in enhancing classroom scenarios for prospective teachers is centred around equipping them with the necessary knowledge and skills to effectively integrate technology into their teaching practices. This framework helps prospective teachers develop a deep understanding of how technology, pedagogy, and content knowledge intersect, and how to leverage this intersection to enhance student learning experiences. This study by Koehler and Mishra (2008)

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provides an overview of the TPCK framework, highlighting its importance in teacher education. It discusses how TPACK helps prospective teachers develop a deep understanding of the content they are teaching, the pedagogical approaches that support effective teaching, and how technology can be integrated to enhance teaching and learning.

TPACK empowers prospective teachers to:

1. **Recognize the Interplay:** TPACK helps prospective teachers understand that effective teaching requires a balance between technology, pedagogy, and content knowledge. It emphasizes the need to consider how these three domains intersect and inform one another in the teaching and learning process.
2. **Integrate Technology Purposefully:** TPACK equips prospective teachers with the knowledge and skills to select and use appropriate technology tools and resources that align with the learning objectives and content being taught. It encourages them to integrate technology in a purposeful and meaningful way that enhances student engagement and learning outcomes.
3. **Design Innovative Learning Experiences:** TPACK enables prospective teachers to design innovative pedagogical strategies that integrate technology effectively. It encourages them to move beyond traditional instructional methods and explore new approaches that leverage technology to engage students and promote a deeper understanding of the content.
4. **Adapt to Changing Educational Contexts:** TPACK prepares prospective teachers to adapt to the evolving landscape of educational technology. It instils in them a mindset of continuous learning and professional growth, enabling them to navigate emerging technologies and incorporate them into their teaching practices as needed.

By developing their TPACK, prospective teachers can enhance classroom scenarios by creating dynamic, technology-rich learning environments that foster student engagement, critical thinking, and active participation.

Conclusion

In conclusion, TPACK plays a vital role in the preparation of prospective teachers for the modern educational landscape. By integrating technology, pedagogy, and content knowledge, TPACK empowers prospective teachers to create dynamic and engaging learning environments. It gives them the skills and abilities to successfully incorporate technological tools and resources into their pedagogical practices, boosting student engagement, encouraging critical thought, and encouraging teamwork and communication skills. Additionally, TPACK equips prospective teachers with the skills necessary to adjust to the rapidly changing technological breakthroughs and educational environments, ensuring that they maintain their competence and confidence in their capacity to use technology to improve learning outcomes. Lastly,

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TPACK enables prospective teachers to meet the needs of 21st-century learners and effectively prepare them for the challenges and opportunities of the digital age. By embracing TPACK, aspiring teachers or prospective teachers can develop into cutting-edge, efficient instructors who can have a positive influence on their student's educational experiences which facilitates greater outcomes of learning.

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Paper 5

Creative Teaching: A conceptual Framework

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ABSTRACT

Human beings are born creative, as they grow and interact with their society, they become uncreative or they are taught to be uncreative. Children are full of curiosity and creativity; they see their surroundings in different way but the environment they grow restricts their creativity. In a Modern society to bring out best from students and to promote creativity among the students creative teaching is very important. Creative teaching also helps to increase students' interest towards the subject matter. Creative teaching is an art. The National Advisory Committee on Creative and Cultural Education suggests that the first task in teaching for creativity is 'to encourage young people to believe in their creative potential, to engage their sense of possibility and to give them the confidence to try'. Creativity in teaching is important to enhance students learning. Research in educational contexts reveals that confidence, enthusiasm and commitment are common qualities in creative teachers (Beetlestone 1998; Jones and Wyse, 2004; Graingeret al., 2004). This article tries to explain how creative teaching develops creativity and increase interest among the students in learning, the barriers for creative teaching in the classroom and the article concludes with the recommendation to develop creativity in teachers.

Key words: Creativity, Creative teaching, Importance of creativity, Curiosity, Barriers of creativity, Recommendation

Introduction:

It is rightly said by “Edward De Bono “There is no doubt that creativity is the most important human resource of all. Without creativity, there would be no progress, and we would be forever repeating the same patterns.”

Teaching as an ethical profession teacher makes choices for their students' betterment. Good teaching is ethical, reflective and creative. Teaching creatively is a skill. In teaching, there are always new challenges and Creative teachers adapt their teaching styles and strategies to better understand and manage the diversity of their classroom. In Modern society creativity is the important factor of the classroom. When teacher

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express their ideas in a creative way students easily understand it. To become a creative teacher, it is very important to be self-motivated, should have right attitude and use some interesting strategies in teaching to explain the content in interesting way.

Review of related literature

Ritchart (2004) and Jaskyte, Taylor, and Smariga (2009) acknowledged two areas of creative educating; curriculum and instruction. As per him, creative educators attempt to shape educational plans and present it in new, increasingly valuable ways. An innovative way to deal with curriculum includes finding new subjects/themes for understudies to investigate. An innovative way to deal with instruction includes discovering new methodologies or approaches for delivering content. The inventive instructor will discover various strategies to involve his understudies.

Deci and Ryan (2002) described that Education that stresses to youngsters' capacities and interests is probably to develop their prosperity and learning and, thus, better prepare them to contribute to the dynamics of present day society. Tanggaard (2014) further explained that within this perspective, creativity is not regarded as something reserved for certain individuals, but it is a central part of cognition and performing in new ways, in a world that expects us to do so. Sternberg (2006) and WRR (2013) express that there is ample evidence that it is possible to develop pupils' creativity. Therefore, policymakers as well as educators claim that education should play an essential part in building up the ability and creativity in students that the 21st century society needs.

Lou, Chen, Tsai, Tseng & Shih (2012) and Stojanova (2010) argued that teachers should be familiar with strategies that invigorate students' curiosity and creativity, including encouraging students to reflect, take part in discussion and ask questions instead of forcing students to just listen, edict, and memorize, consequently preparing them to be dynamic and find new things. Hamza and Griffith (2006) and Starko (2005) further explained that various strategies must be utilized to present content in order to study issues from a wide range of viewpoints. In addition, teachers must initiate self-started projects and give children positive feedback.

The ERIC Thesaurus defines creative teaching as “the development and use of novel, original, or inventive teaching methods” (Educational Resources Information Center, 2017). Kanter (1996) proposed that creative teaching is the teacher's independent ability to conceive of novel ideas or adapt the ideas of others into their context. Creative teaching not only encourages participation from others but also puts ideas into practice in accordance with a plan and involves the use of external resources. In doing so, creativity can be more

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greatly exhibited in teaching contexts. In the book *Teacher Skill and Strategies*, Woods (1990) suggested that creative teaching, including creative teaching plans, is a structural foundation and a type of discovery that disrupts the teaching status quo. Sternberg and Lubart (1995) observed that creative teaching occurs when teachers collect relevant teaching materials through creative teaching activities, draw up creative teaching plans, and improve creative teaching strategies, thereby improving students' learning effectiveness. Sawyer (2011) noted that creative teaching includes the teacher's use of imagination and trendy methods to form the value of originality and judgment. Rankin and Brown (2016) demonstrated that creative teaching can make learning invigorating and deeply experiential, thus furthering the professional knowledge and social and emotional skills of students. Therefore, the researchers define creative teaching as the teacher responding to the individual-level needs of the student, proactively seeking innovation, and designing courses with rich and novel content. Additionally, in creative teaching, engaging teaching methods are adopted to effectively improve the learning motivation and learning outcomes of students, thus achieving the goal of effective teaching.

Need for the study

Good classroom environment is always creative and interesting. Creativity in the curriculum and teaching makes the class innovative and encouraging. Creative classroom helps to bring out best from the students and to achieve educational goals. All-round development of the students can be attained through creative teaching. Creative classroom helps the students to gain knowledge and to apply it in their real-life situation. Even though we have many benefits from creative teaching but implementation of it in the classroom is very less because teaching creatively means coming out of the comfort zone and ignoring some rules and regulations of the school management. In a closed classroom setting creative teaching is not possible. So, it is very important to study about ways of implementing creative teaching in the classroom. Main objective of this study is to understand - To explain how creative teaching in the classroom develops creativity and increase interest among the students in learning, the barriers for creative teaching in the classroom and the article concludes with the recommendation to develop creativity in teachers.

Definitions of the term

Teaching:

Teaching is a process in which one individual teaches or instruct another individual. Teaching is considered as the act of imparting instructions to the learners in the classroom situation.

- **Dewey:-** considers it as a manipulation of the situation, where the learner will acquire skills and insight with his own initiation.

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- **H C Morrison:-** Teaching is an intimate contact between the more mature personality and a less mature one.
- **Jackson:-** Teaching is a face to face encounters between two or more persons, one of whom (teacher) intends to effect certain changes in the other participants (students).

Creativity

Creativity, the ability to make or otherwise bring into existence something new, whether a new solution to a problem, a new method or device, or a new artistic object or form.

According to Human Motivation, 3rd ed., by Robert E. Franken:

- Creativity is defined as the tendency to generate or recognize ideas, alternatives, or possibilities that may be useful in solving problems, communicating with others, and entertaining ourselves and others. (page 396)
- *Creativity* is the ability to transcend the ordinary. It's the critical thinking skill that allows you to "think outside the box" to come up with original solutions to problems.

Creative Teaching

- Creative teaching is defined as educational exchanges facilitated by the teacher that are “unique, customized and meaningful” (Rinkevich, 2011), and that are exciting, engaging and innovative (Craft, 2011). Creative teaching is complex, involving a broad range of skills, experience, and perspectives (Ambrose, 2005).
- For as Joubert (2001, p21) observes: Creative teaching is an art. One cannot teach teachers didactically how to be creative; there is no fail-safe recipe or routine. Some strategies may help to, promote creative thinking, but teachers need to develop a full repertoire of skills which they can adapt to different situations.

NEP 2020 and developing Creativity among the students

After 34 years India brought significant changes to its education system. The National Education Policy (NEP) was unveiled on 31st July 2020.

The first NEP was announced by the Government of India by Prime Minister Indira Gandhi in 1968, the second by Prime Minister Rajiv Gandhi in 1986, and the third by Prime Minister Narendra Modi in 2020. The National Education Policy 2020 (NEP 2020), which was approved by the Union Cabinet of India on 29 July 2020, outlines the vision of India's new education system. The new policy replaces the previous

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National Policy on Education, 1986.

The new National Education Policy also aims to promote creativity and critical thinking in 21st-century learners to encourage logical decision-making and innovation.

The [New Education Policy](#) puts a significant thrust on developing the “creative potential” of each child. It is based on the principle that education must develop not only cognitive skills but also ethical, social, and emotional capacities. It aims to develop innovation and out-of-the-box thinking.

Few points discussed in NEP 2020 in reference to creativity and innovation are:

- a) Development of enjoyable and inspirational books for all students and making these books available in the school library by translating it to local languages.
- b) Importance to experimental based education which in turn helps in creative thinking in the students.
- c) More emphasis on computational thinking in which students solve complex problems by breaking them into a series of small, more manageable sub-problems.
- d) To promote creativity and innovation, academic institutions and their teachers will have the autonomy to innovate on pedagogy, curriculum, and assessment within a broad education framework.

Benefits of the creative teaching in the classroom

To develop creativity in the students it is very important to innovate new creative teaching methods in education. Modern society is open to many modern technologies and what we teach in the normal school setting in lecture methods are not suited for the students so, it is very important for teacher to think in a different way to attain the educational goals.

Creativity helps to motivate students towards learning and increasing understanding. “Create” is at the top of [Bloom’s taxonomy](#) for a reason: By noticing broader patterns and connecting material across academic disciplines, creative thinking can facilitate deeper cross-curricular learning. As Alane Jordan Starko points out in the book *Creativity in the Classroom*, the strategies that support creativity—solving problems, exploring multiple options, and learning inquiry—also support depth of understanding.

Creative teaching gives an opportunity to the students to learn with fun. It helps the students to come out of their Emotional problems and help them to develop problem solving skills. Creative teaching encourages student centred education where students can learn by involving them in the educational process. Creative teaching also helps the students to develop good communication skills and interest in learning process where student can excel in academical performance and thus it contributes in all round development of the student.

Barriers for creative teaching

In the modern society it is very important for the teachers to move out of the comfort zone and to use creative methods in teaching. New educational policy 2020 mainly speaks about development of creativity among the students and it is possible only through teaching creatively. To implement creative teaching, it is very important to overcome of the barriers of creative teaching.

Some of the main barriers for creative teaching are:

- a) Teachers still use traditional methods of teaching which they feel is very easy and comfortable
- b) Teachers themselves have lack of creativity in them.
- c) Being creative involves risk, doing something which is different from the institutional norm. That requires a high degree of confidence and a willingness to face undesirable consequences
- d) The size of the classroom is limited and teacher should plan something which suits to the school setting which limits the creativity of the teacher.
- e) Institution where teacher received her education is also will have great influence on the creativity of the teacher which in turn influences creative teaching in the classroom.

Recommendation for creative teaching in the classroom

As a teacher it's our duty to create good learning environment to the students. Teacher should create accepting environment to the students where student should be free to do mistake in front of the teacher. Teachers should give positive reinforcement to the students where student can do self-assessment. Teacher should use creative instructional strategies, models, and methods to teach the content and should use experimental methods and activities in teaching through which creative thinking in the students will develop.

Teachers who think creatively and teach content playfully, and express ideas creatively will beget creative students. Teachers are the role models for the students. Teachers who have passions towards their subject whether it's drawing, mathematics, painting, biology, music or politics inspire the students. Creatively fulfilled teachers may also be happier teachers.

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Paper 6

ಪ್ರಸಕ್ತ ಶೈಕ್ಷಣಿಕ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಸೃಜನಾತ್ಮಕ ಬೋಧನೆಗಿರುವ ಅಡೆತಡೆಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಮಾರ್ಗೋಪಾಯಗಳು

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ಸಾರಲೇಖ:

ಸೃಜನಶೀಲ ಬೋಧನೆ ಶಿಕ್ಷಕನ ಬಳಿ ಇರುವ ಮಂತ್ರದಂಡದಂತೆ ಕಾರ್ಯನಿರ್ವಹಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಯ ಜ್ಞಾನ ಮತ್ತು ಆಸಕ್ತಿಯ ಮಟ್ಟ ಯಾವುದೇ ಹಂತದಲ್ಲಿರಲಿ ಸೃಜನಾತ್ಮಕತೆಯು ಅದಕ್ಕೆ ವೇಗ ನೀಡುತ್ತದೆ. ಸೃಜನಾತ್ಮಕತೆಯು ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆಯನ್ನು ಹೆಚ್ಚಿಸುತ್ತದೆ ಮತ್ತು ತರಗತಿಗೆ ಜೀವಂತಿಕೆ ನೀಡುತ್ತದೆ ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಧನಾತ್ಮಕತೆಯನ್ನು ತುಂಬಿ ತರಗತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಹೊಸ ಪ್ರಪಂಚ ಸೃಷ್ಟಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಎನ್.ಇ.ಪಿ 2020 ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ ಕ್ರಮ ಸಹ ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳ ಚಟುವಟಿಕೆಗೆ ಹೆಚ್ಚಿನ ಆದ್ಯತೆ ನೀಡಿದೆ ಮತ್ತು ತರಗತಿಯಲ್ಲಿನ ಜಡತ್ವವನ್ನು ಹೊರ ದಬ್ಬಲು ಪ್ರಯತ್ನಿಸುತ್ತಿದೆ ಇಂತಹ ಸನ್ನಿವೇಶದಲ್ಲಿ ಶಿಕ್ಷಕನ ಬೋಧನೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಜೀವಂತಿಕೆ ಇಲ್ಲದಿದ್ದರೆ ಆತ ಮೌಖಿಕ ಸಂಪ್ರದಾಯವನ್ನೇ ಅನುಸರಿಸುವುದಾದರೆ ಮಕ್ಕಳ ಮನಸ್ಸನ್ನು ಕಲಿಕೆಯ ಕಡೆಗೆ ಆಕರ್ಷಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿ ವಿಫಲನಾಗುತ್ತಾನೆ ಮಕ್ಕಳಲ್ಲಿನ ಪ್ರತಿಭೆಗೆ ಇಂಬು ನೀಡಬೇಕಾದ ಶಿಕ್ಷಕ ಪ್ರತಿಭೆಯಿಂದ ಜ್ವಲಿಸುತ್ತಿರಬೇಕು, ಇಲ್ಲದಿದ್ದಲ್ಲಿ ಆತ ಅಪ್ರಸ್ತುತನಾಗುತ್ತಾನೆ ನಾಟಕ, ನೃತ್ಯ, ಕಲೆ, ಸಂಗೀತ ಇತ್ಯಾದಿ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಸೃಜನಾತ್ಮಕತೆ ಥಾಳಾಗಿ ಗೋಚರಿಸುವಾಗ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರ ಹಿಂದುಳಿದರೆ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಹಿನ್ನೆಡೆಯಾಗುವುದರಲ್ಲಿ ಸಂದೇಹವಿಲ್ಲ. ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತ ಸಂಶೋಧನಾ ಲೇಖನದಲ್ಲಿ ಸೃಜನಾತ್ಮಕ ಬೋಧನೆಯ ಅರ್ಥ, ಮಹತ್ವವನ್ನು ವಿವರಿಸುವುದರೊಂದಿಗೆ ಬೋಧನಾ ಕಲಿಕಾ ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಸೃಜನಾತ್ಮಕ ಬೋಧನೆಗಿರುವ ಅಡೆತಡೆ ಮತ್ತು ಮಾರ್ಗೋಪಾಯಗಳ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಬೆಳಕನ್ನು ಚೆಲ್ಲುವು ಪ್ರಯತ್ನ ಮಾಡಲಾಗಿದೆ.

ಪೀಠಿಕೆ:

ಸೃಜನ ಶೀಲತೆಯ ಕಲ್ಪನೆ ಇಂದು ನೆನ್ನೆಯದೇನಲ್ಲ, ಮನುಷ್ಯನು ಜನ್ಮತಾಳಿದ ದಿನದಿಂದಲೇ ಅವನ ಜೊತೆಯಲ್ಲಿಯೇ ಬೆಳೆಯುತ್ತಾ

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ಬಂದಿದೆ. ನಾಗರಿಕತೆಗಳ ಉಗಮ, ವಿಕಾಸ, ಆಹಾರದ ಪರಿಕಲ್ಪನೆ, ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಜೀವನ, ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತಿಗಳ ಅಳವಡಿಕೆ, ಕಲೆ, ವಾಸ್ತುಶಿಲ್ಪಗಳ ಸೃಷ್ಟಿ, ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಅನ್ವೇಷಣೆಯ, ತಂತ್ರಜ್ಞಾನದ ಸೃಷ್ಟಿ ಇವೇ ಮುಂತಾದ ಅಂಶಗಳನ್ನು ವಿಶ್ಲೇಷಣೆ ಮಾಡುತ್ತಾ ಹೋದರೆ ಮಾನವನ ಚಿಂತನಾಶಕ್ತಿಯ ಅರಿವಾಗುತ್ತದೆ ಇದನ್ನೇ ನಾವು ಸೃಜನ ಶೀಲತೆ ಎಂದು ಕರೆಯುತ್ತೇವೆ.

ಪ್ರಾಚೀನ ಇತಿಹಾಸವುಳ್ಳ ಮನುಕುಲದ ಸಾಕ್ಷಾತ್ಕಾರಕ್ಕೆ ಸೋಪಾನವಾಗಿರುವ ಸೃಜನ ಶೀಲತೆ ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತ ದಿನಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಅತ್ಯಂತ ಅನಿವಾರ್ಯ ಹಾಗೂ ಅವಶ್ಯಕತೆಯೂ ಆಗಿದೆ. ಆಧುನಿಕ ಜಗತ್ತಿನಲ್ಲಿ ವಿಜ್ಞಾನ ಮತ್ತು ತಂತ್ರಜ್ಞಾನದ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಯು ಬಹುಮಾಧ್ಯಮಗಳನ್ನು ಸೃಷ್ಟಿಸಿ ಅನೇಕ ವಿಚಾರಧಾರೆಗಳಿಗೆ ವೇದಿಕೆಯಾಗಿರುವ ಹಿನ್ನೆಲೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಅದರ ಸದುಪಯೋಗ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಗೂ ಅವಶ್ಯಕತೆ ಇದೆ. ಆದುದರಿಂದ ಹಿಂದಿನ ಸಾಂಪ್ರದಾಯಿಕ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ ಪದ್ಧತಿಯಿಂದ ಹೊರಬಂದು ಸೃಜನಶೀಲ ಬೋಧನಾ ಕಲಿಕಾ ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆಯ ಪರಿಸರವನ್ನು ನಿರ್ಮಾಣ ಮಾಡುವುದು ಶಾಲಾ ಶಿಕ್ಷಕರ ಆಧ್ಯ ಕರ್ತವ್ಯವಾಗಿದೆ. ಶಿಕ್ಷಕರು ಯಾಂತ್ರಿಕ ಬೋಧನಾ ಕ್ರಮದಿಂದ ಹೊರಬಂದು ವಿಜ್ಞಾನ ತಂತ್ರಜ್ಞಾನವನ್ನು ಅಳವಡಿಸಿಕೊಂಡು ನಾವಿನ್ನಬೋಧನಾ ಕ್ರಮಗಳನ್ನು ಅರ್ಥೈಸಿಕೊಂಡು ಸೃಜನಾತ್ಮಕ ಬೋಧನೆಯ ಮುಖಾಂತರ ಕಲಿಕಾ ಸನ್ನಿವೇಷವನ್ನು ಜೀವಂತಗೊಳಿಸಿ ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳ ಚಿಂತನಾ ಶಕ್ತಿಯನ್ನು ವಿಕಾಸಗೊಳಿಸಬೇಕಾದ ಜವಾಬ್ದಾರಿ ಶಿಕ್ಷಕರ ಮೇಲಿದೆ. ಇದನ್ನು ಅರ್ಥಮಾಡಿಕೊಂಡು ಶೈಕ್ಷಣಿಕ ಸೇವೆಯನ್ನು ಸಲ್ಲಿಸಬೇಕಾಗಿದೆ.

ಸೃಜನಾತ್ಮಕ ಬೋಧನೆ:

ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಆಲೋಚನಾ ಕೌಶಲ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ವಿಶೇಷವಾಗಿ ಸೃಜನಾತ್ಮಕ ಆಲೋಚನಾ ಕೌಶಲ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ಸುಗಮಗೊಳಿಸುವ ರೀತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಬೋಧನೆಯನ್ನು ವಿನ್ಯಾಸಗೊಳಿಸುವ ಮತ್ತು ಕಾರ್ಯತಂತ್ರ ರೂಪಿಸುವ ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆಯನ್ನು ‘ಸೃಜನಾತ್ಮಕ ಬೋಧನೆ’ ಎಂದು ಕರೆಯಲಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಸೃಜನಾತ್ಮಕ ಬೋಧನೆಯು ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಚಿಂತನಾ ಸಾಮರ್ಥ್ಯವನ್ನು ಸೃಷ್ಟಿಸುವಂತಹ ಸರ್ವತೋಮುಖ ವಿಕಾಸಕ್ಕೆ ನೆರವಾಗುವ ಬೋಧನಾ ವಿಧಾನಗಳು, ತಂತ್ರಗಳು, ಮಾದರಿಗಳನ್ನು ಅಳವಡಿಸಿಕೊಂಡು ಕಲಿಕಾ ಸನ್ನಿವೇಷವನ್ನು ನಿರ್ಮಾಣ ಮಾಡಿಕೊಳ್ಳುವಂತಹ ರೀತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಇರಬೇಕಾಗಿದೆ. ಇದು ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳ ಮೇಲೆ ಉತ್ತಮ ಪರಿಣಾಮವನ್ನುಂಟುಮಾಡಿ ನಿರೀಕ್ಷಿತ ಕಲಿಕಾ ಫಲಗಳನ್ನು ಪಡೆಯಲು ಸಾಧ್ಯವಾಗುತ್ತದೆ.

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ಸೃಜನಾತ್ಮಕ ಬೋಧನೆಯ ಅವಶ್ಯಕತೆ:

ಶಿಕ್ಷಣವು ಪ್ರತಿಯೊಬ್ಬರಿಗೂ ಅಗತ್ಯ ಮತ್ತು ಅತ್ಯಮೂಲ್ಯವಾದದ್ದು ಇದರಿಂದಾಗಿಯೇ ಇಂದಿನ ಪೋಷಕರು ತಮ್ಮ ಮಕ್ಕಳಿಗೆ ಉತ್ತಮ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ ನೀಡಲು ಶಾಲೆಗಳನ್ನು ಆಯ್ಕೆ ಮಾಡಲು ಕಸರತ್ತು ನಡೆಸುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಈ ಸನ್ನಿವೇಶದಲ್ಲಿ ಸಾಧಾರಣ ಶಾಲೆಗಳು ತಮ್ಮ ಮಹತ್ವವನ್ನು ಕಳೆದುಕೊಂಡು ಮುಚ್ಚಲಾರಂಭಿಸಿವೆ ಅದೇ ವೇಳೆಗೆ ಹೊಸ ಹೊಸ ಶಾಲೆಗಳು ಅಸ್ತಿತ್ವಕ್ಕೆ ಬರಲಾರಂಭಿಸಿವೆ ಇದಕ್ಕೆ ಕಾರಣವೆಂದರೆ ಯಾವ ಶಾಲೆಗಳು ಬೋಧನಾ ಕಲಿಕಾ ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ನಾವಿನ್ಯತೆಯನ್ನು ಅಳವಡಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತವೆಯೋ ಅವು ಅಸ್ತಿತ್ವ ಉಳಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತವೆ. ಯಾವ ಶಾಲೆಗಳು ಸಾಂಪ್ರದಾಯಿಕ ಶೈಲಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಮುಂದುವರೆಯುತ್ತವೆಯೋ ಅವು ಅಸ್ತಿತ್ವ ಕಳೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತವೆ. ಇಂದಿನ ದಿನಮಾನದಲ್ಲಿ ಮಕ್ಕಳಿಂದ ವೃದ್ಧರವರೆಗೂ ಜನರು ಹೊಸತನವನ್ನು ಬಯಸುತ್ತಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಇದರಿಂದಾಗಿಯೇ ಇಂದು ವಿಜ್ಞಾನ ಮತ್ತು ತಂತ್ರಜ್ಞಾನ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರ ಉತ್ತುಂಗ ಸ್ಥಿತಿಯನ್ನು ತಲುಪಿದೆ. ಈ ಸಂಬಂಧ ತಂತ್ರಜ್ಞಾನ ಆಧಾರಿತ ಕೋರ್ಸ್ ಗಳು ಆರಂಭವಾಗಿವೆ. ಇವು ಜನರ ಬೇಡಿಕೆಗಳನ್ನು ಈಡೇರಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿ ಶ್ರಮಿಸುತ್ತಿವೆ.

ಮಾನವನ ಮೂಲಭೂತ ಕಸುಬಿನಿಂದ ಆರಂಭವಾಗಿ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ವಿಧದ ವೃತ್ತಿಗಳಲ್ಲಿಯೂ ಇಂದು ನಾವಿನ್ಯತೆಯನ್ನು ಕಾಣುತ್ತಿದ್ದೇವೆ, ಇದಲ್ಲದಕ್ಕೂ ಕಾರಣವೆಂದರೆ ಸೃಜನಶೀಲತೆಯ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ. ಸೃಜನಶೀಲತೆಯ ಕಾರಣದಿಂದ ನಮ್ಮ ಭೌತ ಮತ್ತು ಅಭೌತ ಸಂಸ್ಕೃತಿಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ವೇಗವಾದ ಬದಲಾವಣೆಯನ್ನು ಕಾಣುತ್ತಿದ್ದೇವೆ. ನಮ್ಮ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮಗಳು ಜನರ ಸೃಜನಶೀಲತೆಗೆ ಉತ್ತಮ ವೇದಿಕೆಯನ್ನು ಒದಗಿಸಿವೆ. ಇಲ್ಲಿ ಮಕ್ಕಳಿಂದ ವೃದ್ಧರವರೆಗೂ ಎಲ್ಲರೂ ತಮ್ಮಲ್ಲಿರುವ ಸೃಜನಶೀಲತೆಯನ್ನು ಅಭಿವ್ಯಕ್ತಗೊಳಿಸುತ್ತಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಸೃಜನಶೀಲತೆಯ ಬೆಳವಣಿಗೆಗೆ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮಗಳ ಕೊಡುಗೆ ಅನನ್ಯವೆಂದರೆ ತಪ್ಪಾಗಲಾರದು. ಕಾರಣ ಹಿಂದಿನ ದಿನಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಜನರು ತಮ್ಮ ಸೃಜನಶೀಲತೆಯ ಅಭಿವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಗಾಗಿ ವೇದಿಕೆಗಳನ್ನು ಹುಡುಕಬೇಕಾಗಿತ್ತು ಅವಕಾಶಕ್ಕಾಗಿ ಅಂಗಲಾಚ ಬೇಕಾಗಿತ್ತು. ಈ ಹೋರಾಟದಲ್ಲಿ ಗೆಲ್ಲಲಾರದೆ ಹಲವು ಪ್ರತಿಭೆಗಳು ವನ ಕುಸುಮದಂತೆ ಅರಳಿ ಬಾಡಿದ್ದು ಯಾರಿಗೂ ತಿಳಿಯಲಿಲ್ಲ. ಆದರೆ ಈಗಿನ ಪೋಷಕರು ತಮ್ಮ ಮಕ್ಕಳಲ್ಲಿರುವ ಸೃಜನಶೀಲತೆಯನ್ನು ಬಾಲ್ಯದಿಂದಲೇ ಹುಡುಕಲಾರಂಭಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ ಮತ್ತು ಅದಕ್ಕೆ ಇಂಬು ನೀಡುವ ಶಾಲೆಗಳನ್ನೇ ಹುಡುಕುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಇಂತಹ ಸಂದರ್ಭದಲ್ಲೇ ಶಾಲೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಅಗ್ನಿಪರೀಕ್ಷೆ ಎದುರಾಗುವುದು.

ಇಂದಿನ ದಿನಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಶಿಕ್ಷಕ ಪುಸ್ತಕದಲ್ಲಿರುವುದನ್ನು ಬೋಧಿಸಿ ಪರೀಕ್ಷೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಸಿದ್ಧರಾಗಿಸುವುದಕ್ಕೆ ಸೀಮಿತವಾದಲ್ಲಿ ಆತನ ಮತ್ತು ಶಾಲೆಯ ಅಂತ್ಯ ಸಮೀಪಿಸುತ್ತದೆ ಎಂದು ತಿಳಿಯಬೇಕು. ಮಕ್ಕಳ ಕಲಿಕೆಯನ್ನು ಹೆಚ್ಚಿಸಲು ಬೋಧನೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ವೈವಿಧ್ಯತೆಯನ್ನು ತರಬೇಕಾಗಿದೆ. ಹಿಂದಿನ ದಿನಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳು ಆಂಗ್ಲಭಾಷೆ, ವಿಜ್ಞಾನ, ಗಣಿತ ವಿಷಯಗಳು ಕಠಿಣವೆಂದು ಅದರಲ್ಲಿ ಪಾಸಾದರೆ

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ಸಾಕೆಂದು ಭಾವಿಸಿದ್ದರು. ಆದರೆ ಇಂದಿನ ಪೋಷಕರು ಮತ್ತು ಮಕ್ಕಳು ಜಾಣರಾಗಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಅವರು ನಾವು ಕಲಿಯುವಂತೆ ಬೋಧಿಸಲು ನಿಮಗೆ ಸಾಧ್ಯವೇ ಎಂದು ಶಿಕ್ಷಕರನ್ನು ಪ್ರಶ್ನಿಸುತ್ತಿದ್ದಾರೆ ಮತ್ತು ಅಂತಹ ಶಾಲೆಗಳನ್ನೇ ಹುಡುಕುತ್ತಿದ್ದಾರೆ. ಈ ರೀತಿಯ ಬೇಡಿಕೆಗಳು ಈಡೇರಬೇಕಾದರೆ ಶಿಕ್ಷಕ ತರಗತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಸೃಜನಶೀಲತೆಯನ್ನು ಅಳವಡಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳಲೇ ಬೇಕಾಗಿದೆ. ಕೇವಲ ಸೃಜನಶೀಲತೆಯ ಬಳಕೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ವಿಫಲರಾಗಿರುವ ಕಾರಣ ಸರ್ಕಾರಿ ಮತ್ತು ಅನುದಾನಿತ ಶಾಲೆಗಳು ಖಾಸಗಿ ಶಾಲೆಗಳ ಮುಂದೆ ಮಂಡಿಯಾರ ಬೇಕಾದ ಪರಿಸ್ಥಿತಿ ಬಂದಿದೆ ಎಂಬುದು ಕಟು ವಾಸ್ತವ ಮತ್ತು ಸಂಶೋಧನೆಗೆ ಅರ್ಹ ವಸ್ತು ವಿಷಯವೂ ಆಗಿದೆ. ಆದುದರಿಂದ ಶಿಕ್ಷಕರ ಸೃಜನಶೀಲತೆಯು ಇಂದಿನ ದಿನಗಳಿಗೆ ಅತ್ಯಂತ ಅವಶ್ಯಕತೆಯಾಗಿದೆ.

ಸೃಜನಾತ್ಮಕ ಬೋಧನೆಗಿರುವ ಅಡೆತಡೆಗಳು:

ಸೃಜನಾತ್ಮಕ ಬೋಧನೆ ಪ್ರತಿಯೊಂದು ಶಾಲೆಯಲ್ಲಿಯೂ ಶಿಕ್ಷಕರು ಅಳವಡಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳಲೇಬೇಕಾದ ಅನಿವಾರ್ಯತೆಯಿದೆ. ಈ ಸಂಬಂಧ ಸೇವಾ ಪೂರ್ವ ತರಬೇತಿ ಮತ್ತು ಸೇವಾ ನಿರತ ತರಬೇತಿಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಸೃಜನಾತ್ಮಕ ಬೋಧನೆಗೆ ಹೆಚ್ಚು ಒತ್ತನ್ನು ನೀಡುತ್ತಿರುವುದನ್ನು ಗಮನಿಸಬಹುದಾಗಿದೆ. ಅಲ್ಲದೆ ಬಹುಮಾಧ್ಯಮದ ಮುಖಾಂತರ ಸೃಜನಶೀಲ ಬೋಧನೆಗೆ ಸಂಬಂಧಪಟ್ಟ ಅನೇಕ ಕೌಶಲಗಳನ್ನು ಅಭ್ಯಾಸ ಮಾಡಲು ಅವಕಾಶವಿದೆ. ಇಂತಹ ಸೌಲಭ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ಬಹುತೇಕ ಶಿಕ್ಷಕರು ಬಳಸಿಕೊಂಡು ತಮ್ಮ ಬೋಧನಾ ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಅಳವಡಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳಲು ಸಾಕಷ್ಟು ಪ್ರಯತ್ನ ಪಡುತ್ತಿದ್ದಾರೆ, ಆದರೂ ಶಿಕ್ಷಕರಲ್ಲಿ ಸೃಜನಾತ್ಮಕ ಬೋಧನೆಯನ್ನು ಅಳವಡಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳಲು ಹಲವಾರು ಅಂಶಗಳು ಅಡ್ಡಿಯಾಗಿರುವುದನ್ನು ಕಾಣಬಹುದಾಗಿದೆ. ಅವುಗಳೆಂದರೆ.

1. ಶಿಕ್ಷಕರು ಮತ್ತು ಶೈಕ್ಷಣಿಕ ಆಡಳಿತಗಾರರು ನಿರಂತರ ಪ್ರಭುತ್ವಕ್ಕೆ ಒಗ್ಗಿಕೊಂಡಿರುವುದು
2. ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳ ಆಲೋಚನೆಗೂ ಶಿಕ್ಷಕನ ಆಲೋಚನೆಗೂ ತಾಳೆಯಾಗದಿರುವುದು.
3. ಶಿಕ್ಷಕರು ತರಗತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಜೀವಂತಿಕೆಗೆ ಬದಲು ಜಡತ್ವ ತರುವುದು.
4. ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳ ಮುಂದಾಗುವಿಕೆಯನ್ನು ನಿರುತ್ಸಾಹ ಗೊಳಿಸುವುದು.
5. ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳ ಸರಿ ತಪ್ಪುಗಳ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಸೂಕ್ತ ಸಮಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಪುಷ್ಟೀಕರಣ ನೀಡದಿರುವುದು.
6. ಆಲೋಚನೆಯ ಉದ್ದಿಪನಕ್ಕೆ ನೆರವಾಗದ ಪುಸ್ತಕದಲ್ಲಿರುವ ಪ್ರಶ್ನೆಗಳನ್ನು ಯಾಂತ್ರಿಕವಾಗಿ ಬಳಸುವುದು.
7. ಶಿಕ್ಷಕರು ಹಾಗೂ ಶೈಕ್ಷಣಿಕ ಮೇಲ್ವಿಚಾರಕರುಗಳು ಮಕ್ಕಳಿಗಾಗಿ ಸಮಯವನ್ನು ಮೀಸಲಿಡದಿರುವುದು.
8. ಬೋಧನೆಯು ಬುದ್ಧಿವಂತಿಕೆ ಮತ್ತು ಶ್ರಮವನ್ನು ನಿರೀಕ್ಷಿಸುತ್ತದೆ ಎಂಬ ಸತ್ಯಕ್ಕೆ ವಿರುದ್ಧವಾದ ನಡವಳಿಕೆ.

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9. ಶಿಕ್ಷಕರು ಹಾಗೂ ಶೈಕ್ಷಣಿಕ ಮೇಲ್ವಿಚಾರಕರುಗಳು ಸದಾ ನೆಮ್ಮದಿಯಿಂದ ಇರಲು ಹಾತೊರೆಯುವುದು.
10. ಪ್ರವಾಸ, ಏಕಾಂತ, ಮನರಂಜನೆ ಮತ್ತು ಸಮಾಜಮುಖಿ ಕಾರ್ಯಗಳಿಂದ ಹೊರತಾದ ಶಿಕ್ಷಕರ ಅಶಿಸ್ತಿನ ಜೀವನ ಕ್ರಮ.
11. ಸಂತಸಕ್ಕಾಗಿ ಕೆಲಸ ಮಾಡದೆ ಸಂಬಳಕ್ಕಾಗಿ ಕಾರ್ಯ ನಿರ್ವಹಿಸುವುದು.
12. ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರದಲ್ಲಿ ಅನಾವಶ್ಯಕವಾದ ರಾಜಕೀಯ ಪ್ರಭಾವ.

ಇದರ ಒಟ್ಟಾರೆ ಪರಿಣಾಮವೇ ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳು ಶಾಲೆಯಿಂದ ವಿಮುಖರಾಗಲು ಮತ್ತು ನಿರಾಸಕ್ತರಾಗಲು ಕಾರಣವಾಗಿದೆ. ಇದನ್ನು ತೊಡೆದು ಹಾಕಲು ಶಿಕ್ಷಕ ತನ್ನ ಕಾರ್ಯನಿರ್ವಹಣಾ ಶೈಲಿಯನ್ನು ಬದಲಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳಬೇಕಾಗಿದೆ.

ಸೃಜನಾತ್ಮಕ ಬೋಧನೆಗೆ ಅವಶ್ಯಕವಾಗಿರುವ ಮಾರ್ಗೋಪಾಯಗಳು:

ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರದಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರತಿ ಹಂತದಲ್ಲೂ ಕಲಿಯುವ ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಸೃಜನಾತ್ಮಕ ಚಿಂತನೆಗಳನ್ನು ಕಾಣಬಹುದಾಗಿದೆ. ಕೇವಲ ಪಠ್ಯಪುಸ್ತಕವನ್ನು ಆದರಿಸಿ ಪರಿಕ್ಷಾ ದೃಷ್ಟಿಯಿಂದ ಬೋಧನೆಯನ್ನು ಮಾಡಿ ಅತ್ಯುತ್ತಮ ಫಲಿತಾಂಶವನ್ನು ನೀಡಿದರೂ ಅಂತಹ ಶಾಲೆಗಳನ್ನು ಉತ್ತಮ ಶಾಲೆಗಳೆಂದು ಕರೆಯಲು ಸಾಧ್ಯವಾಗುತ್ತಿಲ್ಲ ಏಕೆಂದರೆ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಾತ್ಮಕ ಜಗತ್ತಿನಲ್ಲಿ ಅನೇಕ ಪ್ರವೇಶ ಪರೀಕ್ಷೆ ಮತ್ತು ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಾತ್ಮಕ ಪರೀಕ್ಷೆಗಳನ್ನು ಬರೆಯುವುದರ ಮುಖಾಂತರ ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳು ತಮ್ಮ ಭವಿಷ್ಯವನ್ನು ರೂಪಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳಬೇಕಾಗಿದೆ. ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಾತ್ಮಕ ಪರೀಕ್ಷೆ ಬರೆಯಲು ಕೇವಲ ಜ್ಞಾನಾಂಶಗಳಿದ್ದರೆ ಸಾಲುವುದಿಲ್ಲ ಸೃಜನಾತ್ಮಕ ಚಿಂತನೆಯ ಕೌಶಲ ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳಿಗೆ ಅತ್ಯಂತ ಅವಶ್ಯಕವಾಗಿದೆ. ಈ ದೃಷ್ಟಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಶಿಕ್ಷಕರು ಪ್ರತಿ ಹಂತದಲ್ಲೂ ಪಠ್ಯ ವಿಷಯದ ಜೊತೆ ಜೊತೆಯಲ್ಲಿಯೇ ಸೃಜನಾತ್ಮಕ ಕೌಶಲಗಳನ್ನು ಬೆಳೆಸಬೇಕಾದರೆ ಸೃಜನಾತ್ಮಕ ಬೋಧನೆಯನ್ನು ಅವಳಡಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳಬೇಕಾಗಿದೆ. ಇಂತಹ ಬೋಧನೆಗೆ ಅವಶ್ಯಕವಿರುವ ಮಾರ್ಗೋಪಾಯಗಳನ್ನು ಈ ಕೆಳಕಂಡಂತೆ ಕಾಣಬಹುದಾಗಿದೆ.

1. ಶಿಕ್ಷಕರು ನಿರಂತರ ಅಧ್ಯಯನಶೀಲರಾಗಿರಬೇಕು.
2. ಶಿಕ್ಷಕರು ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳ ಇತ್ತೀಚಿನ ಒಲವುಗಳ ಕುರಿತು ತಿಳುವಳಿಕೆಯನ್ನು ಪಡೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳಬೇಕು.
3. ಶಿಕ್ಷಕರು ಕಲೆ, ಚಿತ್ರಕಲೆ, ನಾಟಕ, ಸಂಗೀತ ಮತ್ತು ನೃತ್ಯ ಇತ್ಯಾದಿಗಳ ಲಲಿತ ಕಲೆಗಳನ್ನು ಅಭ್ಯಾಸ ಮಾಡಬೇಕು.
4. ಶಿಕ್ಷಕರು ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಕಂಡು ಬರುವ ವಿಷಯ ಸಂಪನ್ಮೂಲ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಗಳ ಬೋಧನಾ ಕ್ರಮ ಮತ್ತು ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತಪಡಿಸುವ ಶೈಲಿಯನ್ನು ಅನುಸರಿಸುವುದು.
5. ಶಿಕ್ಷಕರು ನಿರಂತರ ಚಿಂತನೆಗಳನ್ನು ಮಾಡಿ ಲಿಖಿತ ಮತ್ತು ಮೌಖಿಕವಾಗಿ ವಿಚಾರ ಸಂಕಿರ್ಣಗಳು, ಶೈಕ್ಷಣಿಕ ಸಮ್ಮೇಳನಗಳು

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ಹಾಗೂ ಸಂಚಿಕೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ವಿಚಾರಗಳನ್ನು ಮಂಡಿಸುವ ಹವ್ಯಾಸವನ್ನು ರೂಡಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳಬೇಕು.

6. ಶಿಕ್ಷಕರು ಸಮಾನ ಮನಸ್ಸರೊಡನೆ ವಿಚಾರ ವಿನಿಮಯಗಳನ್ನು ನಿಯಮಿತವಾಗಿ ಮಾಡುತ್ತಾ ತಮ್ಮ ಸೃಜನಾತ್ಮಕ ಶಕ್ತಿಯನ್ನು ವಿಕಾಸಗೊಳಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳಬೇಕು.
7. ಶಿಕ್ಷಕರು ತಮ್ಮಲ್ಲಿರುವ ಮಿತಿಗಳು ಅಥವಾ ಕೊರತೆಗಳನ್ನು ಗಮನಿಸಿ ಪರಿಹಾರಾತ್ಮಕ ಅಂಶಗಳನ್ನು ಗುರುತಿಸಿಕೊಂಡು ಅಳವಡಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳಲು ಪ್ರಯತ್ನಿಸಬೇಕು.
8. ಶಿಕ್ಷಕರು ಮುದ್ರಣ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮ ಹಾಗೂ ಡಿಜಿಟಲ್ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮಗಳನ್ನು ಪರಿಣಾಮಕಾರಿಯಾಗಿ ಬಳಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳಬೇಕು.
9. ಶಿಕ್ಷಕರು ತರಗತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಯಾಂತ್ರಿಕವಾಗಿ ಬೋಧಿಸದೆ ಪ್ರಯೋಗಶೀಲತೆಯನ್ನು ಅಳವಡಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳಬೇಕು.
10. ಶಿಕ್ಷಕರು ವಿಮರ್ಶಾತ್ಮಕ ಆಲೋಚನ ಶಕ್ತಿಯನ್ನು ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಪಡಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳಬೇಕು.
11. ಶಿಕ್ಷಕರು ಬೋಧನೆಯನ್ನು ಆರೋಗ್ಯಕರ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧೆಯೆಂದು ಪರಿಗಣಿಸಿ ಜಯ ಸಾಧಿಸಲು ಪ್ರಯತ್ನಿಸಬೇಕು.
12. ಶಿಕ್ಷಕರು ಸುಲಭದ ದಾರಿಗಿಂತ ಸವಾಲಿನ ದಾರಿಯನ್ನು ಆಯ್ಕೆ ಮಾಡಿಕೊಳ್ಳಬೇಕು.
13. ಶಿಕ್ಷಕರು ತರಗತಿ ಬೋಧನೆಗೆ ಪುಸ್ತಕಕ್ಕಿಂತ ಕಲಿಕಾ ಸಂಪನ್ಮೂಲಗಳನ್ನು ಪರಿಣಾಮಕಾರಿಯಾಗಿ ಬಳಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳಬೇಕು.
14. ಶಿಕ್ಷಕರು ತರಗತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಏಕಮುಖ ಬೋಧನೆಯನ್ನು ಕೈಬಿಟ್ಟು ಪ್ರಶ್ನೆ, ಸಂವಾದ, ಚರ್ಚೆ, ಚಿಂತನೆ ಮತ್ತು ಅಭಿವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಗಳಿಗೆ ಆದ್ಯತೆಯನ್ನು ನೀಡಬೇಕು.
15. ಶಿಕ್ಷಕರು ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳಿಗೆ ತರಗತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಪುಸ್ತಕದಿಂದ ಹೊರತಾಗಿರುವ ಆಲೋಚನೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಅವಕಾಶ ಕಲ್ಪಿಸಬೇಕು.

ಶಿಕ್ಷಕರು ತರಗತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಸೃಜನಶೀಲ ಬೋಧನೆಗೆ ಅನುಸರಿಸುವ ಕ್ರಮಗಳು:

1. ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳಿಗೆ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳನ್ನು ನೀಡಿ ಬಿಡಿಸಲು ತಿಳಿಸುವುದು.
2. ಹೊಸ ಪದಗಳನ್ನು ಪರಿಚಯಿಸಲು ಪದಬಂಧ ರಚನೆಗೆ ಪ್ರೋತ್ಸಾಹ ನೀಡುವುದು ಮತ್ತು ದಿನ ಪತ್ರಿಕೆಯಲ್ಲಿನ ಪದಬಂಧವನ್ನು ತುಂಬಲು ಸೂಚಿಸುವುದು
3. ಯಾವುದಾದರೂ ವಿಷಯವನ್ನು ನೀಡಿ ಕಥೆ ಕವನ ಲೇಖನ ಇತ್ಯಾದಿಗಳನ್ನು ರಚಿಸಲು ತಿಳಿಸುವುದು.
4. ಶಿಕ್ಷಕ ಪಠ್ಯ ವಿಷಯಕ್ಕೆ ತಾನೇ ಪಾತ್ರಾಭಿನಯ ಮಾಡುವುದು. ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳನ್ನು ತಂಡಗಳಾಗಿ ರಚಿಸಿ ಪಠ್ಯದ ಕೆಲ ಭಾಗಗಳನ್ನು ನೀಡಿ ಅದನ್ನು ನಾಟಕೀಕರಣ ಗೊಳಿಸಲು ತಿಳಿಸುವುದು.

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5. ಚಿತ್ರಕಲಾ ಪ್ರದರ್ಶನ ಏರ್ಪಡಿಸುವುದು.
6. ಪಾಠೋಪಕರಣಗಳ ಮೂಲಕವೇ ಪಠ್ಯ ಬೋಧನೆ ಮಾಡುವುದು.
7. ತರಗತಿ ಪಠ್ಯವನ್ನು ದೈನಂದಿನ ಜೀವನಕ್ಕೆ ಅನ್ವಯಿಸಿ ಬೋಧಿಸುವುದು.
8. ವೈವಿಧ್ಯಮಯ ಬೋಧನಾ ವಿಧಾನಗಳ ಬಳಕೆ ಮಾಡುವುದು.
9. ಶಿಕ್ಷಕ ತನ್ನ ಮಾತುಗಳನ್ನು ಕಡಿಮೆ ಮಾಡಿ ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳ ಮಾತುಗಳನ್ನು ಆಲಿಸಲು ಉತ್ಸಾಹ ತೋರುವುದು.
10. ತರಗತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಜಾಸತ್ತಾತ್ಮಕ ವಾತಾವರಣವನ್ನು ನಿರ್ಮಿಸಿ, ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳ ಅಭಿವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಗೆ ಒತ್ತು ನೀಡುವುದು.
11. ತರಗತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಏಕದೃಷ್ಟಿ ಕೋನಕ್ಕಿಂತ ಬಹುದೃಷ್ಟಿ ಕೋನಕ್ಕೆ ಒತ್ತು ನೀಡುವುದು.
12. ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳಿಗೆ ಪಠ್ಯವನ್ನು ಬೋಧನೆಯ ಜೊತೆಗೆ ಮನರಂಜನ ಚಟುವಟಿಕೆಗಳನ್ನು ಕೈಗೊಳ್ಳುವುದು.

ಉಪಸಂಹಾರ:

ಸೃಜನಾತ್ಮಕ ಅಂಶಗಳನ್ನು ತನ್ನ ಕಾರ್ಯನಿರ್ವಹಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಶಿಕ್ಷಕನು ಅಳವಡಿಸಿಕೊಂಡಲ್ಲಿ ಆತನ ಬೋಧನೆ ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳ ಬಾಳಿನಲ್ಲಿ ಒಂದು ಮೈಲಿಗಲ್ಲಿನಂತೆ ಕೆಲಸ ಮಾಡುತ್ತದೆ. ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರದಲ್ಲಿ ಯಾಶಸ್ವಿಯಾಗಬೇಕಾದರೆ ಕೇವಲ ಭೌತಿಕ ಸಂಪನ್ಮೂಲಗಳಿಂದಲೇ ಸಾಧ್ಯ ಎಂಬ ಮಾತು ಸುಳ್ಳಾಗಿದೆ. ಒಬ್ಬ ಸೃಜನಶೀಲ ಶಿಕ್ಷಕ ಮರದ ಕೆಳಗಡೆ ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಯನ್ನು ಕೂರಿಸಿಕೊಂಡು ಯಶಸ್ವಿ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣವನ್ನು ನೀಡಬಹುದು. ಆದರೆ ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯ ಶಿಕ್ಷಕ ಎಂತಹ ಸೌಲಭ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ನೀಡಿದ್ದರೂ ಈ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರದಲ್ಲಿ ಯಶಸ್ವಿಯಾಗಲು ಸಾಧ್ಯವಾಗಲಾರನು. ಆದುದರಿಂದ ಸೃಜನಾತ್ಮಕ ಚಿಂತನೆ ಮತ್ತು ಸೃಜನಶೀಲ ಬೋಧನೆ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರದಲ್ಲಿ ಅತ್ಯಂತ ಅವಶ್ಯಕವಾಗಿದೆ.

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6. ಸೃಜನಾತ್ಮಕ ಮೌನ -ಧಿಯಾ ಸಫಿ ಪ್ರಚಾರ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ ಸಮಿತಿ ಕರ್ನಾಟಕ ಧಿಯಾಸಫಿಕಲ್ ಫೌಂಡೇಶನ್ ವಿಭಾಗ, ನಂಬರ್-10 ಕೆಆರ್ ರಸ್ತೆ ಬೆಂಗಳೂರು 56001 ಪ್ರಕಟಣೆ 2019
7. ಶೈಕ್ಷಣಿಕ ಮನೋವಿಜ್ಞಾನ ಲೇಖಕರು ಡಾ. ಎಚ್ ವಿ ವಾಮದೇವಪ್ಪ ಬಸವೇಶ್ವರ ಮುದ್ದಣ 2018 ಏಷಿಯಾ ಓಐ 978-93-51 26-549-8 ಓಐ 10, ಶ್ರೀ ಶಿವಯೋಗಿ ಮಂದಿರ ಸಂಕೀರ್ಣ, ಜಯದೇವ ಸರ್ಕಲ್ ಹತ್ತಿರ, ಹದಡಿ ರಸ್ತೆ, ದಾವಣಗೆರೆ.
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9. ಕಲಿಕಾ ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆಯ ಮನೋವಿಜ್ಞಾನ ಮತ್ತು ಮೌಲ್ಯಮಾಪನ ಲೇಖಕರು ಡಾ. ಹೆಚ್ ವಿ ವಾಮದೇವಪ್ಪ ಏಷಿಯಾ ಓಐ 978-93-51 26-551-1 ಶ್ರೇಯಸ್ ಪಬ್ಲಿಕೇಶನ್ಸ್ ನಂಬರ್ 1660/41, ಮನೋಜ್ಞ, 12 ಅಡ್ಡರಸ್ತೆ, ದಾವಣಗೆರೆ.

e- Education: Digital Initiatives in India

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ABSTRACT

Education (schools, colleges, and universities) in India is largely based on traditional methods of instruction, that is, face-to-face lectures in a classroom. Despite the fact that many academic institutions have begun to implement blended learning, many remain trapped in the past. Over the past few years, e-learning has seen a jump in popularity due to widespread internet connectivity, the proliferation of smartphones, and substantial technological advancements. e-learning activities are important for the development of any country. In modern era everybody is thinking about growth and educational development. If it is planned properly then proper results will come. e-Learning in education sector is an important issue as far as Indian education system is concerned. An attempt has been made through this paper to focus on the e-Learning in education sector in India.

Key Words: Education, Educational Development, e-Learning

1.1 Introduction

The world of education is changing. In this globalization era the cost of education is high, the demand to increase the knowledge of graduates and improve quality, and the increasing diversity of students are factors affecting this change and transition. Information technology and computers possess the ability to solve many of these challenges. Higher education institutions responded by using advanced information technologies (Palloff & Prat, 2000). Electronic learning or e-learning is defined as learning facilitated through electronic means. In the 1980's Computer Based Training (CBT) was used for learning purposes by some universities. After the introduction of the World Wide Web these institutions started using the Internet for educational purposes, starting the era of Web Based Training (WBT). With the advances of Internet technologies, WBT has become very popular in universities and colleges for teaching purposes. E-learning has changed the role of faculties and students. It has personalized education making it more learner-centered. The new technology has helped institutions of higher education save money through improved processes, distance education, and cutting down costs. E-learning has expanded the scope and content of the curriculum and increased enrolment for colleges and universities (Horgan, 1998). The e-learning activities are important for

the development of any country. In modern era everybody is thinking about growth. If it is planned properly then proper results comes.

1.2 Concept of E- Learning

A learning system based on formalized teaching but with the help of electronic resources is known as E-learning. While teaching can be based in or out of the classrooms, the use of computers and the Internet forms the major component of E learning. E-learning can also be termed as a network enabled transfer of skills and knowledge, and the delivery of education is made to a large number of recipients at the same or different times. The technology-based e-learning encompasses the use of the internet and other important technologies to produce materials for learning, teach learners and also regulate courses in an organization (Fry, 2001). E-learning has a promising future in India due to increasing internet connectivity and masses using e- learning as an aid to gain knowledge. But most of students and knowledge seekers are unaware of these amazing E- learning. E-learning raises the level of education, literacy and economic development in countries where technical education is expensive, opportunities are limited and economic disparities exist.

Earlier, it was not accepted wholeheartedly as it was assumed that this system lacked the human element required in learning. E-Learning involves the use of digital media and technology to deliver learning experiences. A learning experience attempts to simulate the real-world classroom learning process. It involves assembling great content, distributing it to facilitate learning, managing the learning process and providing validations. In the current era, where technology is rapidly evolving, education has also taken the support of ICT and now offers convenient ways to help increase the knowledge, education and literacy status of people. E-learning platform provides anywhere, anytime easy access for upgradation of knowledge and skills. It provides a platform wherein the individual gets a customized package related to key thematic areas, through a self-guided process.

1.3 Digital Educational Platforms Launched in India:

Educational Institutions all over the country tried to assure that the students experience less academic loss. These institutions are giving their best efforts in conducting virtual classes, video conferencing and using of other online platforms to upload the concerned study material online.

A number of considerable online learning platforms has been provided by Union HRD ministry to support learning amid lockdown

- **SWAYAM Portal MOOCs:** These are online based interactive-media courses created specifically for students studying at higher education level. Many courses are approved by AICTE as FDP for Faculty. Students can also earn academic credits in plenty of these available courses. These are

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available throughout the year.

- **E-PG Pathshala:** This web-based platform offers e-books up to PG level, which can be easily accessed.
- **Digital Infrastructure for Knowledge Sharing (DIKSHA):** Around 80,000 Curriculum related content in 15 languages is being provided on the portal. It is also giving access to extensive scope of videos with explanation, various interactive activities and games, quiz, lesson plans, experience-based content along with worksheets.
- **CBSE PODCAST:** A new podcast app has been launched by CBSE which goes with the name ‘CBSE-Shiksha Vani’. This application is accessible through Play Store for downloading by Android phone users.
- **National Digital Library of India (NDL):** This digital platform is available for all categories of educational institutions, academicians, differently abled students and all others who are ready to learn. The Website address to access is: <https://ndl.iitkgp.ac.in/>.
- **IIT Pal:** Many students wish to clear through IIT entrance exams. So IIT Pal provides lectures for such students in Science subjects which are helpful in cracking IIT entrance exams. Website that can be accessed is: <https://nta.ac.in/LecturesContent>.
- **Vidwan:** It is linked with National Mission on Education through ICT (NME-ICT). It is an index of experts and all stakeholders associated with research areas and wish to establish networks.
- **E-Shodh Sindhu:** It provides platform for access to higher education electronic resources with the help of INFLIBNET centre. A large number of peer reviewed journals and institutions are linked with the portal.

Table1: Expenditure Incurred on Education under Various e-Learning Schemes in India (Rs. In Crore)

Schemes	2016-2017	2017-2018	2018-2019
Swayam	61.00	63.00	117.27
NMEICT (Including SWAYAM Prabha)	146.44	108.03	113.04
National Digital Library (NDL)	9.71	10.00	7.00
E-Shodh Sindhu	235.00	145.12	199.57
DIKSHA	--	--	2.91

Source: Lok Sabha Unstarred Question No. 223, dated 03.02.2020. Indiatat.

Abbr.:

- SWAYAM: Study Webs of Active Learning for Young Aspiring Minds.
- NMEICT: National Mission on Education through Information and Communication Technology.
- DIKSHA: Digital Infrastructure for Knowledge Sharing.

1.4 Advantages of E-Learning

The implementation of e-learning in education sector has been favourable in multiple contexts. Past studies, have exposed several advantages associated by the implementation of e-learning technologies into university education (Raspopovic et al., 2017). E-learning has been viewed as the ability to focus on the requirements of individual learners. For instance, focusing on the needs of individual learners can deliver knowledge in digital age effectively as compared to educational institutions’ needs or instructors (Huang and Chiu, 2015). Objectives can be achieved in the shortest time with least efforts through e-learning. When managing the e-learning environment, its effect on educational learning are observed in providing equal access to the information regardless of the users’ locations, their ethnic origins, races, and ages. The environment for e-learning also help students or learners to depend on themselves so that instructors are no longer the solitary knowledge source rather they serve as guides and advisors (Joshua et al., 2016). Most of the studies have shown the positive effects of e-learning from the insights of learners or students (Gautam and Tiwari, 2016; Martínez-Caro, Cegarra-Navarro and Cepeda-Carrión, 2015; Chang, 2016). For instance; E-learning allows to observe much flexible learning ways to go for classes with much reduced need for travel. Learners are allowed to get deeper insights of the information through activities that are carried-out in the classroom through interactive video facility (Gautam and Tiwari, 2016; Martínez-Caro, Cegarra-Navarro and Cepeda-Carrión, 2015). This allow learners to respond promptly toward the activities.

1.5 Disadvantages of E-learning

Despite of the significant advantages of e-learning, students or learners encounter several challenges and Issues which ultimately lead towards either limited or negative outcomes. Arkorful and Abaidoo (2015) in their study outlined that e-learning, in certain cases is held through remoteness and contemplation resulting in lack of student’s interaction. In comparison with the contemporary mode of education, e-learning might result in being less effective due to the absence of face to face encounter with instructions or teachers. Since in e-learning method, assessments are generally held online which reduces the possibility of restricting illegitimate activities such as; cheating, plagiarism etc (Arkorful and Abaidoo, 2015). The absence of essential personal interactions is the most noticeable drawback of e-learning, not only among colleague learners, but also between instructors and learners (Islam, Beer and Slack, 2015). There is a scarcity of

community in the online learning environment as student-student engagement is much less of a concern when compared with student-instructor interaction. Gilbert (2015) highlighted that most of the students wish to work autonomously to avoid the need to interact with their classmates. The above literature studies indicated a significant influence of individualism and collectivism on organizational and individual impacts.

1.6 Conclusion

In underdeveloped and developing countries, e-learning raises the level of education, literacy and economic development. This is especially true for countries where technical education is expensive, opportunities are limited and economic disparities exist. E-learning can be highly beneficial to both students and institutions if properly implemented. The impact of E-learning and internet technology on the quality of education in the institutions of higher education has predominantly influence the current studies.

E-learning is a large and growing market with great potential in higher education and the students using E-learning performed better than students who did not use E-learning. In order to maximize this potential, E-learning implementations should endeavor to satisfy the needs and concerns of all stakeholder groups as much as possible

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Paper 8

Creative Teaching Strategies at Secondary Level- Feasibility and Process

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ABSTRACT

In the present study Researcher used experimental method and had made an attempt to practice different creative teaching strategies like integrated e-resource collaborative learning, project method, co-operative learning outdoor learning practice and to find its effectiveness on achievement in science among the secondary school learners. Learners are tested using achievement pre-test and post-test. Scores are analysed statically to calculate mean and standard deviation. Researcher found that mean scores of post-test is greater than pre-test. Hereby researcher found that through the practice of creative teaching strategies in the classroom teaching it is effective on achievement and also it improved learner's interest towards science subject.

Keywords: Creative teaching strategy, attitudinal changes, behavioural changes, achievement, science subject.

INTRODUCTION

The question why we teach science is important from more than one point of view. The answer to this question depends upon what we should teach in the subject and how we should teach it. It is known that the what and how have always been governed by 'why'. 'What' concerns with the curriculum. How concerns with the method, while why concerns with the objective and the process of thinking. The ability to think and reason is the most precious possession of the human brain. It is a fact that most of the new ideas have been discovered by reasoning. But to reason correctly one needs information and ideas. Moreover one must know how to use these ideas and information to discover the new truth. The classroom activities involve four components. The teacher, the student, the instructional material and the method of instruction. The final outcome is the resultant of the interaction of these four components.

The greatness of a nation depends upon its enlightened citizens. The citizens of tomorrow are shaped in

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today’s classroom. The educationist, teacher and researcher, who understood well the crucial role of classroom in national development are constantly engaged in improving it.

Students are creative by nature for that they have innate ability to see new relationships and produce new combinations that result in progress. Creative teaching strategies can develop creativity among pupils. Creative students are the valuable assets of the nation. The future of any nation depends upon the creative student.

Creativity is an important aspect of human development. The trend towards globalization with technological developments requires energy products that are productive and innovative people in all walks of life. Acculturation creativity is needed in the early development of the mind of an individual. Educational institutions are the most important places to nourish the creative talents and abilities of students and also as an important medium in the generation of creative minds of the students. Science curriculum taught in educational institutions is seen as a subject that can help to improve the quality of creative thinking among students.

The creativity was a very minor concern of psychology until the fifth grade of the twentieth century. In 1950, when J.P. Guilford became President of the American Psychological Association, in his inaugural speech he stressed the importance of studying creativity in addition to intelligence.

Creative teaching describes approaches and activities, developed and delivered by those who lead learning, which are usually exciting, innovative and often use unexpected techniques to engage learners. Human beings have always been creative. The fact that we have survived on the planet is testament to this. Humans adapted to and then began to modify their environment. We expanded across the planet into a whole range of climates. At some point in time we developed consciousness and then language. We began to question who we are, how we should behave, and how we came into existence in the first place. Part of human questioning was how we became creative. Creative teaching is an important skill needed by teachers to carry out the teaching and learning process. Teachers have the most important role in nurturing students’ interest and creative thinking ability by implementing creative teaching. Throughout the world, national governments are reorganizing their education systems to meet the challenges of the 21st century. One of the priorities is promoting creativity and innovation. Research into creativity in the 1980s and 1990s became rooted in a social psychological framework in which it is recognized that social structures affect individual creativity. (Rhyammar and Brolin 1999)

Creative teaching skills are about working towards the genesis of something unique both within and outside of the learner. It’s important to teach creatively for a few reasons. Creativity is the heart of the motivational classroom. It expresses students and teachers to express ideas and opinions in unique ways. The act of teaching in a novel and useful way that promotes student growth related to the development of original

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thought and action. Creative teaching focuses both on the methods a teacher uses to deliver learning and the overall effect those methods have on students and the outcomes produced. A process of designing and strategizing instruction in such a way so as to facilitate thinking skills especially creative thinking skills among students is called creative teaching. For example teachers teaching creativity to enhance originality in thinking in a class.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Piaget (2002), creativity is an “inborn aptitude” (p. 221), something the child 'has' and can potentially lose when they become socialized into norms and values. The inventiveness and curiosity that Piaget (2002) connects with creativity are only “deformed by adult society”. Six main elements contribute to creativity: intelligence, knowledge, thinking styles, personality, motivation, and the environment. Intelligence contributes using three elements drawn from Sternberg's diarchic theory Gardner's Intelligence Studies. 'Being creative enables children to make connections between one area of learning and another and so extend their understanding. This area includes art, music, dance, role-play and imaginative play. Creative teaching is defined as educational exchanges facilitated by the teacher that are “unique, customized and meaningful” (Rinkevich,2011), and that are exciting, engaging and innovative (Craft, 2011). Creative teaching is complex, involving a broad range of skills, experience, and perspectives (Ambrose, 2005). In the context of education, creativity is necessary for teaching and learning. Teachers need to be creative in teaching to get and retain students' attention, and for them to remain motivated in the classroom. Creative teaching can also make learning invigorating, meaningful, and realistic. To maintain the quality of teaching, teachers need to be creative to ensure that the teaching and learning process encourages students to experience meaningful learning ([Jasni et al., 2020](#)). The successful provision of a creative environment in education is largely dependent on teachers ([Bereczki and Karpati, 2018](#)). Hence, teachers need to be creative in teaching for developing unique and meaningful knowledge in the context of learning ([Huang et al., 2019](#)). However, the implementation of creative teaching in schools is poor and teachers do not make creative teaching a priority ([Hong et al., 2017](#); [Huang et al., 2019](#)). In the context of education, creativity is necessary for teaching and learning. Teachers need to be creative in teaching to get and retain students' attention, and for them to remain motivated in the classroom. Creative teaching can also make learning invigorating, meaningful, and realistic. It is defined as “the development and use of novel, original, or inventive teaching methods” ([Educational Resources Information Center \(ERIC\), 2017](#)). It is a process whereby teachers provide innovative curricula and adapt teaching strategies according to the needs of their students. The focus is on the characteristics of knowledge and the teaching environment to achieve learning goals ([Reilly et al., 2011](#); [Liu et al., 2022](#)). According to [Palaniappan\(2009\)](#) and [Jasni et al. \(2020\)](#), creative

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teaching is closely related to a variety of techniques and methods that incorporate elements of creativity and involve effective interactions between teachers and students ([Tan and Goh, 2007](#); [Palaniappan, 2009](#)).

Effective interaction between teachers and students includes transferring meaningful knowledge creatively ([Rinkevich, 2011](#)), improving teaching in terms of flexibility ([Sawyer, 2004](#)), and transferring open and existing knowledge to motivate and inspire students to explore and innovate ([Mariani and Ismail, 2015](#)). The effective teaching strategies used by the awarded teachers are: student-centred activities, a connection between teaching contents and real life, management of skills in class, open-ended questions, an encouragement of creative thinking and use of technology and multimedia. Integrated Activities are closely connected to life experience and a basis for the development of creative thinking within education. (Jeo-Shyan Horng, 2005). It was evident that principal's instructional leadership and creative teaching affects student learning satisfaction. The results also showed that the principal's instructional leadership affects student self-actualization, while creative teaching has no direct effect unless it is mediated by learning satisfaction. (Azam and Suyatno, 2022). The research showed that collaborative creativity models were effective in improving scientific creativity skills. (Astutik and Susantini, 2020). a creative teacher analyzes what the learners' needs and the results of the need analysis are used to formulate instructional goal and design instructional materials in a lesson plan. Effective instructional materials contain tasks and activities that promote not only cognitive skills but also psychomotor skills. None of teaching strategies is perfect in itself. In order to conduct an effective teaching, creative teacher chooses a variety of effective learning strategies that underpin each other to activate learners, to engage learners and to instill motivation to learn. Effective strategies are those that can transfer knowledge into practical application. Motivation is important to bring about successful learning. Creative teachers, well-designed instructional materials, and effective learning strategies are among important factors that motivate learners to learn. (Kunder Manurung, 2012). . Our results demonstrated that (a) the majority of teachers do not implement any teaching strategies that foster student creativity; (b) teachers who elicit student creativity turn out students that make substantial achievement gains; and (c) classrooms with high proportions of minority and low-performing students receive significantly less creative teaching. (John and Yeow, 2011). This case study of creative teaching possesses characteristics resembling creative acts in other domains (e.g., art, literature, physics, and economics) and presents a model for the education of future teachers. (Frank and Rejskind, 2011). According to cognitive views of creativity, creative problem solving can be defined as producing a novel method of solving a new problem. Creative teaching occurs when a teacher teaches subject matter in ways that help students to transfer what they have learned to creative problem solving. New developments in cognitive theories of transfer, mental models, and learning strategies are likely to contribute to our understanding of how to foster creativity in our students. (Richard, .E..Mayer).

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

1. To review the related literature related to effectiveness of creative teaching strategy in science teaching Learning process.
2. To prepare creative teaching instructional material in teaching Science for the improvement of cognitive level competencies in Achievement in science among the learners.
3. To find out the effectiveness of creative teaching instructional material on the achievement of the pupils of standard eighth of the government high school, Mangalore Taluk.
4. To find out whether there exist any difference between the means of the scores of the Pre-test and Post-test of “The test on Achievement in Science of standard eighth of the Government High School of Mangalore Taluk.

HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

The following are the hypotheses that are formulated for the study.

1. There is a significant difference between the means of the scores of the Pre-Test and Post-Test on the “Test on Achievement in Science” among the pupils of standard eighth of government high school of Mangalore taluk.
2. There is a significant difference between the means of the scores of the Pre-Test and Post-Test on the “Test on Achievement in Science” among the Boys of standard eighth of government high school of Mangalore taluk.
3. There is a significant difference between the means of the scores of the Pre-Test and Post-Test on the “Test on Achievement in Science” among the Girls of standard eighth of government high school of Mangalore taluk.

METHODOLOGY

Researcher used here Experimental method research method. Researcher used here single group pre-test post-test experimental design in the study. The In the beginning Pre-test on “Test on Achievement in Science” is conducted and scores were tabulated. Then the creative teaching instructional materials prepared for the topics of 8th standard and implemented in the classroom. The details of instructional strategy and topics developed by the researcher are given below.

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SL.NO.	NAME OF THE LESSON	CONCEPTS	CREATIVE TEACHING STRATEGY USED
1	Crop Production And Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Crop-types • Procedure in crop production • Manure-types and uses • Irrigation –types and selection • Weed- meaning, removal • Crop –storage. 	*E –resource integrated teaching-power point presentation integrated with video. * Field visit- outdoor learning-real exposure to agriculture – hands on experience of cultivation. * Visit to food storage granaries.
2	Synthetic fiber	Fiber- types-natural and synthetic Synthetic fiber- types, uses.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Videos on cotton, silk fiber-manufacturing. • Visit to textile industry- real exposure to manufacturing, dyeing etc. • Visit to textile shop-introduction to different type of fiber and its uses by expert.
3	Conservation of plants and animals	Conservation-meaning , importance Conservation-methods Reserved forest- national park-zoo Red data book, endangered species	Videos on – national park, reserved forest. Visit to Pilikula Nisargadhama-park and zoo- real view of flora and fauna and also conservation of plant and animal and also exposure to conservation of endangered plant species.

Researcher here limited topics only for three lesson from 8th standard. After teaching these concepts using these creative teaching strategy post –test was conducted. The result were tabulated and analyzed statistically by the researcher.

Table1: Number (N), Mean (M), Standard Deviation (SD) of the Pre-Test and Post-Test Scores on the test on Achievement in Science among the Pupils of Standard Eight of Government High School, Mangalore Taluk.

Variable	<u>N</u>	<u>MEAN</u>	<u>S.D.</u>
Pre-Test	30	51.20	5.93
Post-Test	30	73.85	3.03

OUTCOME OF THE STUDY

It is evident from the study that science teaching using creative teaching strategy remarkably effective method of teaching.

1. Teaching science using only chalk and talk method, lecture method will not be enough to understand the hidden taste and idea behind each concept in science.
2. If Science is taught using creative teaching strategy in the classroom give scope to arouse interest among the learner in teaching learning process.
3. Science teaching using creative teaching strategy improves student's achievement in science.
4. Teaching science beyond the classroom as one of the creative teaching strategy is a effective method to develop social skill among the learner.
5. Science is not a subject is to be taught without giving any learning experience to the learner. Hence if science taught using creative teaching strategy it will be a gateway to attain the objectives of teaching science.

CONCLUSION

Teaching method used in the classroom teaching learning process means a lot in the shaping of future citizens of the nation. The teaching method followed inside the classroom plays a great role in designing well-disciplined, knowledgeable, responsible, creative builders of the future nation. So it must be given much importance and priority to use creative teaching strategies in teaching learning process. Hence the attempt made by the researcher in teaching Science using creative teaching strategy like e-resource integrated teaching, outdoor learning, laboratory experiment, talk by experts and field visit helped to develop creativity, interest and curiosity to learn science among the learner and learners developed confidence to continue their education in Basic science. Totally teaching science using creative teaching strategy will help to achieve the objectives of teaching science.

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Paper 9

Women Skill Development: The Path to Economic Change and Sustainability

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: Skills development leads to financial sustainability. Most of the marginalized lack vocational education and need to develop their skills if they want to bring about a change in their economic status. There are different types of skills – soft skills, hard skills, transferable skills, hybrid skills, etc. Indian women have proven their skills in the workplace. Behind such success is a great story of struggle and freedom in the traditional social arena. In addition, the roles of women workers are changing, they have kept the traditional housework ethic. This study is dedicated to finding the root causes of the problems of working women. It also tries to find viable solutions that have been practiced elsewhere and that must be implemented on other social fronts. Some work-related skills should be acquired right from the start. To bring a change of income or gain wealth, it is not possible to have a profession and property alone, but by developing your skills you can also get a sustainable income. The purpose of this research is to understand women's empowerment and financial sustainability. For working women, it is important to use innovative technologies because of the modern lifestyle. This study explains the challenges women face, how to improve their skills and how they can change their economic status and sustainability.

Methodology / Design /Approaches: It is an exploratory study with the help of secondary data where the researchers have conducted a content analysis of various skills required for women to change their economic status and sustainability.

Findings and results: Continue improvement in Innovation skills, and consistency in the work, up-to-date knowledge is the basic requirement. Regular challenges like coping with family pressure, conditions of workplace harassment, and natural challenges like social and Psychological.

Originality/value: Content analysis of economic change and sustainability on skill development of the women in India.

Type of Paper: Descriptive research with exploratory research design.

Keywords: Skill Development, Women's Empowerment, Financial, Sustainability, Innovative.

I. INTRODUCTION

Women's skills development is becoming increasingly important to achieving economic changes and sustainability in today's quickly changing global scene. Women in the past experienced for a variety of socioeconomic obstacles that prohibited them from fully participating in the workforce and limited their access to possibilities for development and advancement [1]. Women receiving equal access to opportunities for training, education, and career development will help employees contribute more effectively, foster innovation and entrepreneurship, and develop the economy, these introductions set the stage for a thorough examination of how women's skill growth influences economic change and sustainability [2]. This research is devoted towards finding the root causes of the existing problems faced by women in Skill Development.

Women's skill development means the process of developing and perfecting the skills, knowledge and expertise of women so that they can be empowered and actively participate in various sectors of society [3]. It aims to close the gender gap by giving women the skills they need to succeed in their personal and professional lives. Women have historically faced many barriers and discrimination that have limited their access to education, employment opportunities and skill development programs. However, governments, organizations and communities have recognized the importance of gender equality and women's empowerment and have increasingly focused on promoting women's skills development [4].

Investing in women's skills development significantly benefits individuals, families and society. By acquiring new skills, women can improve their employability, earning potential and job prospects. This helps them break the cycle of poverty and increases their financial independence. In addition, experienced women participate in the overall development and growth of their community, being change makers and role models for future generations [5].

Various initiatives and programs have been implemented to support the skill development of women. These include vocational training programs, business development programs, mentoring and tutoring programs, and initiatives to promote science, technology, engineering and

mathematics (STEM) education for girls. Additionally, there are organizations and NGOs that focus on empowering women through skill development workshops, networking events and leadership development programs. Skills development not only creates jobs but also strengthens them. The goal of developing women's skills is not just to prepare them for work, but also to improve their performance by improving the quality of their work. [6]

India is one of the fastest growing economies in the world. Skill development has been a major agenda of the Government of India since the Eleventh Five Year Plan. India is the second most populous country; it has the second largest labour force and most of the working age population [7]. Women make up 49% of the total population. However, the status of Indian women is not the reason. The development of women is crucial for the economic development of any nation. India is a male dominated society, women are usually against all types of fences. To realize the goals of the harmonious development of the country, women must go hand in hand with men, which requires women's empowerment and education and skill play an important role in women's empowerment [8]. Marginalized sections of society, especially women, have insufficient access to education. India has gender-based education gaps. Education was considered an important tool to reduce socio-economic differences and build an inclusive society [9].

II. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To explore the role of education in empowering women
2. To analyse the benefits of capacity development through women's empowerment

III. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

1. Empowerment

Empowerment refers to moving from one place to another of vulnerability to a position of dominance [10]. Empowerment improves access to information and resources. Empowerment liberate women by facilitating their mobility, decision-making and awareness of their rights and opportunities. Due to life experience, women often have different perceptions, priorities and strengths than men, and as a result, they may make different choices. Empowerment includes higher literacy, higher educational attainment, awareness of rights and responsibilities, active participation in economic activity, better health care and equal access to productive resources, and better standards of living [11].

1.1 Women's Skill Development can have a significant impact

2. Skill Development Among the Women

India's demographic bonus has become a global topic as the world ages. Young people make up a significant proportion of India's population. This demographic dividend will soon become an asset to achieve prosperity and rise to global economic power. But to take advantage of this young population, we must provide them with qualifications and training opportunities [12]. This activity is soliciting curriculum ideas that help students develop their skills. This work begins with identifying skills and incorporating them into a curriculum that works for students. Improved skills are essential to address some of the most pressing challenges of inclusion, gender equality and access. Education contributes to skill development [13]. Skills and human capital are the cornerstones of economic prosperity and social well-being in the 21st century. Education is a crucial factor for innovation and human capital development and plays a key role in the stability and sustainability of the knowledge economy. Creating opportunities to utilize women's skills in the labour market is also necessary [14].

IV. Challenges and Opportunities for the Women

1. Gender Studies

- ✓ This interdisciplinary field explores the social, cultural, and economic dimensions of gender.
- ✓ She explores the challenges women face in accessing education, training and employment opportunities, and explores strategies to promote gender equality.

2. Labor Economics

- ✓ The industry focuses on workers, employers and labour market behaviour.
- ✓ It explores issues such as wage inequality, job discrimination, labour market participation, and the impact of skills and education on employment prospects [15].

3. Human Resource Development

- ✓ This area studies the processes of human capital development and management within an organization.
- ✓ This includes training, talent management, career development and organizational strategies to promote gender diversity.

4. Vocational Education and Training

- ✓ Vocational training refers to educational programs that develop the practical skills and knowledge required for a particular occupation.
- ✓ Participation in vocational education and training, the effectiveness of skill development programs for women, and the links between emerging industries and vocational education and training [16].

5. Entrepreneurship and Small Business Development

- ✓ This field focuses on the challenges and opportunities facing women entrepreneurs and small business owners.
- ✓ Explore the factors that influence women's entrepreneurship, access to finance, networking and business development support.

6. Sustainable Development

- ✓ Sustainable development includes economic, social and ecological dimensions.
- ✓ Sustainable development can highlight the role of women in promoting green practices, green jobs and inclusive growth.

7. Policy Analysis

- ✓ It is important to analyse policies and interventions to improve women's skill development and

economic empowerment.

- ✓ This includes examining the effectiveness of government programs, action policies and institutional frameworks to promote gender equality.

V. SUGGESTION

By empowering women through technology and entrepreneurship, we can pave the way for economic transformation and sustainability. It is essential to work with governments, educational institutions, industry experts and women themselves to design and implement comprehensive programs that address the specific needs and challenges of women in developing their skills. Women can contribute their skills as online communities, forums and social media can facilitate the exchange of ideas, best practices and resources.

VI. CONCLUSION

Developing women's skills is not only a matter of gender equality but also a strategic investment in the future of economies and societies. We can create a more inclusive, fairer and more sustainable world by empowering women and enabling them to reach their full potential. In order to achieve sustainable economic change and ensure a brighter future for all, it is important that we continue to prioritize and invest in the development of women's skills.

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Inclusive education: A Paradigm shift through Blended Learning Environment.

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ABSTRACT

Education system is always changing its environment by adopting the new methods in learning. The Covid-19 pandemic stunned the functioning of education systems all over the world. Blended learning got acceptability during these days. The blended learning approach revolutionized the whole education system. It was used in the western countries before pandemic but countries like India it was introduced as a new approach in order to overcome the covid pandemic lockdown. This paper is aimed at highlighting the blended learning environment in inclusive education. The need for practicing blended learning approach in ensuring the education of all students at various levels of school education. The paper attempts to understand the possibilities of digital technologies in inclusion and positivity in using technologies to reduce student dropouts. In focusing more specifically on the use of ICT for children with special needs the aim is to carry into effect the principles of equality, diversity in learning. We cannot restrict technology from the present educational system as the new generation demands its role in their learning. Technology has its hands which touches all walks of life, with endless knowledge and experience.

Introduction

Globalization and technological advancement create changes in almost all aspect of our life. Education is one of them. We have different sources of information and even education institutions are relying on technological sources to make them effective. Today we are trying to transform classroom atmosphere to address the needs of the 21st century learners. Use of information and communication technology continuously changes the way of transmitting information. Technology specifically, Information Communication Technology involves in school education in two ways as a subject to be learnt and as a tool in teaching learning process. In order to prepare our children for this new world dominated by technology, we need to change the way we educate them. The education of this century took a big leap which led to the

paradigm shift of closed model and teacher centered classroom to an open model and student- centered classroom leading to shift in teaching learning process from chalk and talk to interactive method. But the importance of teacher in the classroom is inevitable. For this a better solution to be the blending of traditional classroom with computer -mediated activities which is possible through blended learning. Blended learning has gained more urgency with recent challenges in education, during impact of the pandemic on education. Covid-19 lockdown has highlighted the need for education to be more responsive and resilient including Blended Learning strategies. Through different experience blended learning prepare the learners to face new challenges in the digital era.

Inclusive Education

In recent years Inclusive Education has developed in to a global policy movement which advocates the rights of disabled students to access quality participation in main stream educational institutions. Inclusive education is a new approach towards educating the children with disabilities with normal ones within the same classroom. Inclusive education is when all students, regardless of any challenges they may have, are placed in age appropriate general education classes that are in their own neighborhood schools to receive high quality instruction interventions, and support that enable them to meet success in the core curriculum (Bui ,Quirk ,Almazan ,&valenti, 2010;Alqurainin&Gut, 2012). Successful Inclusive Education happens primarily through accepting, understanding and attending to student difference and diversity, which can include physical, cognitive, academic, social and emotional. New technologies provide technical assistance that allows students with special needs to take active part in the process of interaction and communication. If a person has motor disability he may be helped to write, if a person is with a visual deficiency, he may be helped to read. Some kinds of disabilities don't allow students to use handwritten text that is an integral part of traditional education.

Blended learning

Blended learning has lot of scope to blend different approaches of learning like face-to-face learning, self-directed learning, online learning and virtual learning. These studies reveal the importance of blended learning strategies. B. Antony (2020) conducted a study on “Blended Learning Adoption and Implementation in Higher Education”. This study systematically reviews, synthesizes and provides meta-analysis of Blended Learning reach and articles. This study presents the factors that influence student, lectures and administration towards adopting Blended Learning. C.Senturk (2020) conducted a study on “Effects of the blended learning model on preservice teacher’s academic achievements and twenty- first century skills”. This study reveals the effects of blended teaching-learning approach on academic

achievements and twenty-first century skills of preservice teachers who took the teaching principles and method course. C.Dziuban (2018) conducted a study on “Blended Learning: The New Normal and Emerging Technologies.” This study addressed several outcomes, implementation and possible future directions for blended learning in higher education. R.K. Kavitha (2018) conducted a study on “The Student Experience in Blended Learning Environment.” Through this study the researcher examines the student’s experiences in blended learning environment.

The time has come to reject the dualistic thinking that seems to demand choosing between conventional face to face and online learning, a dualism that is no longer tenable, theoretically or practically. By the use of technology in the teaching learning process, we can improve quality, support curricular changes and provide new learning experiences. There is a better approach with the increasing awareness and adoption of the communication technology to correct learners a more sensible way forward would be to better understand the potential of these technologies and how they might be integrated with the best of the face-to-face learning. Both face to face and online learning are made better, offers the possibility of recapturing the traditional values of education while meeting the demands and needs of the twenty-first century. Blended learning not only seeking technology in learning but mixing up of different learning strategies along with classroom teaching. It doesn’t neglect the traditional classroom teaching but it blends the innovative techniques with the traditional teaching and makes the approach a blended one.

The term ‘blended’ encompasses a broad continuum and can include any integration of face to face and online instructional content. The blend of face to face and online material will vary depending on the content, the needs of the students and the preferences of the instructors. Blended learning is the combination of approaches like role play, simulation, dramatization and group work to make learning effective. Blended learning strategies cater to the needs of all learners regardless of their differences.

Importance of Blended learning environment in inclusive education

Education and equality of educational opportunities are needed for human development and development of the country. Inequality of educational opportunities is a big hurdle or barrier in all-round development of a person. In our country, education is not reaching to all children due to no of reasons like geographical areas, poverty, population and other social problems. Blended learning approach utilizes face to face teaching along with technology mediated teaching in order to help all students and it caters individual differences also. It provides different learning experiences.

Inclusive learning provides all children with access to flexible learning choices and effective paths for achieving educational goals in spaces where they experienced a sense of belonging. Blended learning approach is a good option that it will make the areas of educational opportunities wider. In an inclusive

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education environment all children, regardless of ability or disability learn together in the same age-appropriate classroom. It is based on the understanding that all children and families are valued equally and deserved access to the same opportunities. Blended learning approach caters to the needs of all learners. It provides a pinnacle of experience ranges from direct teaching to online learning. Blended learning approach is a flexible approach which incorporates different modes suited to different learners. Inclusive learning and teaching recognize all student’s entitlement to a learning experience that respects diversity, enables participation, remove barriers and anticipates and considered a variety of learning needs and preferences. Usually, the students with multiple disability or physical disability face the problems of attendance which leads to dropout exists in the traditional mode of education whereas using the blended learning it will ensure students attendance without their physical presence using the online mode. Physically challenged can also join in any of the institutions using the internet and technology. Personalized learning is also possible through blended mode and it helps each learner to learn at their own pace. It provides a variety of experience and enable the learners maintain active throughout the class. By blending multiple modes blended learning provides quality education and increase the rate of retention. Students having different learning disabilities learn with more powerful resources using this approach. Online learning helps students to get in touch with new knowledge and person having locomotor disability can learn and find online carrier in their future life. Blended learning approach provide endless opportunities to all people regardless of their abilities.

Technological pedagogical content knowledge

The technological content knowledge frame work describes the kind of knowledge required by teachers for the successful integration of technology in teaching. It suggests that teachers need to know about the inter sections of technology, pedagogy and content. Using of technological knowledge while teaching different concepts, making difficult areas easy to learn. The understanding of information technology broadly enough to apply presenting concepts, teaching theories, citing examples. Pedagogical techniques that use technologies in constructive ways to teach content. Here comes the designing and selection of different materials that can be utilize for each area. TPACK frame work outlines how content (what is being taught) and pedagogy (how the teacher imparts that content) must form the foundation for any effective educational technological integration. Technology has improved making teaching and learning more curious and interactive. It is teachers’ duty to incorporate the right type of technology into their subject while planning courses and providing learning experience. For the digital inclusion trends, we need some requirements from the part of school authorities, teachers and parents. Teachers should be provided with adequate training programs like seminars, online workshops, orientation programs and other educational

activities.

Conclusion

In today's hyper-connected world, sensible use of technology can enhance education. Technology is not meant to replace the teacher. Technology helps to create a flexible learning environment that breeds innovation. It shifts the classroom experience from the rigid approach to a more collaborative learning environment. Students can learn according to their abilities. Blended learning is an approach as well as a policy which considers all students with diverse learning style under the same roof. The no of techniques, resources and right blend of technology attracts different learners. It enables students to learn at their own pace. Blended learning can be a solution to many problems in the education sector. In a technology advanced era education with the right blend of technology and content can become the flexible mode of learning. Technology in education can open doors to unlimited experiences, new discoveries, and new ways of learning and collaboration.

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Paper 11

NEP 2020 referred deep-rooted-Indian-pride criteria as envisaged in the contest of Sanskrit to Prakrit Transformation

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ABSTRACT:

Purpose: NLP 2020 stresses upon promoting multilingualism in teaching and learning which is to be rooted in the ancient pride and tradition of India. So, the present paper intends to trace out the roots of Prakrit the power behind major Indian languages

Design/ Methodology/ Approach: Sanskrit the mainstream language of ancient of India and so always gets its due importance. And at the same time several Prakrit varieties emerged afterwards from Sanskrit played their own role in transforming the flow of Sanskrit over centuries and the formation of many more major Indo Aryan Languages off today. So a brief linguistic analysis is done to trace the Sanskrit to transformation. Prakrit plays a major role in the tradition history of Modern Indian languages which lead to the origin of modern Indian languages over a period of few centuries. And these languages include the 22 Languages of eighth schedule of Indian Constitution. NEP document recommends several programs for the development of Sanskrit, as well as establishing National Institute of Prakrit, Pali and Persian languages

Finding /Results: With this backdrop, the present paper discusses, in brief, the general characteristics of Prakrit which reflects its Sanskrit base and documented some evidences in this respect

Originality value: The theme of the present is based on content analysis of similar discussions by linguistic experts in the reference literatures quoted. The Sanskrit part is written in Devanagari script more clarity.

Paper Type: Conceptual Paper based on linguistic analysis with historical and descriptive approach

Key words: Sanskrit, Prakrit, NEP 2020

1.0 INTRODUCTION

In this section we first discuss what the NEP 2020 document specifies regarding the Language policy for learning Language at higher education level. And in the next stage a relation between Sanskrit and Prakrit is investigated with linguistic evidences.

2.0 REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The main literature of this study is the document published by Govt of India on new National Education Policy. The author consulted this literature to draw the following prescription for the theme of the present paper.

2.1 NEP -The Fundamental Principles of the Policy:

The new education policy 2020 suggests about promoting multilingualism and the power of language in teaching and learning. It stresses upon instilling a deep-rooted pride among learner in being Indian. Education as a whole must enlighten the rich, diverse, ancient and modern culture and knowledge systems and traditions It should be not only in thought, but also in spirit, intellect, and deeds, as well as to develop knowledge, skills, values, and dispositions that support responsible commitment to human rights, sustainable development and living, and global well-being, thereby reflecting a truly global citizen. So the role of promoting Languages, Art, Tradition and Culture of the mother land plays a major role in the process of Educating.

It is pointed out that Languages must also have consistent official updates to their vocabularies and dictionaries, widely disseminated, so that the most current issues and concepts can be effectively discussed in these languages. Strong departments and programmes in Indian languages, comparative literature, creative writing, arts, music, philosophy, etc. will be launched and developed across the country. More HEIs, and more programmes in higher education, will use the mother tongue/ local language as a medium of instruction, and/or offer programmes bilingually. SANSKRIT will be mainstreamed with strong offerings in school - including as one of the language options in the three-language formula - as well as in higher education. Sanskrit Universities too will move towards becoming large multidisciplinary institutions of higher learning. Sanskrit and all Indian language institutes and departments across the country will be significantly strengthened. National Institute (or Institutes) for PALI, Persian and PRAKRIT will also be set up within a university campus. Universities dedicated to languages will become multidisciplinary. For each of the languages mentioned in the Eighth Schedule of the Constitution of India, Academies will be established consisting of some of the greatest scholars and native speakers. These Academies for Eighth Schedule languages will be established by the Central Government in consultation or collaboration with State Governments. Academies for other highly spoken Indian languages may also be similarly established by the Centre and /or States. With this background of information we will focus our future discussions only on Prakrit its relation with Sanskrit and its progenitor connections to several modern Indian Languages.

3.0 OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

- (1) The main objective of the present study is to familiarize the Prakrits and their major role in building the modern India Language world
- (2) It also attempts to point out the Sanskrit roots of Prakrits on the basis of proper analysis of linguistic characteristics

4.0 SIGNIFICANCE OF SANSKRIT & PRAKRIT LANGUAGES

4.1 The place Prakrit in Indian Languages

Indo-Aryan (IA) literary history can be classified into three stages- Old (OIA), Middle (MIA) and the Modern Stage. OIA are days when Aryan arrived to Indian sub continent which is up to 500 BC. The two major dialects of this period were Vedic and the Sanskrit. Later in the MIA stage, which extends up to 11000 AD, the languages in use were Pali and Prakrit. And the present modern stage there after gave birth to so many new languages like Bengali, Hindi, Marathi, etc [1]

Thus Prakrit has a great role in the genesis stage of most of the modern India Languages. We may add some other languages included in the eighth schedule of Indian Constitution like Assamese, Kashmiri, Manipuri, Panjabi, Nepali, Oriya, Guajarati, Sindhi, Konkani, Santali, Maithili, and Dogri.

4.2 Prakrit and Sanskrit

The term Prakrit is derived from the word prakruti which means nature-natural. *प्रकृतेषुः प्राकृतम्* - It is a language occurred and flowed naturally hence a language of the people[2]. It comes from the other meaning of prakruti, ‘the basis’, which refers to the refined language Sanskrit. *प्राकृतीषु संस्कृतम्*. So Prakrit is what developed or what comes out from the Sanskrit [3].

Prakrit is therefore not so much controlled by the rules or grammar as to the extent that it happens with Sanskrit. And on the advent of Buddhism, Jainism Sanskrit was treated as tough and moved away from masses and Prakrit elevated its status by taking literary touch. So Sanskrit and Prakrit coexisted, perhaps Sanskrit stands as the Chronological precedence of to Prakrit.

As it is a natural situation that when people speak a language the speech need not uniform and in particular when they spread across regions dialects comes into existence. And we can just conclude that, in Indo Aryan Age, the more systematic dialect Sanskrit became literary language and all other remaining varieties with their colloquial forms become speech of the masses as Prakrit varieties

4.3 Prakrit and its Varieties:

Several varieties are found in Prakrit, which counts up to twenty seven. But among these some five to six are recognised well as dialects. Maharastri *महाराष्ट्री*, Souraseni *सौरसेनी*, Magadhi *मागधी*, Ardhamagadhi *अर्धमागधी*, Paishachi *पैशची*

It is said that the sermons of Buddha is written in Pali (*पाळी*). But many experts say that Pali is nothing but the first offshoot of Vedic Language, and so is called as the ancient Prakrit (*प्राकृत*). This variety again spread across Shoorasena kingdom (Mathura, Vrindavan etc) and hence this first branch was called as Souraseni Prakrit. And the third branch was the dialect Magadhi used in the kingdom of Magadha. Paishachi is the variety used by the lower level society sect in Northwest region of India. *ब्रह्मकथा* (*गुणाढ्य*) a wonderful composition in Paishachi is not available in its original form. It only leaves its traces in *कथासरित्सागर* (*सोमदेव*) and *ब्रह्म कथामञ्जरी* (*क्षेमेंद्र*). It is actually the modified form of Souraseni. Souraseni was prose form conversational variety of Prakrit. Avanti and Apabhramsa are some other varieties that can be mentioned here [4]. It is surprising to note that people enjoying he performance in which both Sanskrit and Prakrit languages are used. Maharastri was used in verse form and others like Magadhi and Souraseni were in prose form.

4.5 Linguistic Literatures of Prakrit:

प्राकृत प्रकाशा (*वररुची*) is the first available grammar book on Prakrit which covers Maharastri Paishachi Magadhi Souraseni varieties. *प्राकृत लक्षणम्* (*कवी चंद्र*) is another old grammar mainly covers Maharastri. But the most descriptive complete grammar of Prakrit is *सिद्धहेमचंद्र* (*हेमचंद्र*) which covers other varieties like *प्राकृतानुशासन* (*पुरुशोत्तम*), *प्राकृतरूपावतार* (*सिम्हराजा*). Other than these, there are many other grammar Books on Prakrit which are either commentaries on these main books or on some particular varieties of it.

5.0 ANALYSIS OF LINGUISTIC CHARACTERISTICS OF PRAKRIT

Some of the phonological and morphological characteristics of ancient Prakrit can be identified especially from the most ancient form of Prakrit found in literature like sermons of Buddhadeva. They look like the some formulae that help us to understand the conversion process of Sanskrit to Prakrit:

(i) If we take Sanskrit nouns in nominative case singular ending with ‘अ’ or carries a visarga (अः) at the end,

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in Prakrith it will change as ‘ओ’ where the visarga clubs with ‘अ’ (सूत्र: ॥ सो 2-1-52 ॥) as in pp 19 (1) [4] .

So, visarga is completely lost pp 172 (f) [1].

घोटकः - घोटको (Horse)

वंशः - वंसो (Bamboo, Pedigree)

पुरुषः - पुरिसो (Male)

अतः - अतो (Therefore)

ततः - ततो (From there) [4]

(ii) In all Plural form of feminine noun with in nominative and accusative cases, ओ joins and it occurs after the previous इ to become यो afterwards

नद्यः - नदय - नजज - नज्जो (to rivers, from rivers)

स्त्री - इत्थी - इत्थियो (women, to women)

Sanskrit consonants clusters get eliminated by processes like assimilation, metathesis svarabhakti. We will now examine a few cases below:

(iii) Homo-organic Consonant undergoes regressive assimilation. (For definition of Assimilation vide Appendix 1):

For example in a homo organic Cluster (इ, ग) first undergoes regressive assimilation (ग, ग) then reduces to geminate form of later phoneme

भुक्तम् - भुततम् - भुत्तम् (eaten)

खडग - खगग - खग्गो (sword)

(iv) In the case of hetero-organic groups progressive assimilation takes place to end up with geminate form of stronger consonant. That means the clusters stop (occlusion)(क्, ग्) is followed by liquid, nasal, glide etc

(न्, म्) the process of assimilation will be like,

नग्न - नगग - नग्गो (naked)

चक्रम् - चकरम् - चक्को (wheel)

There will be regressive assimilation if a stop follows other varieties like in

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वल्कलम् - वलकलम् - वक्कलम् (garment made of bark)

(v) If a cluster has a sibilant (श, ष, स) and a stop the sibilant get assimilated with the stop. And the stop gets aspirated in the process

भिक्षु - भिकषु - भिककु - भिख्यु (monk)

सुष्क - सुषक - सुक्क - सुख्य (dry)

(vi) If in a cluster the dental stop is followed by a palatal /y/, then it gets palatalized like

सत्य - सतय - सचय - सच्च (truth)

विद्य - विदय - विजय - विज्ज (knowledge) [1]

मृत्यु - मृतयु - मच्यु - मच्चु (death)

गद्यम् - गदयम् - गजजम् (prose) [4]

(vii) Sometimes the consonant cluster when it gets into Prakrit form it get separated by a vowel

यज्ञ - यज्ज - यजन (worship)

पृत्वि - पृत्वि - प्रितिवि (earth)

(viii) In closed syllables then contrast for the length of the first syllable is lost like in

राज्यम् - राज्जम् - रज्जम् (kingdom)

आद्य - अद्द - अज्ज (today) [1]

आत्मा - अत्ता (soul)

रात्री - रातरी - रत्ती (night) [4]

And in some cases this contrast takes place after a Palatalization

पांडित्यम् - पांडिच्यम् - पंडिच्च्यम् (scholar) [4]

(ix) Metathesis is observed in a small class of words with phoneme like /r/ and the cluster which undergoes metathesis first, finally results in geminates of second sound by assimilation.

प्रेमन् - पेर्मन् - पेम्मन् (love)

क्रिडा - किर्डा - किडुडा (play)

The major changes in morphological characteristics are listed below:

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- (x) All the consonant endings of nominal stems are removed. And so, in Prakrit the distinction between vocalic and consonant endings is fully removed.
- (xi) So the majority of Prakrit stems are reduced to अ, इ, उ, (masculine and neuter nouns) अ, इ, ई, उ, ऊ (feminine nouns)
- (xii) Out of the three varieties of number only singular and plural are retains the dual is lost for ever
- (xiii) The dative case (संप्रदान्/चतुर्थ् विभक्ति) merges with genitive (संबन्ध्/षष्ठी विभक्ती)
- (xiv) The future tense is represented by स्स or हि
- (xv) The two way conjugation distinction found in Sanskrit (thematic and athematic) is eliminated in Prakrit
- (xvi) The active voice usage is terminated to passive and middle voice
- (xvii) इत्त an aorist (past perfective) form which is used to create a tense other than the present tense

6.0 CONCLUSIONS

Discussion on Sanskrit and Prakrit covers a very major part of the deep rooted pride of Indian Languages. It gives the background knowledge of the role of Sanskrit in Building a robust foundation for the later era of Prakrit. The analysis of linguistic characteristics of Prakrit provides good evidence that how it got evolved from the basis of Sanskrit.

7.0 RECOMMENDATIONS

There is ample scope to do more analytical study on various grammatical Literature which is spread over different Schools of grammar like eastern western etc. Also many commentaries on Prakrit grammars have powerful thoughts which could expose in depth language structure and the transformational patterns

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APPENDIX 1

Definition of phonological Processes

(i) **Assimilation** is a process in which two phonemes which occur in sequence, then some aspect of one phoneme is taken away by the other. That means either the adjacent phonemes influence partially each other in progressive or regressive way. Or the influence may be complete type. In the first case phonemes are said to become Homo-organic and in the second case the phonemes are said to be geminate.

(2) **Homo-organic consonants** are consonant sounds which are articulated in the same position or place of articulation in the mouth say pronounced with lips [प] [ब] [म], or pronounced by touching the tip of tongue to the upper gums: [ट] [द] [स] [न] [ल].

(3) **Geminate** means consisting of same identical adjacent speech sounds like consonants. It is the process of doubling of consonants.

(4) **Metathesis** is a process of sound change where in there is a rearrangement of the sounds (vowel or consonants) or syllables in a word or in a sentence. It refers to the reversal of position of sounds or contiguous sounds that can occur between two sounds either at adjacent or at non adjacent positions.

A study on Personality traits among the Secondary School Students of Malekudiya Tribe.

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Personality is a characteristic way of thinking, feeling, and behaving. Personality embraces moods, attitudes, and opinions and is most clearly expressed in interactions with other people. It includes behavioural characteristics, both inherent and acquired, that distinguish one person from another and that can be observed in people's relations to the environment and to the social group. The word 'personality' derives from the Latin word 'persona' which means 'mask'. Personality development is a part of skill development as it prepares people to express your thoughts with clarity and precision. Personality development and soft skills go hand in hand. You can instantly become more appealing if you know how to present yourself in situations. This comes by honing certain skills that can help you progress in your career. Since the Secondary School Malekudiya Tribe Students are considered as disadvantaged group and are deprived of some facilities and opportunities, they must be provided with provisions and practical solutions for the development of personality. The present study is a Survey nature to find out the different dimensions of Personality traits among the Secondary School Students of Malekudiya Tribe. The sample of the study consists 210 students. Statistical techniques such as Mean, SD, 't' test were calculated to interpret the data. The tool used was "Junior Eyesencks Personality Questionnaire" developed by Hans Jurgan Eyesenck and Dr. Sybil B.G. Eyesenck. The analysis of the study revealed that 40.5% of students fall under Neuroticism dimension of personality, 54.7% of students come under Stability dimension. Whereas 4.8% of students data has been rejected because their **Lie scores** are found more than 5 in scale. And also it is found that the boys and girls of Secondary School level Malekudiya Tribe do not differ in their Extroversion and Introversion dimension, Neuroticism and Stability dimension of Personality Trait.

Key words: Personality traits, extroversion, introversion, stability, neuroticism

1.1.0 Introduction

Personality isa characteristic way of [thinking](#), feeling, and behaving. Personality embraces moods, attitudes, and opinions and is most clearly expressed in interactions with other people. It includes

behavioural characteristics, both inherent and acquired, that distinguish one person from another and that can be observed in people’s relations to the environment and to the [social group](#). The word ‘personality’ derives from the Latin word ‘persona’ which means ‘mask’.

Personality refers to individual differences in characteristic patterns of thinking, feeling and behaving. It is the characteristic sets of behaviours, cognitions, and emotional patterns that evolve from biological and environmental factors. The study of personality focuses on two broad areas: One is understanding individual differences in particular personality characteristics, such as sociability or irritability. The other is understanding how the various parts of a person come together as a whole.

The study of personality can be said to have its origins in the fundamental idea that people are distinguished by their characteristic individual patterns of behaviour—the distinctive ways in which they walk, talk, furnish their living quarters, or express their urges. The systematic psychological study of personality has emerged from a number of different sources, including psychiatric case studies that focused on lives in distress, from philosophy, which explores the nature of man, and from physiology, anthropology, and social psychology.

Personality development has become an important tool today for developing overall skills within a person that help him to develop professionally as well as personally. With the help of good training a child or an adult can learn communication skills, different subjects, driving, improve vocabulary, pronunciation or computer operating that plays an important part in personality development. Similarly, a proper training in personality development enhances the general as well as unique traits or characteristics of a person. These days basic personality features like confidence, spoken skills as well as language skills are very important for making a mark professionally. A teacher of personality development helps a person to get a positive thought pattern, gain confidence, improve behaviour, learn better communication and develop a healthy physique.

Personality development helps you develop an impressive personality and makes you stand apart from the rest. Personality development also plays an essential role in improving one’s communication skills. Individuals ought to master the art of expressing their thoughts and feelings in the most desired way. Personality development makes you a confident individual who is appreciated and respected wherever he goes.

Personality trait or dimensions compels an individual to behave consistently in diverse contexts. These characteristics can be used to compare people. These characteristics are referred to as “pretty permanent” because they do not alter over time. An introvert, for example, may no longer be an introvert after ten years. Some of the important traits are: Introversion-extraversion, Neuroticismstability, Psychoticism, conscientiousness, openness, agreeableness.

These dimensions represent broad areas of personality. Research has demonstrated that these groupings of characteristics tend to occur together in many people. For example, individuals who are sociable tend to be talkative. However, these traits do not always occur together. Personality is complex and varied and each person may display behaviours across several of these dimensions (Varywell).

Research suggests that both biological and environmental influences play a role in shaping our personalities. Always remember that behaviour involves an interaction between a person's underlying personality and situational variables. The situation that a person finds himself or herself plays a major role in how the person reacts. However, in most cases, people offer responses that are consistent with their underlying personality traits.

1.2.0 Review of related literature

Helion (2021), has conducted a study on ‘ Analysis of personality traits and academic performance in higher education at a Colombian university’. This paper arises from the question of the correlation between specific personality traits and academic performance, since it is of crucial importance to consider variables other to students’ grades that also affect this phenomenon. The objective was to correlate personality traits with the academic performance of students in a higher education institution. This is a quantitative, co relational research, with a final sample of 214 students. Results confirmed that there is a positive correlation between those variables. Personality traits of abstractedness and perfectionism correlate with academic performance. Results show that perfectionism and abstractedness traits and sex, affect academic performance. It is still important to notice that there are other factors (beyond the scope of this research) that could possibly have a significant impact on academic performance.

ShabirAhamad Malik (2020),has conducted a study on ‘ the personality traits among the school going students’.The research paper attempted to assess and compare personality traits (openness, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness and emotional stability) among secondary school students. The sample of the present study composed of 100 secondary school students (50 male and 50 female) selected from Ganderbal District. Standardized tool were used to draw information. Statistical analysis of the data was done using frequencies, percentages, Mean, SD, and t- test and it was observed that in case of personality traits majority scored average with only a meager percentage falling in high and low categories. The comparative analysis revealed that secondary school students do not differ in their personality traits with respect to gender except the trait of conscientiousness and emotional stability. The comparative analysis also showed that the secondary school students do not differ in their personality traits except the trait of agreeableness with respect to family status.

Dr. B.ReenaTok (2017), has conducted a study on’ “A STUDY ON PERSONALITY TRAITS OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN LOWER DIBANG VALLEY DISTRICT OF ARUNACHAL PRADESH WITH REFERENCE TO SOME NONCOGNITIVE VARIABLES”. The purpose of this study was to investigate the personality traits of secondary school students in Lower Dibang Valley District of Arunachal Pradesh. For this study, normative survey method of research was used. The sample consists of 210 secondary school students from Lower Dibang Valley District of Arunachal Pradesh. Personality traits scale developed by R.B Cattell and Cattell (1968) was used for data collection. Mean (M), Standard deviation (SD), and t-test was used to analyze the data and the result revealed that male and female, urban and rural, non-tribal and tribal secondary school students does not differ in their personality traits and mean scores shows that male, urban, non-tribal secondary school students have higher personality traits than female, rural and tribal secondary school students of Lower Dibang Valley District of Arunachal Pradesh. Based on these findings some suggestions were given with great implication for further studies.

Dr. Dhanasakaran (2015), has conducted a STUDY ON PERSONALITY AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT OF SECONDARY LEVEL SCHOOL STUDENTS. The present study explored the extent to which the Personality and Academic Achievement of Secondary Level School Students. The survey research method was used for the study. In the present study sample of 500 students (250 boys and 250 girls) were taken by using propositante simple random sampling technique. Personality scales developed by the investigator on 2015 were used for data collection. Moreover, for academic achievement Marks obtained in the IXth class of the State board, Aided and Matriculation board for assessing the achievement of students. The findings of the study revealed that: (i) There no significant difference between boys and girls secondary level students on personality. (ii) There no significant difference between boys and girls secondary level students on academic achievement.

Ghazi, S., Shahzada, G. and SaifUllah (2013), investigated relationship between students' personality traits and their academic achievement in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. Theoretical framework of this study is based on Big Five Personality Trait Theory (Cattell's and Eysenck's 1973). The objective of the study was to find out different personality traits of secondary school students and to identify the relationship between personality traits and their overall academic achievement. Results of the study revealed that no significant relationship was found between the students' personality traits and their academic achievement.

1.3.0 Need for the study

An individual's personality refers to his/her appearance, characteristics, attitude, mindset and behaviour with others. Personality development helps you gain recognition and acceptance from the society as well as people around. Personality development plays an essential role not only in an individual's professional but

also personal lives. It makes an individual disciplined, punctual and an asset for his/her organization. Personality development grooms an individual and helps him make a mark of his/her own and helps to develop a positive attitude in life. It encourages individuals to look at the brighter sides of life. An individual with a negative attitude finds a problem in every situation. Rather than cribbing and criticizing people around, analyze the whole situation and try to find an appropriate solution for the same.

Personality development plays an important role in developing not only your outer but also inner self. Human being is a social animal. One needs people around. An individual needs to have that magnetic power which attracts people towards him. You need to have that charisma of yours. Personality development helps you gain recognition and acceptance from the society as well as people around. It makes an individual disciplined, punctual and an asset for his/her organization. **Personal development** is more than just working on talents you already have but it is a part of Self-awareness: it's about growing, developing, getting progressively mind, and increasing significant capacities that you can use to affect this world. We people have the power and capacity to shape our characters anyway we wish. At the point when we create ourselves to be all that we can be, we add to our own, just as the bliss of others.

Personality development is a process where you work on yourself to nurture your talents and add new skills to your arsenal. None of us is born with the ability to excel in various fields; however, experience and training prepare us to use our talents. Personality development is a part of skill development as it prepares people to express your thoughts with clarity and precision. Personality development and soft skills go hand in hand. You can instantly become more appealing if you know how to present yourself in situations. This comes by honing certain skills that can help you progress in your career. Since the Secondary School Malekudiya Tribe Students are considered as disadvantaged group and are deprived of some facilities and opportunities, they must be provided with provisions and practical solutions for the development of personality.

Therefore, the study on the status of Personality of Secondary School Students of Malekudiya Tribe is very significant. From the review of literature it's found that many studies have been done on personality traits of Secondary school students, but no study is found among these secondary school students of Malekudiya tribe. With this focus in mind through the study, the investigator intended to explore the status of Personality traits of Secondary School Students of Malekudiya Tribe. In this context, the present study assumes a greater significance in the field of education especially among the socially disadvantaged group Malekudiya tribe.

1.4.0 Statement of the problem

A study on Personality traits among the Secondary School Students of Malekudiya Tribe.

1.5.0 Objectives

1. To measure the Extroversion and Introversion dimensions of Personality among the Secondary School Students of Malekudiya Tribe.
2. To measure the Neuroticism and Stability dimensions of Personality among the Secondary School Students of Malekudiya Tribe.
3. To find the difference in Extroversion dimension of Personality among the Secondary School Students of Malekudiya Tribe in terms of gender.
4. To find the difference in Introversion dimension of Personality among the Secondary School Students of Malekudiya Tribe in terms of gender.
5. To find the difference in Neuroticism dimension of Personality among the Secondary School Students of Malekudiya Tribe in terms of gender.
6. To find the difference in Stability dimension of Personality among the Secondary School Students of Malekudiya Tribe in terms of gender.

1.6.0 Hypotheses

H.0.1 Boys and girls of Secondary School level do not differ in their Personality traits.

1.7.0 Methodology

The study followed descriptive survey method.

1.8.0 Population

All the Secondary School Students of Malekudiya Tribe of Kadaba Taluk were the population of the study.

1.9.0 Sample

Sample of the study included 210 Secondary School Students of Malekudiya Tribe.

1.10.0 Tools for the study

The Personality traits of Secondary School Students of Malekudiya Tribe were measured using “Junior Eyesencks Personality Questionnaire” developed by Hans Jurgan Eyesenck and Dr. Sybil B.G. Eyesenck.

1.11.0 Statistical techniques

Descriptive statistics namely Mean, Median, SD were used to analyse the data. Hypotheses were tested using ‘t’ at 0.05 level of significance.

1.12.0 Analyse and Interpretation of data

1.12.1 Objective one: To measure the Extroversion and Introversion dimensions of Personality among the Secondary School Students of Malekudiya Tribe.

Table: 1.1 showing the measurements of Extroversion and Introversion dimensions of Personality among the Secondary School Students of Malekudiya Tribe.

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Personality trait	No. of students	Percentage %
Extrovert	110	52.4
Introvert	90	42.8

In Table: 1.1, the measurements of Extroversion and Introversion dimensions of Personality among the Secondary School Students of Malekudiya Tribe are shown. While considering the dimensions, it has been found that 52.4% of students fall under Extroversion dimension of personality, 42.8% of students come under Introversion dimension. Whereas 4.8% of students data has been rejected because their **Lie scores** are found more than 5 in scale.

1.12.2 Objective two: To measure the Neuroticism and Stability dimensions of Personality among the Secondary School Students of Malekudiya Tribe.

Table: 1.2 showing the measurements of Neuroticism and Stability dimensions of Personality among the Secondary School Students of Malekudiya Tribe.

Personality trait	No. of students	Percentage %
Neuroticism	85	40.5
Stability	115	54.7

In Table: 1.2, the measurements of Neuroticism and Stability dimensions of Personality among the Secondary School Students of Malekudiya Tribe are shown. While considering the dimensions, it has been found that 40.5% of students fall under Neuroticism dimension of personality, 54.7% of students come under Stability dimension. Whereas 4.8% of students data has been rejected because their **Lie scores** are found more than 5 in scale.

1.12.3 Objective three: To find the difference in Extroversion dimension of Personality among the Secondary School Students of Malekudiya Tribe in terms of gender.

Table- 1.3 Number(N), Mean(M), Standard Deviation(SD) and ‘t’ value of the Secondary School students of Malekudiya Tribe in terms of gender.

Gender	N	M	SD	‘t’ value	Significant level
Boys	45	18	1.5		Not significant

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Girls	65	17.1	1.5	0.0007	at 0.05 level
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From the table-3, it is observed that the obtained ‘t’ value 0.0007 is lesser than the Table value 1.98 at 0.05 level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis, “There is no significance difference among the boys and girls of Secondary School level Malekudiya Tribe in their Extroversion dimension of Personality Trait” is accepted and it is concluded that the boys and girls of Secondary School level Malekudiya Tribe do not differ in their Extroversion dimension of Personality Trait.

1.12.4 Objective four: To find the difference in Introversion dimension of Personality among the Secondary School Students of Malekudiya Tribe in terms of gender.

Table- 1.4 Number(N), Mean(M), Standard Deviation(SD) and ‘t’ value of the Secondary School students of Malekudiya Tribe in terms of gender.

Gender	N	M	SD	‘t’ value	Significant level
Boys	40	16.8	1.5	0.191	Not significant at 0.05 level
Girls	50	17	2		

From the table-4, it is observed that the obtained ‘t’ value 0.191 is lesser than the Table value 1.99 at 0.05 level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis, “There is no significance difference among the boys and girls of Secondary School level Malekudiya Tribe in their Introversion dimension of Personality Trait” is accepted and it is concluded that the boys and girls of Secondary School level Malekudiya Tribe do not differ in their Introversion dimension of Personality Trait.

1.12.5 Objective five: To find the difference in Neuroticism dimension of Personality among the Secondary School Students of Malekudiya Tribe in terms of gender.

Table- 1.5 Number(N), Mean(M), Standard Deviation(SD) and ‘t’ value of the Secondary School students of Malekudiya Tribe in terms of gender.

Gender	N	M	SD	‘t’ value	Significant level
Boys	38	17.1	1.8	0.275	Not significant at 0.05 level
Girls	47	17	1.4		

From the table-5, it is observed that the obtained ‘t’ value 0.27 is lesser than the Table value 1.99 at 0.05 level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis, “There is no significance difference among the boys and girls of Secondary School level Malekudiya Tribe in their Neuroticism dimension of Personality Trait” is accepted and it is concluded that the boys and girls of Secondary School level Malekudiya Tribe do not differ in their Neuroticism dimension of Personality Trait.

1.12.6 Objective six: To find the difference in Stability dimension of Personality among the Secondary School Students of Malekudiya Tribe in terms of gender.

Table– 1.6 Number(N), Mean(M), Standard Deviation(SD) and ‘t’ value of the Secondary School students of Malekudiya Tribe in terms of gender.

Gender	N	M	SD	‘t’ value	Significant level
Boys	47	17.5	1.8	0.339	Not significant at 0.05 level
Girls	68	20	1.9		

From the table-3, it is observed that the obtained ‘t’ value 0.339 is lesser than the Table value 1.98 at 0.05 level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis, “There is no significance difference among the boys and girls of Secondary School level Malekudiya Tribe in their Stability dimension of Personality Trait” is accepted and it is concluded that the boys and girls of Secondary School level Malekudiya Tribe do not differ in their Stability dimension of Personality Trait.

1.13.0 Major findings of the study

1. It has been found that 52.4% of students fall under Extroversion dimension of personality, 42.8% of students come under Introversion dimension.
2. It has been found that 40.5% of students fall under Neuroticism dimension of personality, 54.7% of students come under Stability dimension.
3. There is no significance difference among the boys and girls of Secondary School level Malekudiya Tribe in their Extroversion dimension of Personality Trait.
4. There is no significance difference among the boys and girls of Secondary School level Malekudiya Tribe in their Introversion dimension of Personality Trait.
5. There is no significance difference among the boys and girls of Secondary School level Malekudiya Tribe in their Neuroticism dimension of Personality Trait.

6. There is no significance difference among the boys and girls of Secondary School level Malekudiya Tribe in their Stability dimension of Personality Trait.

7. About 4.8% of students' data has been rejected because their **Lie scores** are found more than 5 in scale.

1.14.0 Educational implications of the study

1. Orientation and workshops should be conducted by the department and school authority to train teachers in organizing curricular and co-curricular activities which enhance Personality traits of the Secondary School Students of Malekudiya Tribe.

2. Special emphasis during inservice programme should be given in organizing community service programmes or outreach programmes, so that the teachers can effectively organize activities which enhance the Personality traits of their students from Malekudiya Tribe.

3. Since NCC, NSS, Scouts and Guides provide ample of opportunities to enhance students; personality traits, these organisations should be started in every Secondary School.

4. The Social Institutions including the school and family should provide a conducive environment for proper development of human personality.

5. Teachers should provide enabling environment that suits the varying personality characteristics of children in a learning situation.

6. Each individual owns a responsibility to himself to fully understand his own personality and positively develop capacity to manage and deploy the attributes to productive endeavours.

7. It is recommended that continuous research should be conducted by scholars to explore and shed more light on the relationship between personality development and the education process.

8. Awareness programme should be conducted to make the students realize about the importance of Life skills. A democratic environment in the classroom needs to be created so that students get an opportunity to implement these values in day today life and enrich their Personality.

1.15.0 Limitations of the study

1. This study can be applied to a large sample of Secondary School Students of Malekudiya Tribe.

2. This study can be applied on large sample of young adults or college level students.

3. Further study can be conducted on students in terms of different Streams of Courses.

4. Further survey can be done on a large sample on wide areas of Personality traits.

1.16.0 Conclusion

Personality refers to the enduring characteristics and behaviour that comprise a person's unique adjustment

to life, including major traits, interests, drives, values, self concept, abilities and emotional patterns. Personality development is a multi dimensional aspect and covered all the areas of life, mainly education. Indian Constitution, Indian Education Commission (1966) and National Education Policy (1986) have focused the need of developing Personality among Secondary School students, more focusing the socially disadvantaged group and the Tribal communities. **NEP2020** has given prominent facilities and opportunities to endure the challenges and grow up with better personality. **The New Education Policy 2020** has highlighted the need for developing personality among Secondary school students. It is the responsibility of the teachers to organise personality development programmes to enable the learners to attain integrated development of personality.

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Paper 13

REVOLUTIONIZING EDUCATION: EXPLORING THE POTENTIAL OF ADAPTIVE LEARNING TECHNOLOGIES IN E-LEARNING INITIATIVES

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ABSTRACT

In the era of digital transformation, the field of education is undergoing a profound revolution, with e-learning initiatives at the forefront of this transformation. Adaptive learning technologies, powered by artificial intelligence (AI) algorithms, have emerged as a promising solution to personalize and enhance the learning experience. This presentation aims to explore the potential of adaptive learning technologies in revolutionizing education and transforming e-learning initiatives. The traditional one-size-fits-all approach to education is being challenged by adaptive learning technologies that enable personalized and tailored learning experiences. Adaptive learning technologies leverage AI algorithms to analyse learner data and provide individualized instruction, feedback, and resources. By adapting the content, pace, and complexity of learning materials to suit each learner's needs, adaptive learning technologies address the limitations of the traditional classroom setting and accommodate diverse learning styles.

Intelligent tutoring systems, one of the key applications of adaptive learning technologies, provide personalized guidance and support to learners. These systems use AI algorithms to assess learners' knowledge, track their progress, and deliver targeted interventions. By identifying knowledge gaps and offering customized feedback, intelligent tutoring systems enhance learning outcomes and improve retention rates. Looking ahead, the future of education lies in the continued advancement of adaptive learning technologies. Emerging trends, such as the integration of virtual reality and augmented reality, further enhance the immersive and personalized learning experiences offered by adaptive learning technologies. The role of educators remains vital in leveraging these technologies effectively, guiding learners, and creating meaningful learning experiences that harness the full

potential of adaptive learning technologies.]

Keywords: Adaptive learning technology, e-learning, Intelligent tutoring system.

INTRODUCTION

The rapid advancements in technology have given rise to transformative changes in various sectors, and education is no exception. E-learning initiatives have gained significant momentum in recent years, allowing learners to access education anytime and anywhere. However, to maximize the effectiveness of these initiatives, it is crucial to harness the power of adaptive learning technologies. Adaptive learning leverages the power of artificial intelligence, data analytics, and cognitive science to tailor educational content and delivery methods to the unique needs of each learner. By continuously assessing learners' knowledge, skills, and learning styles, adaptive learning technologies can dynamically adjust the learning experience, providing personalized pathways, targeted interventions, and real-time feedback.

The potential of adaptive learning technologies in e-learning initiatives is immense. By harnessing the capabilities of these technologies, educators and institutions can create a more inclusive and effective learning environment, ensuring that learners receive the support they need to succeed. Adaptive learning promotes individualized instruction, allowing learners to progress at their own pace, focus on areas that require more attention, and explore topics of interest in greater depth. Moreover, adaptive learning technologies have the capacity to transform the role of educators. Instead of being mere providers of information, educators can become facilitators, mentors, and guides, utilizing data-driven insights to offer personalized guidance and support to each learner. This shift from a teacher-centric to a learner-centric approach fosters greater engagement, motivation, and ownership of the learning process.

OBJECTIVES

The main purpose of this study is to facilitate a comprehensive understanding of adaptive learning technologies in e-learning initiatives. The specific objectives are:

1. To understand the concept of Adaptive Learning Technologies and its potential to enhance educational experiences.
2. To identify the role of adaptive learning technologies in e-learning initiatives.
3. To find out the potential obstacles of adaptive learning technologies.

METHODOLOGY

The paper is descriptive in nature, based on secondary data, and attempts to discuss the concept of Adaptive Learning Technologies and its potential to enhance educational experiences. Books, journals, newspapers, articles, and government websites are used to gather secondary data. The information has been collected by using the keywords Adaptive learning technology, e-learning, and Intelligent tutoring system through Google Scholar and Sci-Hub. The required articles were obtained by electronic search and manually screened.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Adaptive learning technologies refer to educational tools and platforms that use artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning algorithms to personalize the learning experience for individual students. These technologies are designed to adapt and adjust to each student's unique needs, abilities, and learning styles. By analysing data on student performance, preferences, and progress, these technologies create personalized learning paths and provide targeted feedback. They offer flexible and accessible learning opportunities, allowing students to study at their own pace and convenience. With their ability to adapt and adjust to each learner's needs, adaptive learning technologies enhance engagement and motivation. They generate valuable data-driven insights that help educators make informed instructional decisions. While not intended to replace teachers, these technologies serve as valuable tools to support and augment the traditional classroom experience, offering personalized instruction and scalable learning opportunities.

KEY FEATURES AND BENEFITS OF ADAPTIVE LEARNING TECHNOLOGIES

1. **Personalized Learning:** Adaptive learning technologies provide personalized instruction by analysing data about each student's performance, preferences, and progress. This enables the system to tailor the content, pacing, and difficulty level of the learning materials to suit the individual learner.
2. **Intelligent Feedback:** These technologies offer immediate and targeted feedback to students, helping them understand their strengths and areas for improvement. The feedback is often based on the student's responses and performance data, allowing for targeted interventions and support.

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3. **Individualized Instruction:** Adaptive learning platforms can dynamically generate individualized learning paths for each student. As students’ progress, the system adapts and modifies the content and activities to match their current knowledge level, ensuring that they are appropriately challenged and engaged.
4. **Data-driven Insights:** Adaptive learning technologies generate a wealth of data about students' learning behaviours and outcomes. Educators can utilize this data to gain insights into student progress, identify learning gaps, and make data-informed instructional decisions.
5. **Flexibility and Accessibility:** These technologies can be accessed anytime and anywhere, offering learners the flexibility to study at their own pace and convenience. Additionally, adaptive learning platforms can often accommodate different learning modalities, providing support for diverse student needs.
6. **Enhanced Engagement:** By tailoring the learning experience to each student's interests and abilities, adaptive learning technologies aim to increase learner engagement and motivation. Interactive and gamified elements are often incorporated to create an immersive and enjoyable learning environment.
7. **Scalability:** Adaptive learning technologies can be implemented at various educational levels, from K-12 schools to higher education institutions and corporate training programs. They have the potential to scale and support large numbers of learners with personalized instruction.

It's important to note that while adaptive learning technologies offer valuable benefits, they are not intended to replace human teachers or the traditional classroom experience. Instead, they serve as tools to augment and support educators in their instructional practices, providing personalized learning opportunities and data-driven insights.

OBSTACLES OF ADAPTIVE LEARNING TECHNOLOGIES

Adaptive learning, with its potential to tailor instruction to individual learner needs, faces several obstacles that need to be addressed for its effective implementation. One significant obstacle is the infrastructure and technology required. Implementing adaptive learning necessitates a robust technological setup, including hardware, software, and reliable internet connectivity. However,

many educational institutions, particularly those in resource-constrained settings, may struggle to provide the necessary technological resources to support adaptive learning initiatives. Without adequate infrastructure, the seamless integration and implementation of adaptive learning become challenging.

Another obstacle lies in data collection and privacy concerns. Adaptive learning relies on gathering and analysing extensive amounts of data about learners' behaviour, performance, and preferences. While this data is valuable for personalizing instruction, privacy concerns arise when sensitive student information is collected, stored, and used for adaptive learning purposes. Striking the right balance between utilizing learner data effectively and safeguarding privacy is crucial and requires adherence to strict data protection regulations.

Content and curriculum adaptation present another significant challenge. Developing adaptive learning materials and curricula that effectively cater to individual learner needs requires substantial effort and resources. It involves designing multiple pathways and learning experiences tailored to different learners. Ensuring the quality, accuracy, and relevance of adaptive content across various subjects and educational levels is vital for its success. Curriculum designers and educators must work together to create adaptable content that addresses the diverse needs of learners.

Teacher training and support is a critical obstacles that must be overcome. Adaptive learning requires teachers to shift their roles from traditional lecturers to facilitators and mentors. However, teachers may face challenges in adapting to this new approach. They need proper training and ongoing professional development to effectively use adaptive learning technologies, interpret learner data, and provide personalized guidance. Adequate support systems should be in place to address any concerns or difficulties that teachers may encounter during the transition.

Equity and access are fundamental considerations for adaptive learning. While it has the potential to personalize education for all learners, there is a risk that adaptive learning technologies may exacerbate existing educational inequities. Factors such as socioeconomic disparities, lack of internet access, and limited availability of devices can hinder equitable access to adaptive learning resources and opportunities. Efforts must be made to bridge the digital divide and ensure that all learners, regardless of their background, have equal access to adaptive learning.

Pedagogical and motivational factors also pose obstacles. Adaptive learning should not only deliver

customized content but also engage learners, foster critical thinking skills, and promote motivation and self-directed learning. Balancing personalized instruction with effective pedagogical strategies is crucial for the success of adaptive learning. Overemphasis on adaptive algorithms without considering pedagogical aspects can undermine its effectiveness in promoting meaningful learning experiences. Lastly, cost and sustainability are significant obstacles to consider. Implementing adaptive learning can require substantial financial investments, including acquiring appropriate technology, developing adaptive content, and providing teacher training and support. Educational institutions must carefully evaluate the costs and benefits of adaptive learning initiatives and consider long-term sustainability to ensure their viability and scalability.

Addressing these obstacles requires collaborative efforts among policymakers, educators, technology developers, and researchers. By acknowledging and actively working to overcome these challenges, adaptive learning can be leveraged to enhance educational experiences and improve learning outcomes for a diverse range of learners.

CONCLUSIONS

Adaptive learning technologies have the potential to revolutionize education by providing personalized and tailored learning experiences. By leveraging AI algorithms and data-driven insights, these technologies enable educators to cater to individual learner needs, improve engagement and outcomes, and unlock the full potential of e-learning initiatives. However, it is crucial to address challenges related to ethics, data privacy, and inclusivity to ensure the responsible and equitable implementation of adaptive learning technologies in education.

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“Online Education-A Boon for Work life Balance”

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ABSTRACT

In today’s contemporary world scenario, our professional life one must need to gain more education and knowledge to do a particular given task. A particular degree is very much necessary for higher level job posts. A certificate is required to get a task to perform and also to upgrade our knowledge, skills, in order to continue our journey in professional life. If we are a working employee for a full time, then really it’s a great wonder that how we are going to manage the “Time” in travelling and sincerely attend the classes effectively. Especially if we are working late night or having our personal family commitment. In today’s challenging life one must keep on updating their knowledge, skills through the help of some certification courses. Because without the certification courses one cannot able to go for reputed top positions by doing the challenging task in the world.

As today there is a drastic development in the field of information and technology which surprise all personal and professional activities. Today’s knowledge and skills for doing a particular task or a job has very less life span because of the improvement in the science and technology. In present context everything was becoming outdated very easily in a very short span of time. So to survive in the present competitive world one must keep on upgrading their skills and knowledge throughout their life.

Keywords: online education, work life balance, challenging days, science and technology.

1. INTRODUCTION:

Performing of a full time job with our personal and professional desires, really our life will be into a challenging position. Present conditions like COVID-19, working full time in tier 1 cities made most of us to opt for online. Today’s online education or training programmes either for students or for employees of organizations are designed in such a way that, they must feel comfort in reaching their goals easily. Present online training or educations are customized in a way that the path of the candidate must be clear and fill confident in reaching their destiny with more speed and accuracy. Current online training/education programmes have made the listeners understand and complete their courses with the mixture of audio,

video, live interactions etc.

2. OBJECTIVES:

- a) To understand the meaning of online education.
- b) To analyze the factors responsible for the increase in online education.
- c) To know why online education is becoming popular.
- d) To evaluate the present scenario of online education.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

The study aims at analyzing today’s working employees working condition and competitive world. This research focuses on how online education benefits the working employees in balancing their both personal life and professional life. Data collected from secondary sources like websites of online education institutions and corporate company’s employees.

4. Meaning of ONLINE EDUCATION:

Online learning means one who learns from remotely. It is also be called as distance education, E-learning, internet learning, digital learning etc. It helps the learner not to attend the class physically but mentally it prepares in accessing to the programme being from where ever place, from which ever place he is interested through the help of internet.

5. Factors responsible for the increase in ONLINE EDUCATION:

- a) Online education was very poor or low in earlier days.
- b) Started learning from different places and trainers.
- c) Development in science and technology
- d) Advancement in cell phones.
- e) Contents can be easily accessible.
- f) Available at anytime and anywhere.
- g) More expert and knowledge trainers.
- h) Programmes designed in customized way.
- i) Recognition to online education.
- j) Quality in online service education.
- k) More advertisements of E-learning programme.
- l) Covid-19 pandemic conditions.
- m) Changes in government rules in education sector.

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6. Reasons for popular of ONLINE EDUCATION:

- a) **Online courses can be easily measured:** when an organization having more than 50-100 employees' workers, then the online learning education/programme makes it more easy and effective in learning. Training and development for teams to educate their employee for taking of new challenges and work effectively in the work places. Along with this, in offline learning or teaching the employees physically will be more time consumption and expensive. From a research study it shows that 40 to 60% less employee's time will be consumed by online education than the offline education.

- b) **Employee loyalty will be increasing:** When the employees will be given with an accredited online education, they feel that it helps them increasing personal life and professional life and starts thinking feeling of loyalty to the company. They feel that the organization have provided valuable knowledge which their competitiveness will get increases. Around 18% boosting can be found in employee engagement by the online education.

- c) **Flexibility through online learning:** It makes employees to feel accessible to any part of the world for enhancing their knowledge for any courses, for any place and any number of times. Online education helps employees to look after personal work and professional work in a simultaneous time increasing their skills and knowledge.

- d) **Safe learning places through online education:** Everyone wants to enhance their skills and knowledge and want to be competitive in today's world. But for this there are so many problems especially with going and attending to the classes where it is held. Conditions like women it still be problem to going and attending he programmes far away from their workplace and coming late night to their houses. Conditions like covid-19 pandemic conditions which made human beings not be crowded and not to travel and need to maintain distance. In the above causes we can see it is safe. IBM study found online education enhances 5times more material in a short period of time.

- e) **Improve remembering nature:** Usually in the natural learning a employee can remember around 75% of the programme. But with the online education the employees can visit the websites repeatedly until they became perfect with less cost, minimum time spending etc. Along with this research institute of America said up to 25% to 60% online education boosted the retention rates in the organization.

- f) **Easy feedback:** Today in online education, some of the programmes gives the immediate feedback to the employees those who attends the programme. It helps the employees in conducting some small tests or

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continuous respond of employees to the screen shows how much % that candidate attended classes. What important portion that he missed. All this can be give through feedback immediately.

- g) Reduces harmful impact on the environment:** By using of offline education it found that employees spend more on the travelling, attending the classes. With this travelling emission can be prevented and usage of electricity and other sort of expenses. According to Britain Open University study states that online education comes less than 90%of energy as compare with offline education. Thus online education is good compare with offline education.
- h) Helps in tackling Business needs:** In some organizations some employees will be very good at selling but they might not be having a proper knowledge. In this type of employees, the employees can gain that required knowledge and can get useful tricks to overcome the problems in the organizations. According to Deloittee, organizations realize the value for personalized learning design approach.
- i) Available in wide range formats:** The more advantage is that the online education, now a day’s available to the employees in different languages they like, different time duration like short videos and long videos, videos or power point presentation, through stories and animated etc which helps employees to increase their productivity and became competitive in the world.
- j) Save costs and increases productivity:** Some of the online education programme providing education through paperless which in turn saves trees which uses for manufacturing of papers etc and through instant learning they can inculcate any knowledge anywhere. According to IBM study every dollar invested in online education leads to 30 dollars increase in productivity. Along with this 22% faster in production and productivity have found.

7. Present Scenario/status of online learning (facts):

- a) In 2021 the e-learning market size was around 210.1 billion and it is to be 848.12 billion in 2030.
- b) In 2021 remote learners around 17.3 million in US with coursera and in India it was 13.6million learners.
- c) Online learning education revenue market may reach around 4.73 billion dollars in 2023.
- d) India ranks 2nd in online education with 9.8 million learners. US ranks top with 14 million learners.
- e) As of 2020, online learning grew by 38 billion dollars from 2017 to 2022 and 6 billion dollars upward trajectory found.
- f) Online courses and MOOC Courses

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Course Name	Learners	Course
Coursera	45 million	3800
Edx	24 million	2640
Future learn	10 million	800
Swayam	10 million	1000

Conclusion:

Online programmes emerged as a new tool for learners with great easily available anytime, anywhere, any number of times with different modes, method, varieties feasible for learners in their level. In this context online education and training programmes made a great mile stones in achievement in balancing of life with their personal and professional life.

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Promoting Achievement through Experiential Learning among Secondary School Students

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ABSTRACT

The research paper is on promoting achievement through experiential learning among the students of standard ninth. Experiential learning in language could be learner-friendly and foster achievement by the implementation of 5E's constructivist instructional module. In experiential learning students are playing an active role and learn to reflect on their learning experiences. Thus, helps in developing skills, attitudes, and new ways of thinking among the learners. In the present study, the researcher has reviewed prior studies and in-depth analysis of literature was done to formulate hypothesis. The quasi-experimental method was designed for students from the CBSC board and English as the medium of instruction. The 25 students were taught using the conventional method of teaching and 25 students were taught using 5 E's constructivist instructional module and experiential learning. The 5E's constructivist instructional module prepared for the topic of **My Beginning (English Prose)**. The 5E constructivist learning model includes Engage, Explore, Explain, Elaborate and Evaluate. The Pre-test was conducted before the implementation of the program and the post-test was administered after the program. Data were analyzed by applying the t-test and the hypotheses were tested. The study revealed that the experimental group has performed better in the achievement test in language as compared to the control group. The researcher found that experiential learning in language increases the autonomy among the learners, and it is best achieved when teacher acts as a facilitator of learning. Thus, it can be said that instructional program based on 5E's constructivist approach and experiential learning activities enhances achievement. The study recommends that, such learning can be imparted in different curriculum and also for different age groups of students.

Key Words: Experiential Learning, 5E's constructivist Instructional module

1. INTRODUCTION:

Today's Education scenario is incorporated with technology. Modular teaching is one of the widespread and recognizes teaching-learning technique. Considering individual difference among the learners, it is

necessary to plan appropriate teaching strategies for them. Such learning can impart through experiential learning with instructional module. The learning which enhances hands-on experiences leads to meaningful learning among the students. Experiential Learning is one of the approaches of constructivist learning (Amin 2011). As stated by Lewis and Williams “In its simplest form, experiential learning means learning from experience or learning by doing”. Experiential education first immerses learners in an experience and then encourages reflection about the experience to develop new skills, new attitudes or new ways of thinking.” (Lewis & William 1994)

2. LITERATURE REVIEW:

Laney (1993) compared experience-based learning with experiential approaches in teaching of Economics. The findings supported the advantage of experience-based instruction over experiential approaches.

Siegel, Omer and Agrawal (1997) conducted research on theory of experiential learning in relation to video simulation of an audit. The results showed significantly better performance of students in the experimental group as compared to control group.

Gibbons and Gray (2002) conducted a comparative study on social work education by integrated approach based on experience. The model propagated that learning is effective by doing, working experiences, collaborative approach with integrating theory and practice.

Smart and Csapo (2007) studied the impact of learning by doing and engaging students through learner-centered activities. The study revealed that active learning resulted in positive learning outcomes.

3. THE RATIONALE OF THE STUDY:

The present education system is changing, so there is a need to promote learning based on a learner-centered approach. The idea of the experiential learning with 5E’s constructivist instructional module in language provides a meaningful learning experience among the students of standard ninth. And the instruction focuses on building the learners to reflect on the learning process at their own pace. The instructional module program could be used for enhancing achievement in language and influence achievement through experiential learning. The 5E’s of the constructivist approach are Engage, Explore, Explain, Elaborate, and Evaluate. The study was intended for ninth standard students of CBSE board curriculum.

4. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY:

Learning is the process of acquiring new skills, knowledge, behavior, attitudes, and achievement of values. It involves an ongoing, active process of inquiry, engagement, and participation in the learning process. Engaging the learners in the different learning process in language increases their attention and motivates them to practice critical thinking skills which intern promote autonomy for insightful learning experiences.

The researcher thinks that the instructional strategies in the language classroom with experiential learning to promote achievement in classroom which leads to a fun learning environment. The study has implications for curriculum designers to include instructional module for different grade levels. The study also expected to be beneficial to students in language subjects, as well as other subjects can be incorporated through it. As a consequence of teaching learner through the experiential learning with instructional program would enhance their achievement scores to higher level.

5. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

- To study the pre-test achievement scores from experimental and control group of ninth standard students.
- To study the post-test achievement scores from experimental and control group of ninth standard students.
- To study the effectiveness of developed instructional module with traditional method of teaching in relation to achievement scores of experimental groups of standard ninth.

6. HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY:

To facilitate present study the following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

- There is no significant difference between the pre-test achievement scores from experimental and control groups of ninth standard students.
- There is no significant difference between the post-test achievement scores from experimental and control group of ninth standard students.
- There is no significant difference between the mean scores of pre-tests and post-test achievement in language from experimental group of ninth standard students.

7. METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY:

The study was based on the quasi-experimental method along with pre-test post-test parallel group design. The aim was to enhance achievement through experiential learning for experimental group and conventional method for control group students. The population of the study consists of students of standard ninth from CBSC board curriculum and English as a medium of instruction. The experimental and the control group included 25 and 25 students respectively. The experimental group was taught by experiential learning with instructional module, and control group was taught the same topic by conventional method of teaching.

7.1 Intervention Program

The intervention program was conducted for the experimental group and conventional method was used for the control group of the study. The appropriate learning experiences were developed by the researcher. The program includes varied task, group and individual activities, think and share with partner, videos & group discussion, students’ reflection on learning for the topic in language. The pre-test was conducted for both experimental and control group of students. After execution of the program, post-test was conducted for both the groups. The effectiveness was measured by comparing pre-test and post-test scores of controls and experimental group using statistical techniques. The significant difference was measured by comparing pretest and posttest achievement scores of experimental groups.

8. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS:

Null hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between the pre-test achievement scores from experimental and control groups of ninth standard students.

Group	N	Mean	SD	‘t’ ratio	Level of significance
Pre-test	25	32.5	4.53	0.33	Not Significant at 0.05 and 0.01Level
Post-test	25	32.09	4.19		

$df=25+25-2=48$, Table value at 0.05 level =2.01 At 0.01 level = 2.68

Table 1

If we look at Table-1, it shows that the obtained t-value 0.33 which is less than the table value both at 0.05 and 0.01 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis was accepted. Therefore, the null hypothesis stating that, there is no significant difference in mean scores of pre-test achievement in language between experimental and control group before implementation of the program.

Null hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between the post-test achievement scores from experimental and control group of ninth standard students.

Group	N	Mean	SD	‘t’ ratio	Level of significance
Pre-test	25	34.78	4.97	7.53	Significant at

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Post-test	25	45.63	5.23		0.05 and 0.01Level
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df=25+25-2=48, Table value at 0.05 level =2.01 and at 0.01 level = 2.68

Table 2 If we look at Table-2, it shows that the obtained t-value 7.53 which is higher than the table value both at 0.05 and 0.01 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, the null hypothesis stating that, there is a significant difference in mean scores of pre-test achievement in language between experimental and control group.

Table 3. t-test between mean scores of pre-tests and post-test Experimental Group

Experimental Group	N	Mean	SD	't' ratio	Level of significance
Pre-test	25	32.09	4.19	10.18	Significant at 0.05 and 0.01Level
Post-test	25	45.63	5.23		

df=25+25-2=48, Table value at 0.05 level =2.01 and at 0.01 level = 2.68

Table 3

If we look at Table-3, it shows that the obtained t-value 10.18 which is higher than the table value both at 0.05 and 0.01 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis was rejected. It means that there exists significant difference between the mean pre-test and post-test scores of IX grade students of experimental group. It means there is a significant difference in post test scores after implementation of the program. The finding shows that the experimental group was benefited with the program.

9. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION:

In the present study, it's found that there is no significant difference in pre- test mean scores in language between experimental and control group before implementation of experiential learning among the students of ninth. The study revealed that there is a significant difference in post-test achievement scores in language between experimental and control group after the treatment. Instructional module was found to be effective than traditional method of teaching. After implementation of the experiential learning, there was a change in students' perception and contributed to promote the achievement. The 5E's of constructivist approach found to be significant in raising achievement scores of students from experimental group as compared to traditional approach from control group students. Sanya Sachdeva (2017) has given importance to role of

experiential learning and encouraged dialogue, involvement of students in learning process. Study conducted by Abdulkadir showed that the 5E learning cycle based on constructivist approach has a positive effect on achievement levels and attitude of the experimental group of the study. Therefore, this study has provided evidence which support the result of present study. Engaging learners in learning process increased their autonomy, and motivated to be creative in sharing their learning experience. The researcher found that experiential learning with 5 E’s constructivist instructional program strengthens students’ potential to develop their deeper understanding of concepts.

10. CONCLUSION:

The study concluded that experiential learning in language promotes achievement among the students of standard ninth. Moreover, the 5 E’s constructivist instructional module is effective in enhancing achievement in language as compared to the conventional method of teaching. The innovative approaches in teaching-learning will be beneficial for learners to boost their deeper understanding as well as interest in language among the students. The study concluded that experiential learning in language enhances achievement, and it is best achieved when teacher acts as a facilitator of learning. In sum up, the results of the study would provide a framework for educators to implement best practices that will lead to raise the achievement level of students in language.

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Impact of NEP on Higher Education & Language Policy

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ABSTRACT

National Educational Policies are a set of policies formulated by the Government of India to promote education in Indian. The New Education Policy introduced by Indian Government (NEP 2020) is a positive change in the field of education. The new policy replaces the previous National Policy on Education, 1986 transform both elementary and higher education in India by 2040. Lot of reforms and new developments have been introduced by NEP in the higher education sector which will create a positive difference in the higher education. The policy also brought reforms that will affect every student, from playschool level to a degree considering a Ph. D. program. The language policy in NEP is a broad guideline and advisory in nature; and it is up to the states, institutions, and schools to decide on the implementation. The new National Education Policy (NEP) has a segment called ‘multilingualism, and power of language’. Under ‘multilingualism, policy has emphasized mother tongue/local language/regional language as the medium of instruction at least till Grade 5, but preferably till Grade 8 and beyond. No language will be imposed on any student. NEP 2020 has impacted school and college education equally; but this article mainly focuses on NEP 2020, salient features of NEP related to higher education, its impact on Higher Education and language policy.

Keywords: National Education Policy, Higher Education, Multilingualism, New Policy

Introduction:

After 34 years India brought significant changes to its education system. The National Education Policy (NEP) was unveiled on 31st July 2020.

The first NEP was announced by the Government of India by Prime Minister Indira Gandhi in 1968, the second by Prime Minister Rajiv Gandhi in 1986, and the third by Prime Minister

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Narendra Modi in 2020. The National Education Policy 2020 (NEP 2020), which was approved by the Union Cabinet of India on 29 July 2020, outlines the vision of India's new education system. The new policy replaces the previous National Policy on Education, 1986. The policy is applicable to all levels of education, from elementary education to higher education as well as vocational training in both rural and urban India. The National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 mainly focused on higher education that prepare the next generation to new digital India.

Review of related Literature

Foreign Universities will be allowed to set up campuses in India. It will promote research and bring flexible approach. The foreign universities would bring in programme and institution mobility. The idea of internationalization of higher education is based on the mobility of students, faculty members, programmes and institutions across countries. **(Prof. Jagdish Sheth)**

Technology will be part of education planning, teaching, learning, assessment, teacher, school and student training. The e-content to be available in regional languages, starting with 8 major languages – Kannada, Odia, Bengali among others to join the e-courses available in Hindi and English.

The new NEP is focused on increasing the Gross Enrolment Ratio in higher education space which is currently around 26%. This is much lesser than other countries such as China, Brazil and North American nations. The Indian government needs to introduce stronger policies for educational infrastructure development. It has to promote foreign direct investments (FDI) and open up the External Commercial Borrowing (ECB) route to strengthen the capital pool for the sector. As rightly mentioned by Finance Minister, Nirmala Sitharaman during the 2021-22 Budget speech, the country needs greater inflow of finance to attract talented teachers, build better infrastructures and formalize measures which will enable sourcing ECBs and FDI. **(Avanse Financial Services)**

A Higher Education Council of India (HECI) will be set up to regulate higher education. The council's goal will be to increase gross enrollment ratio.

The HECI will have 4 verticals: a) National Higher Education Regulatory Council (NHERC), to regulate higher education, including teacher education, while excluding medical and legal education. b) National Accreditation Council (NAC), a "meta-accrediting body". c) Higher Education Grants Council (HEGC), for funding and financing of universities and colleges. This

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will replace the existing National Council for Teacher Education, All India Council for Technical Education and the University Grants Commission. d) General Education Council (GEC), to frame "graduate attributes", namely the learning outcomes expected. It will also be responsible in framing a National Higher Education Qualification Framework (NHEQF). The National Council for Teacher Education will come under the GEC, as a professional standard setting body (PSSB). **(timesofindia.indiatimes.com)**

We have found that there are 35 mother tongues as mediums of instruction, and as part of the three-language formula, 160 languages as well as mother tongues are taught (for example, Hindi is a mother tongue and a language, while Garhwali is a mother tongue but not a language). The first roadblock in implementing NEP is providing study material, and our focus for the first year is to prepare books in the languages of the Eighth Schedule of the Constitution from Class 1 to the post-graduate level in all streams of education such as Science, Humanities and Commerce. **Chamu Krishna Shastry)**

Need for the study

There is low level of enrollment in higher education institutions. India's current GER is 26.3 per cent lower than the developed countries. Present NEP 2020 is very much concerned about the higher education where it is trying to prepare the population for digital India.

NEP language policy stresses more on the use of mother tongues in education from grade one to the post graduate level in all streams. Introduce of NEP 2020 in education will bring change in economical and digital efficiency level of India. Main objectives of this study are to understand about NEP 2020, salient features of NEP related to higher education, its impact on Higher Education and language policy.

Etymology

Education:

The process of receiving or giving systematic instruction, especially at a school or university.

Policy:

A course or principle of action adopted or proposed by an organization or individual.

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Language:

The principal method of human communication, consisting of words used in a structured and conventional way and conveyed by speech, writing, or gesture.

Educational Policy:

Education policy consists of the principles and policy decisions that influence the field of education.

Definitions:

According to **John Dewey** "Education is the development of all those capacities in the individual which will enable him to control his environment and fulfil his responsibilities.

According to **Heinrich Pestalozzi** "Education is natural harmonious and progressive development of man's innate powers.

Henry Sweet, an English phonetician and language scholar, stated: "Language is the expression of ideas by means of speech-sounds combined into words

National Educational Policies 2020

The National Education Policy (NEP) was approved by the Union Cabinet of India on July 28th, 2020. After a gap of 34 years, the Indian government consolidated feedback from 2.5 lakh village-level stakeholders to two national parliamentary level committees, over more than 50 months of consultations and workshops.

The National Education Policy is expected to bring positive and long-lasting impact on the higher education system of the country.

The vision of the National Education Policy is: "National Education Policy 2020 envisions an India-centric education system that contributes directly to transforming our nation sustainably into an equitable and vibrant knowledge society by providing high-quality education to all."

Salient features of NEP related to higher education

1. **Recognizing, identifying, the unique capabilities** of each student and helping them to develop in both academically and non- academically with the help of teachers and parents.
2. Achieving Foundational Literacy and Numeracy by all students by Grade 3.

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3. **Flexibility**, helping learners to choose their interested field and thus bringing out their talents
4. No hard separations between arts and sciences, between curricular and extra-curricular activities, between vocational and academic streams, etc. It is multidisciplinary education.
5. Understanding the concept is given more importance than rote learning and learning-for-exams.
6. Creativity and critical thinking to encourage logical decision-making and innovation;
7. Ethics and constitutional values like empathy, respect for others, cleanliness, courtesy, democratic spirit, spirit of service, respect for public property, scientific temper, liberty, responsibility, pluralism, equality, and justice are given importance in the curriculum.
8. Promoting multilingualism and the power of language in teaching and learning;
9. Focus on regular formative assessment for learning rather than the summative assessment that encourages today’s ‘coaching culture’;
10. Use of Technology in Education
11. Respect for diversity and respect for the local context in all curriculum, pedagogy, and policy, always keeping in mind that education is a concurrent subject;
12. Teachers and faculty as the heart of the learning process – their recruitment, continuous professional development, positive working environments and service conditions;
13. Continuous review of progress based on sustained research and regular assessment by educational experts;
14. A rootedness and pride in India, and its rich, diverse, ancient and modern culture and knowledge systems and traditions.
15. Education is a public service; access to quality education must be considered a basic right of every child;
16. Multiple entry and exit programme. There will be multiple entry and exit options for those who wish to leave the course in the middle. Their credits will be transferred through Academic Bank of Credits.

Impact of National Educational Policy 2020 on Higher Education

The National Education Policy is expected to bring positive and long-lasting impact on the higher education system of the country. Under New Educational policies foreign Universities will be allowed to set up campuses in India. It will promote research and bring flexible approach and helps

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students to experience the global quality of education in their own country.

Importance given in teaching ethical as well as constitutional values will help in developing national spirit among the Indians.

The new policy focuses on online and e-learning. Online education will play an extensive role to bridge the gap between the students and the institutes.

New Education Policy is not just about the degree. It is all about developing life skills and vocational courses.

The National Research Foundation (NRF) proposed by the NEP is likely to create a dedicated focus towards the quality research, including lightening the research funding by making it competitive and also by improving efficiency of funding processes to have more targeted approach towards funding research initiatives. Research activities will be imbibed in the students from their younger age itself.

The introduction of single common entrance test is positive step which will reduce the stress of multiple competitive exams it will also ensure a level playing ground for all student applicants going forward. Establishing Academic Bank of Credit (ABC) is definitely a robust idea to store the academic credits that students earn by taking courses from various recognized higher education institutions. A student can earn scores by completing a course and these will be credited to the ABC account. One can then transfer these credits if he/she decides to switch colleges. If a student ever drops out for some reasons, these credits will remain intact which means he/she can come back years later and pick up from where the student had left.

National Educational Policy 2020 and Language policy

There is enough research and evidence now to prove that if children are taught in their mother tongue, particularly in the foundational years (ages 3 to 8), then higher retention, higher proficiencies, lesser repetition of grades, and improved test scores are seen. The National Education Policy 2020 has also ‘emphasised’ on the use of mother tongue or local language as the medium of instruction till Class 5 while, recommending its continuance till Class 8 and beyond. The draft National Education Policy, 2019, prepared by a committee headed by scientist Dr Kasturirangan has recommended the three-language formula. As a medium of instruction: Wherever possible, the medium of instruction until at least Grade 5, but preferably till Grade 8 and beyond it will be the

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home language/mother-tongue/local language/regional language.

The three-language formula will continue to be implemented to promote multilingualism as well as promote national unity.

NEP states that there will be greater flexibility in the three-language formula. But no language will be imposed on any State.

To learn three languages will be the choice of States, regions, and students themselves, as long as at least two of the three languages are native to India.

The three languages learned by children will be the choices of States, regions, and of course the students themselves, so long as at least two of the three languages are native to India. In particular, students who wish to change one or more of the three languages they are studying may do so in Grade 6 or 7, as long as they are able to demonstrate basic proficiency in three languages (including one language of India at the literature level) by the end of secondary school,” it adds. From the implementation from, the policy says, there will be a major effort from both the central and state governments to invest in large numbers of language teachers in all regional languages around the country, and, in particular, for all languages mentioned in the Eighth Schedule of the Constitution of India.

11. Research Findings:

The new national education policy 2020 is a good policy as it aims at making the education flexible and multi-disciplinary to suit the needs of 21st century. As per the National Education Policy 2020, Exams will also be made ‘easier’. They will test primarily core competencies to eliminate the “Coaching Culture”. Board exam questions to have two types: a) Objective type with multiple-choice questions b) Descriptive type. Multiple-exit option for undergraduate programs gives institutions cover to stop tracking students dropping out due to socio-economic compulsions. The intent of policy seems to be ideal in many ways but it is the implementation where lies the key to success. Under the NEP 2020, the focus areas of the reforms seek to cultivate 21st century skills among students including critical thinking problem solving creativity and digital literacy.

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Conceptual Study of the National Education Policy 2020

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ABSTRACT

The New Education Policy announced by Government of India (NEP 2020) was a greeting change and fresh news amidst all the negativities surrounding the world due to the challenges posed by Covid- 19 pandemic. The announcement of NEP 2020 was purely unexpected by many. The changes that NEP 2020 has recommended were something that many educationists never noticed. Though the education policy has impacted school and college education equally, this article mainly focuses on NEP 2020 and its impact on Higher Education. This paper also outlines the salient features of NEP and analyses how they affect the existing education system.

Design/Methodology/Approach: The research questions of this study are pursued by means of a systematic theoretical analysis. We conducted this research through systematically searching and screening for relevant research articles through secondary sources and analyzing them with the purpose of answering our scientific study. This research is a descriptive study. The necessary secondary data was collected from various websites including those of Government of India, magazines, journals, other publications, etc. This data was then analysed and reviewed to arrive at the inferences and conclusions.

Expected Outcomes of National Education Policy 2020: The major focus of the NEP 2020 is to bring holistic and major changes in the educational system upgrading the levels. It aims to concentrate on bringing forth inclusiveness in the education system.

Keywords: Higher education, National education policy 2020, NEP-2020.

INTRODUCTION:

The National Education Policy (NEP) was approved by the Union Cabinet of India on July 28th, 2020. After a gap of 34 years, the Indian government consolidated feedback from 2.5 lakh village-level stakeholders to two national parliamentary level committees, over more than 50 months of consultations and workshops. However, the extent to which the policy has incorporated recommendations remains unknown. The National Policy on Education (NPE) is a policy formulated by the Government of India to promote

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education amongst India's people. The policy covers elementary education to colleges in both rural and urban India. The first NPE was promulgated by the Government of India by Prime Minister Indira Gandhi in 1968, the second by Prime Minister Rajiv Gandhi in 1986, and the third by Prime Minister Narendra Modi in 2020. The National Education Policy 2020 (NEP 2020), which was approved by the Union Cabinet of India on 29 July 2020, outlines the vision of India's new education system. The new policy replaces the previous National Policy on Education, 1986. The policy is a comprehensive framework for elementary education to higher education as well as vocational training in both rural and urban India. The policy aims to transform India's education system by 2021. The language policy in NEP is a broad guideline and advisory in nature; and it is up to the states, institutions, and schools to decide on the implementation. The NEP 2020 enacts numerous changes in India's education policy. It aims to increase state expenditure on education from around 4% to 6% of the GDP as soon as possible

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

The National Education policy 2020 has many initiatives to enhance the quality of the education system in India.

The objectives of this study on National Education Policy 2020 are:

- (1) To identify the salient features of NEP and analyses how they affect the existing school education system
- (2) To study the impact of New Education Policy 2020 on higher education.
- (3) To discuss the importance of various educational stages to be implemented as per NEP 2020
- (4) To examine the merits and the concerns of National Education Policy 2020.

METHODOLOGY:

This research is a descriptive study. The necessary secondary data was collected from various websites including those of Government of India, magazines, journals, other publications, etc. This data was then analysed and reviewed to arrive at the inferences and conclusions.

HIGHLIGHTS OF NATIONAL EDUCATION POLICY 2020 ON SCHOOL EDUCATION:

1. Early Childhood Care and Education (ECCE)

Extends the Right to Education eligibility window from 6-14 years to 3-18 years. With a goal of having 100 percent of children ‘school-ready’ by 2030, the policy pushes for universalisation of ECCE.

- Investment in infrastructure such as play equipment and child-friendly buildings, as well as continuous professional development (CPD) of ECCE teachers and anganwadi workers through a six-month

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certification programme, including some online components.

2. Foundational Literacy and Numeracy (FLN)

A three month preparatory course for students, access to digital content through energised textbooks (ETB-DIKSHA), student-led peer learning, and community tutoring are recommended as some of the means to achieve 100 percent foundational level (upto Grade 3) learning by 2025.

- Teacher vacancies to be filled in a time-bound manner, with a priority to disadvantaged areas and sections of the society.

3. Universal access to education at all levels

A commitment to achieve 100 percent Gross Enrolment Ratio (GER) across all levels by 2030.

- Investment in resources such as infrastructure and teachers for students till Grade 12; as well as ensuring social workers and counsellors are made available to students, so they can address factors contributing to dropout rates.
- Rigorous tracking of 100 percent of children, through a technology-based platform to ensure no one is left behind.
- Encouraging different public-private partnership school models to curtail the number of dropouts and out-of-school children.

4. Curriculum and pedagogy in schools

The policy encourages local languages to be the medium of instruction at least up to Grade 5; promotes bi-lingual education and textbooks for learning; as well as multiple languages at middle and secondary levels.

- The suggested 5+3+3+4 class system focuses on defining learning levels at each critical juncture, taking a multi-disciplinary approach, and reducing content by targeting core learning competencies.
- New age subjects such as coding and computational thinking (among others) introduced at a middle school level.
- Students can now choose subject courses in secondary school (primarily in arts, physical, and vocational education).

5. Testing and assessments

Focus on measurable learning outcomes at all levels of the newly proposed schooling system, with testing at 3rd, 5th, and 8th grade levels.

- Promoting formative assessments (those that are conducted on an ongoing basis covering smaller portions of the syllabus), peer assessment, and holistic progress reports, to measure the ongoing academic progress of the children.
- Student choice to be incorporated in the 10th and 12th grade board exams. The policy suggests doing so

by offering freedom of subject choice, allowing best of two attempts, and choice of difficulty (standard and higher level).

6. Teachers and teacher education

The policy proposes the minimum teacher education degree requirement to change from the current two year D.El.Ed/B.Ed degree to a four year B.Ed undergraduate programme, by 2030.

- Excessive teacher transfers to be halted, in principle, leading to better continuity with students, as also provision for local residence.
- Policy strongly suggests promotion based on merit, rather than on seniority and teaching level (elementary/primary/secondary). There are also options for vertical mobility of teachers, where high-performing teachers can be promoted to work at a district or state level.
- Promotion of blended learning teacher training programmes (MOOCs) for CPD of teachers and school principals, with at least 50 hours of CPD mandated per year.

7. Equitable and inclusive education

The ‘Gender Inclusion Fund’ which supports female and transgender students by driving state-level inclusion activities, developing sufficient infrastructure for safety, and targeted boarding.

- Special Education Zones (SEZs) and Kasturba Gandhi Balika Vidyalayas (KGBVs)/KVs to be set up in aspirational districts, with targeted focus on improving the quantity and quality of learning

8. School complexes

Re-organising smaller schools with very low enrolment into a ‘school complex’ structure, which connects 10-15 such small schools into one administrative unit, will help reduce school isolation, efficiently use teaching learning resources, and increase governance and accountability, especially in rural/Adivasi parts of India.

- Providing autonomy to plan and implement the initiative locally is a good idea in principle. School Complex Management Committee (SCMC) and public representation at a school complex level will encourage decentralised implementation as well as higher engagement of parents.

9. Standard setting and school accreditation

A strong push to bring in transparency and accountability across schools by setting standards through a dedicated agency (State Schools Standards Authority, or SSSA), which incorporates learning related indicators as well as student feedback into school ratings.

- Development, performance, and accountability to be three key pillars of supporting officers and teachers in the system, promoting greater alignment and clarity in job roles, periodic performance measurement structures, and timely feedback mechanisms.

DETAILED ANALYSIS OF IMPACT OF NEP ON HIGHER EDUCATION

Regulatory System of Higher Education:

HECI is aiming at reforming the higher education sector; the Bill will separate the Academic and Funding aspects of the sector. According to the new Bill, HECI will not have any financial powers. The funding processes which were handled by the University Grants Commission (UGC) will be taken care by the Ministry of Education, previously known as the Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD). This change however is expected to clear the regulatory mess in India’s Higher Education system. HECI is expected to have four independent verticals - National Higher Education Regulatory Council (NHERC) for regulation, General Education Council (GEC) for standard-setting, Higher Education Grants Council (HEGC) for funding, and National Accreditation Council (NAC) for accreditation. To have uniformity in education standards, a single umbrella body was always a requirement and this has been a vision of numerous educationalists. This is considered as the right step in streamlining education policy. However, to ensure quality of higher education, institutes must be measured on relevant parameters like research, industry linkages, placements and academic excellence, etc. If the HECI can manage this, the benefits to its biggest stakeholder, the youth of India, might be significant.

Graded Accreditation and Graded Autonomy:

The concept of “empowerment and autonomy to innovate” is one of the key features in NEP 2020 which supports a “phasing out” strategy from Affiliated Colleges to Autonomous Institutions. The increased flexibility offered to autonomous institutions also gives hope in curriculum enrichment. It also says that with appropriate accreditations, Autonomous degree-granting Colleges could evolve into Research-intensive or Teaching-intensive Universities, if they so aspire. The announcement of setting up Multidisciplinary Education and Research Universities (MERUs) in the country gives more hope. These institutions will be at par with the existing IITs and IIMs and will aim to showcase multidisciplinary education for the Indian students.

Another important change the NEP 2020 suggests that the National Testing Agency will serve as a premier, expert, autonomous testing organization to conduct entrance examinations for undergraduate and graduate admissions and fellowships in Higher Education Institutions. The high quality, range, and flexibility of the NTA testing services will enable most universities to use these common entrance exams - rather than having hundreds of universities each devising their own entrance exams - thereby drastically reducing the burden on students, universities and colleges, and the entire education system. It will be left up to individual universities and colleges to use NTA assessments for their admissions. It also surely helps the students to easily transfer their degrees and credits to universities abroad.

Internationalisation at home:

NEP 2020 also allows foreign universities and colleges to come to India and this brings out a challenge for the native institutions to improve the quality of education provided by them. The Indian higher education sector is buzzing all around as the opportunity of paving the way for foreign universities to set up campuses in the country. India has one of the largest networks of higher education systems in the world, with more than 900 universities and 40,000 colleges. But GER (Gross Enrolment Ratio) of India in higher education is 26.3%, which is significantly low when compared to other BRICS countries like Brazil (50%) or China (51%), and very much lower when compared with European and North American nations which would be more than 80%. India must achieve a significant growth in the area of global higher education for obtaining a sustainable economic growth, which should not be driven by natural resources, but by knowledge resources. As per the reports, India will need another more than 1,500 new higher education institutions by 2030 to accommodate a huge inflow of students, that's why the Indian government wants to promote FDIs (Foreign Direct Investment) and open up the ECB (External Commercial Borrowing) route to strengthen the capital investment for the education sector.

The ministry is also trying to boost India's image as an education centre because already more than 7 Lakhs of Indian students are studying abroad. So, the intention of this policy is that, allowing foreign universities will enable world-class education available locally at a significantly lower cost without travelling and will considerably reduce the human capital migrating to other countries for study and job prospects. According to the different global surveys, cross-border education is beneficial for the economy and brings a wider level of global awareness, culturally perceptive, and competitiveness. Foreign collaborations enable local institutes to design their curriculum in alignment with international pedagogy and offer a diverse portfolio of subjects and specialization to students.

More Holistic and Multidisciplinary Education:

The NEP 2020 claims that, a holistic and multidisciplinary education would aim to develop all capacities of human beings -intellectual, aesthetic, social, physical, emotional, and moral in an integrated manner. Such an education will help develop well-rounded individuals that possess critical 21st century capacities in fields across the arts, humanities, languages, sciences, social sciences, and professional, technical, and vocational fields; an ethic of social engagement; soft skills, such as communication, discussion and debate; and rigorous specialization in a chosen field or fields. The NEP 2020 envisions one large multidisciplinary Higher Education Institution (HEI) in or near every district, by 2030.

Towards the attainment of such a holistic and multidisciplinary education, the flexible and innovative curricula of all HEIs shall include credit-based courses and projects in the areas of community engagement

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and service, environmental education, and value-based education. Environment education will include areas such as climate change, pollution, waste management, sanitation, conservation of biological diversity, management of biological resources and biodiversity, forest and wildlife conservation, and sustainable development and living. Value-based education will include the development of humanistic, ethical, Constitutional, and universal human values of truth (satya), righteous conduct (dharma), peace (shanti), love (prem), nonviolence (ahimsa), scientific temper, citizenship values, and also life-skills; lessons in seva/service and participation in community service programmes will be considered an integral part of a holistic education.

As the world is becoming increasingly interconnected, Global Citizenship Education (GCED), a response to contemporary global challenges, will be provided to empower learners to become aware of and understand global issues and to become active promoters of more peaceful, tolerant, inclusive, secure, and sustainable societies. Finally, as part of a holistic education, students at all HEIs will be provided with opportunities for internships with local industry, businesses, artists, crafts persons, etc., as well as research internships with faculty and researchers at their own or other HEIs/research institutions, so that students may actively engage with the practical side of their learning and, as a by-product, further improve their employability.

The structure and lengths of degree programmes:

In the context of the National Education Policy 2020 scheme, any undergraduate degree in any institution will be of duration of three or four years. One can leave the degree within this period. Any educational institution will have to give to the student a diploma degree after the student completes two years of study, a degree after the student completes three years of study and a certificate to those students who complete one year of study in any professional or vocational course of their choice. The Government of India will also help in establishing an Academic Bank of Credit for storing the academic scores digitally. This will enable the institutions to count the credit at the end and put it in the degree of the student. This will be helpful for those individuals who might have to leave the course mid-way. They can start the course later on from where they left off and not start from the beginning once again. Even though NEP 2020 says that Higher education institutions will be given the freedom to start PG courses there may be some difficulty in designing One Year PG Degree for students who have completed 4 Year UG Degree and a Two Year PG Degree for students who have completed 3 Year UG Degree.

VARIOUS EDUCATIONAL STAGES TO BE IMPLEMENTED AS PER NEP 2020

Educational life-cycle and Features

1. Foundation Stage: Five years Foundational Stage provides basic education which is flexible,

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multilevel, play-based, activity-based, and discovery-based learning. Using time tested Indian traditions and cultures; this stage is continuously improved by research and innovation for the cognitive and emotional stimulation of children.

2. Preparatory Stage

Three years Preparatory stage consists of building on the play-, discovery-, and activity-based learning. In addition to it, this stage gradually introduces formal classroom learning with Text books. The focus is to expose different subjects to the students and prepare them to delve deeper into insights.

3. Middle school Stage

Three years of Middle school education focus on more abstract education concepts in each subject like sciences, mathematics, arts, social sciences, and humanities. Experiential learning is the method to be adopted in specialised subjects with subject teachers. Students are exposed to the semester system and yearly two class level examinations will be conducted.

4. Secondary education Stage

Four years of Secondary school education is designed to provide multidisciplinary subjects including Liberal Arts education. This stage will be built on the subject-oriented pedagogical and curricular style with greater depth, greater flexibility, greater critical thinking, and attention to life aspirations, Students are exposed to the semester system and will study 5 to 6 subjects in each semester. There will be Board exams at the end of 10th and 12th standards.

5. Under-graduation Education Stage

The Undergraduate degrees in every subject will be of either three- or four-year duration with multiple exit options including a certificate after passing first year, a diploma after passing second year, or a Bachelor 's degree after passing third year. The four years undergraduate degree programme is preferred with major, minors and research projects.

6. Post-graduation Education Stage

The Master's degree – a one-year for four years bachelor degree students, a two-year degree for three years bachelor degree students, and an integrated five-year degree with a focus on high quality research in the final year. The Masters' degree will consist of a strong research component to strengthen competence in the professional area and to prepare students for a research degree.

7. Research Stage: Research stage consists of pursuing high quality research leading to a Ph.D. in any core subject, multidisciplinary subject, or interdisciplinary subject for a minimum period of three to four years for full-time and part-time study respectively. During Ph.D. they should undergo 8-credit coursework in teaching/ education/ pedagogy related to their chosen Ph.D. subject. The earlier one-year MPhil programme is discontinued.

8. Lifelong learning

The NEP 2020 proposes lifelong learning and research to avoid human beings becoming obsolete in society in terms of knowledge, skills, and experience to lead a comfortable life. It is believed that education and research at any stage of life will give further maturity for satisfaction in life;

MERITS OF NEW EDUCATION POLICY 2020

The National Education Policy has been working to change the old education system by bringing modern and practical learning forms. It has numerous objectives and parameters that will cumulatively bring forth a methodical education system bringing in inclusiveness. The merits of the National Education Policy 2020 are as under-

- **Early Childhood Education-** The new National Education Policy was formed on the principle that a child's most important and formative years are from 3 to 8. It adopts the 5+3+3+4 model, where a child must start his education at 3 for a successful future.
- **Multi-Disciplinary Approach-** The NEP has created a strict division of Science, arts, and commerce in high school.
- **Comprehensive-** The New National Education Policy addresses the whole spectrum of education from preschool to doctoral studies and professional degrees to vocational training.
- **Easy on Regulations-** The National Education Policy believes in the prescription to free educational institutions (schools, colleges, and universities) from inspections. Instead, the students must lead the path of voluntary declaration and self-assessment.
- **Promotes Inclusion-** This Education Policy promotes the idea of creating inclusion funds to help children pursue education without worrying about social and educational disadvantages.
- **Holistic-** It aims to eradicate the problems of structural inequities, rampant commercialization, access asymmetries, and pedagogy.
- **Education and Skills Integration-** With the new NEP, vocational courses were introduced for practical education that provides internships that might compel society's vulnerable sections to send their children to schools to gain an education.
- **Allowing Foreign Universities-** According to the National Education Policy 2020, almost 100 foreign universities can set up their campus in India.
- **Made Education More Inclusive-** It suggests that the children's RTE (Right to Education) must be extended up to 18 years of age.

NATIONAL EDUCATION POLICY 2020 CONCERNS

The National Education Policy 2020 has successfully created impactful educational system changes. However, there are a few concerns related to the newly introduced policy, and these are-

- **Lack of clarity-** There is a lack of clarity regarding the Public Sector like Kendra Vidyalaya, state-run institutions, and municipal schools in the government strategies.

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- **Problems related to Anganwadis-** A lot of focus was pointed toward early schooling and childhood care, yet it faced a problem related to the changes that the Anganwadis.
- The National Education Policy 2020 report **failed to incorporate the ideas on contemporary global thinking** like critical thinking, emphasis on creativity, and the need for learning in the non-hierarchical and non-competitive ecosystem.
- **Persistent inequity & inequality-** It fails to address the problems of inequality and inequity.
- **Short-term solutions-** The concept of peer tutoring, sharing resources, volunteer teachers, and rationalizing the school system is not the long-term solution for a better education.
- **Scepticism-** NTA (National Testing Agency) has resulted in skepticism as the universities, and particular educational departments cannot conduct admissions autonomously because of the NTA.
- **Knowledge-Jobs Mismatch-** Since independence, the problem of the knowledge & skills imparted and the jobs have been a major concern, and NEP fails to explain this mismatch.

EXPECTED OUTCOMES OF NATIONAL EDUCATION POLICY 2020

The major focus of the NEP 2020 is to bring holistic and major changes in the educational system upgrading the levels. It aims to concentrate on bringing forth inclusiveness in the education system. National Education Policy 2020 aims for the following outcomes in the future-

- NEP wants to attain foundational learning and numeracy skills by 2025 via National Mission.
- It aims to universalize Secondary Education aligning with SDG 4 from ECCE within 10 years.
- To bring the Gross Enrolment Ratio to 100% in Pre-school to secondary level in the forthcoming years.
- To reintroduce 2 Cr out of School Children.
- It aims to prepare teachers for assessment reforms by 2023.
- By 2030, NEP aims to implement an equitable and inclusive Education System.
- The purpose of conducting the board exams should be to test the core concept of students and judge their application of knowledge.
- An individual student must be adapting at least one skill during their school time.
- There should be common learning standards in private and public schools.

CONCLUSION

The new education policy has a laudable vision, but its strength will depend on whether it is able to effectively integrate with the other policy initiatives of government like Digital India, Skill India and the New Industrial Policy to name a few, in order to effect a coherent structural transformation. Hence, policy linkages can ensure that education policy addresses to and learns from Skill India’s experience in engaging

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more dynamically with the corporate sector to shape vocational education curriculum in order to make it a success. There is also a necessity for more evidence-based decision-making, to adapt to rapidly evolving transmutations and disruptions. NEP has reassuringly provisioned for real-time evaluation systems and a consultative monitoring and review framework. This shall empower the education system to constantly reform itself, instead of expecting for a new education policy every decade for a shift in curriculum. This, in itself, will be a remarkable achievement. The NEP 2020 is a defining moment for higher education. Effective and time-bound implementation is what will make it truly path-breaking.

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B.Tech Civil Engineering
B.Tech Electronics & Comm. Engg.
B.Tech Cloud Tech. & Info. Security
B.Tech Data Science
B.Tech Nanotechnology
BPT Physiotherapy
B.Sc. Cardio Vascular Technology
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B.Sc. Hotel Management
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BCA Software Development
BCA Cloud Tech. & Info. Security
BCA Info. Security & Mobile Apps.
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BBA Aviation & Airport Mgmt.
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BBA Logistics & Supply Chain Mgmt.
BBA International Business
BBA Financial Services
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BHA Hospital Administration
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B.Com Int. Accounting with ACCA
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